

CTURE

H O G E S C H O O L

TU Delft BK 22-25

Midterm Research
Self-Evaluation Report

Bouwkunde

TU Delft BK 22-25

Midterm Research Self-Evaluation Report

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BK's research is a blend of humanities, social, data and engineering sciences

Faculty

The Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment (Bouwkunde, or BK in Dutch) is one of the eight faculties of TU Delft. Its research and education cover the full spectrum of design, engineering, planning, management, and data science in the built environment.

Bouwkunde is home to four departments: Architecture, Architectural Engineering + Technology (AE+T), Management in the Built Environment (MBE), and Urbanism.

The research conducted within these departments is evaluated periodically, every six years. This self-evaluation report has been compiled in the context of the so-called Midterm, which is usually organised halfway through this period, after three years. For pragmatic reasons, this Midterm was postponed by one year.

The Faculty itself is not subject to the Midterm evaluation; the departments are. This chapter is included in the report to support the departments' self-evaluations. It addresses the context and policies to which all departments are subject. Presenting these here avoids the need for each department to explain them separately in their respective chapters.

The Scope of BK's research

The faculty's research focuses specifically on improving the design and performance of buildings, districts, cities and regions to better meet the requirements and expectations of their users and communities. From that perspective, much of the research that is conducted can be understood as applied science, appealing to the curiosity and the needs of other researchers, practitioners and the broader public alike.

The research is a blend of humanities, social, data and engineering sciences. The humanities are strongest represented in the Architecture department, social sciences in the MBE and Urbanism departments, while the engineering sciences find their strongest representation in AE+T. Data sciences are covered by all departments.

The faculty introduced strategic and urgent themes (or initiatives) that combine the research interests of all four departments as platforms for collaboration. Dick van Gameren, the faculty's dean until early 2026, put three grand challenges on the agenda: climate change, the growing shortage of raw materials and increasing urban inequality, and linked these to six themes or strategies.

Sustainable urbanisation

Cities are the convergence point for major issues encompassing space, social inequality, climate, energy, water, food, and raw materials. In the face of ongoing global urbanisation, how can we ensure the safety, accessibility, and liveability of cities for all, both now and in the future?

Healthy cities

The link between health and the built environment has become self-evident, particularly in the wake of the pandemic. How can we design buildings and public spaces that positively contribute to the health of those who live and work there?

Heritage with future value

Our existing built environment, our heritage, must be made future-proof. What implications does this hold for the assessment, management, and necessary adaptations of what already exists?

Climate adaptation and energy transition

A redesign of the built environment is imperative to counteract further global warming and address other climate change related impacts. What will the buildings, cities and landscapes of the future look like?

Digitalisation and artificial intelligence

The use of data and digital solutions in the conception, realisation, and management of the built environment will play an ever more pivotal role in the future. How do we safely and responsibly lead the digital transformation of our built environment, and in what ways can values, data and computational methods come together to contribute to the design of future living spaces?

Circularity in the built environment

It is necessary to increase resource efficiency by closing, narrowing and slowing loops in the built environment. Circular design principles help mitigate climate change, reduce energy consumption, recover biodiversity, reduce pollution and lower geopolitical tensions. What are these circular design principles, and how can we implement them?

Joint PhDs

Through funding from the faculty and the University Board, twelve PhD candidates were recruited to undertake research that cuts across these strategic themes. The PhD projects facilitated cross-departmental collaboration by ensuring that supervisors were drawn from multiple disciplines in different departments, thereby enriching the experience of the PhD candidates in their theoretical, methodological and empirical engagements.

Positioning BK's research

The faculty is on course to maintain the quality of its research, as well as its excellent international academic reputation as a leading design academy; to be an international platform for innovation in architectural design, architectural engineering, urban planning, landscape architecture, real estate management, housing, urban studies and geoinformation; and to be a platform for debate on current societal themes in the fields of architecture and the built environment.

Although ranking does have its shortcomings, an indicator of our achievements is the fact that TU Delft obtained a top ranking in the field-specific ranking for Architecture and the Built Environment of the QS World University Ranking. On average, TU Delft ranks 3rd here, just behind UCL and MIT.

The faculty's strategy is firmly focused on positioning itself as a leading research and design-oriented institute for architecture and the built environment, with strong roots in the Randstad region as one of the key metropolitan regions in Europe, and with a firm international ambition. The frameworks needed for this mission are already in place:

- The local Graduate School of Architecture and the Built Environment has established itself in the faculty as the main environment for conducting PhD research and providing doctoral education;
- The Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS) by TU Delft, Wageningen University and MIT. AMS is a strategic institute in Amsterdam that valorises TU Delft's knowledge and expertise in the field of metropolitan solutions;
- 4TU.Built Environment Center, a centre within the 4TU.Federation, the Federation of the four Dutch Universities of Technology: TU Delft, TU Eindhoven, Twente University and Wageningen University;
- Disciplinary Council for Designing Built Environment, a collaboration of TU Delft, TU Eindhoven, Twente University, Wageningen University and the University of Groningen directly linked to the agenda setting of the Sector Plan Natural Science and Technology II;
- LDE, the alliance between Leiden University, TU Delft and Erasmus University Rotterdam;
- Convergence EUR, Erasmus MC, TU Delft, the collaboration between academic centres in the metropolitan region Rotterdam-The Hague;
- OSK, the National Research School for Art History;
- NETHUR, The Netherlands Graduate School of Urban and Regional Research;
- NIG, the Research School for Public Administration & Political Science in the Netherlands and Flanders.

Social safety

But not all is well in Delft. In 2024, a report by the Education Inspectorate concluded that the board of TU Delft "neglects" the care of its employees, leading to an "increased risk of social insecurity for all employees". According to the Inspectorate, the problems are serious enough to speak of "mismanagement" – a judgement severe enough to prompt government intervention.

The Inspectorate investigated 148 reports about intimidation, shouting, sexually suggestive comments, racism, fear of reporting abuses, and managers who sided with the person responsible for the unsafe situation, among other things.

The report caused quite a stir among staff and board members. What followed was a strong debate between board and staff, resulting in an action plan to address the issues, and in its wake many meetings, workshops, trainings and changes in the way we work.

Two years later, in 2026, the Education Inspectorate published its report on the remedial investigation of compliance with legislation and regulations. During this follow-up assessment, the Inspectorate examined how much the welfare of staff had improved since it was found to have been seriously neglected in 2024. The Inspectorate states that care for staff has now been sufficiently restored. Consequently, the Inspectorate will not carry out any further supervision.

As confirmed in the Inspectorate's report, TU Delft has improved its policies and facilities aimed at creating and maintaining a socially safe environment over the past two years. These include the integrity and social safety reporting point, the Integrity Office, confidential advisors, ombuds officers, the company doctor, the university social worker, the complaints committee on undesirable behaviour, and the TU Delft Code of Conduct.

But as it goes with these processes, culture change is slow and requires an enduring effort.

BK as a vibrant research environment

Over the past five years, BK has laid the foundations for inter- and transdisciplinary research. A key lesson from these efforts points to the need to create a vibrant and safe space for cross-disciplinary dialogue, as different disciplines are rooted in a diverse range of theoretical perspectives, methodological approaches, and empirical interests.

Such space is necessary to enable exploration across different perspectives, approaches and interests, and to harness the full potential of inter- and transdisciplinary work. Furthermore, engagement with non-academic societal actors is becoming increasingly important to ensure that the findings of academic research can be translated into meaningful societal impact. Five guiding principles were co-created with researchers across the faculty's four departments.

Cultivating a Dynamic Faculty Research Environment

In cultivating a dynamic research environment, we value transdisciplinary connections, engagement and collaboration between disciplines and departments, and between academic and non-academic parties. For meaningful exchanges to occur across departmental boundaries and between BK and civil society, there must be respect for differences and for the contributions that arise from diverse perspectives. This requires the development of, and participation in, more interdepartmental activities and programmes. At the same time, BK continues to encourage and facilitate applications for individual grants through a comprehensive organisational process.

Ensuring that Research Feeds into Education and Informs It

The reciprocal relationship between research and education – that is, research informs education and education informs research – is essential for developing the next generation of leaders in academia and practice. A stronger research base enables us to instil key academic attitudes (such as critical thinking, research skills and ethics) throughout the educational journey. This requires more space within curricula to introduce research areas and directions, as well as greater opportunities for knowledge exchange

between colleagues and departments. This can also be facilitated through Student–Practitioner–Researcher learning labs. It is envisaged that there will be an increase in education-based scientific publications and research-based educational materials, including MSc and PhD theses that integrate research and design.

Staying at the Forefront of Academic and Societal Priority Fields

Central to this principle is the design and production of future-ready built environments. Such environments consider developments in climate adaptation and resilience, regeneration and the preservation of the built environment, while maintaining critical perspectives on architecture and engaging with digitisation and Artificial Intelligence. A holistic, systems-based understanding is fundamental to this vision, building on diverse research expertise within transdisciplinary contexts. Collaboration – rather than competition – and civic impact are central.

Addressing Pressing Issues for Broader Society

Addressing global and local challenges in the design, production and use of the built environment through transdisciplinary engagement is a central principle in responding to pressing societal issues. The housing crisis, resource and energy scarcity, and developments in digitisation and Artificial Intelligence raise important questions about justice and human-centredness in promoting healthy environments. How nature is incorporated into the production of built environments for collective wellbeing is also a key concern. Transdisciplinary research and education – potentially linked to (urban) living laboratories and pilot projects – can increase public awareness, acceptance and involvement, while targeted research initiatives can provide space for academic and non-academic partners to co-produce knowledge. In this way, BK can strengthen trust in academia.

Growing a New Generation of Assistant and Associate Professors

Diversity and respect for interdisciplinarity in research and education are essential for fostering a collaborative environment in which all academic staff can grow and actively contribute to society. BK must value diversity in academic profiles and maintain the flexibility to adapt these profiles over time. It is important to cultivate a safe and collaborative working environment. Our thought leadership can contribute to society through strong public engagement. In recognising and rewarding ('Erkennen en Waarden'), we have an opportunity to acknowledge the value of diverse academic outputs. Increased cross-departmental research days and the provision of strategic funding beyond seed funding can play an important role. The aim is to foster synergistic networks of independent scholars (already at assistant professor level) who interact coherently within and beyond TU Delft, while maintaining a healthy work-life balance.

Graduate School – the environment for conducting PhD research and receiving training

Context, supervision and quality assurance

The Graduate School of Architecture and the Built Environment (A+BE) continues to be a key vehicle for supporting doctoral researchers and their supervisors, and for providing doctoral education. By 2025, BK has more than 285 active PhD candidates from all over the world. This growth in number, compared with 260 around 2021, reflects investments in recruiting new faculty members, as well as successes in securing research funding from sources such as the Dutch Research Funding Agency (NWO), Horizon Europe, industry and government.

In the last period, the focus was on improving the timely completion rates of PhD candidates. Along with efforts to improve social safety at the workplace, activities included regular lunches with PhD candidates, PhD Days and intervision sessions for supervisors and PhD candidates to facilitate the sharing of experiences, successes and struggles. Furthermore, we also increased the provision of discipline-related courses to strengthen our doctoral education offering.

These activities have paid off, with the average duration over the last five years falling to just under five years for all categories of PhD candidates (including those on standard contracts, bursaries and external collaborations). Furthermore, BK has also decided to stop the recruitment of self-funded PhD candidates, since self-funded PhD candidates have tended to struggle with rising costs of living in the Netherlands. By 2030, the A+BE Graduate School aims to have achieved the following objectives:

- Maintain current efforts to increase the percentage of timely completed theses (within 5 years) to 60%;
- Select strategically not only on personal quality of scholarship candidates, but also on the alignment of their research topics with the strategic themes of the faculty.;
- Create more space for intervision for PhD candidates and supervisors;
- Encourage cooperation between different departments (and with other faculties) in offering doctoral education and sharing research outcomes and impacts.

Selection and admission procedures

Standard PhD candidates (mostly financed by externally funded projects) are recruited via internationally advertised calls. The Human Resources department developed guidelines to ensure good recruitment practices. After recruitment, the TU Delft GS initiates the registration process, followed by a further welcome at the Faculty GS.

GS A+BE developed a central procedure for the applications of PhD candidates with a scholarship or other external funding. The A+BE Graduate Office screens the

documentation and forwards it to the relevant professor(s), who concentrate on scanning the quality of the candidate and the proposal. Full proposals are sent to the relevant professors and selection committees within the departments. The selections are based on the quality of the proposal, the candidate's CV and the performance in one or more (online) interviews.

Academic Career Track

TU Delft implemented a new policy that replaced the so-called tenure-track: the Academic Career Track. All new assistant professors in the Academic Career Track start with a temporary employment contract for 18 months, where a permanent employment contract will be offered after a positive evaluation based on confidence in results and development. The Academic Career Track takes a maximum of 8 years.

During the Academic Career Track, it will be determined whether an academic career within TU Delft suits the ACT'er and whether (s)he could eventually progress to the position of associate professor. If the evaluation is positive, the ACT'er obtains a position as associate professor. Furthermore, (s)he will have the prospect of advancing to the position of full professor.

Development programme

Throughout the Academic Career Track, TU Delft offers an ACT Development Programme, consisting of a wide range of training courses and instruments in all areas of the academic career. Based on the ACT Personal Development Plan, and depending on talents, experiences and preferences, the ACT'er decides which recommended and in-depth training courses to follow in addition to the required training courses. The ACT'er will be supported in this by the manager/supervisor, mentor, fellow Academic Career Track assistant professors and colleagues. In the Development Programme, new assistant professors will go through three phases:

- Onboarding: to become familiar with TU Delft, get to know the working environment and lay the foundation for development for the coming years.
- Mid-term: learning all aspects of education and obtaining the University Teaching Qualification (UTQ). In addition, working on project management skills, learning how to apply for grants and how to adapt leadership style and use it in academic work.
- End-term: delving into the development of education, working on broadening research, learning how to manage a larger team, and developing a sustainable vision of the future in all areas of science.

At the end of the Academic Career Track, the assistant professor should be ready to make the transition to associate professor.

Recognition & Rewards

It has been a long-held wish among the Dutch academic community to assess the performance of scientific staff differently. In line with the [national position paper Room for everyone's talent](#) and its Impact for a Better Society strategy, TU Delft has now formulated a perspective on the recognition and rewards of academics.

The TU Delft Recognition & Rewards committee has investigated how the ambitions set out in the national position paper can be realised and what should be the focus within TU Delft. Dialogue sessions with representatives of various academic communities provided valuable input and insights. These included placing less emphasis on the number of publications, and greater emphasis on the other domains, such as education, teamwork and impact. This broader form of recognition and appreciation is better suited to the current core tasks of knowledge and educational institutions and what society requires. The conclusions and actions are captured in the TU Delft Recognition & Rewards Perspective 2021–2024.

There have been many actions to increase the possibilities to pursue a variety of career paths linked to the various goals and values of TU Delft: research, education and innovation. These will be reinforced by this new perspective on Recognition & Rewards. The resulting projects focus on building on talent and building excellent teams to support the needed cultural change. The next step is to recruit project leads for the different projects and to kick-start the Recognition & Rewards programme together with the TU Delft community.

The modernisation of the system of Recognition and Rewards is very much connected to the university's Open Science programme. To create impact for a better society, TU Delft wishes to take Open Science to the next level: a situation in which Open Science has become the default way of practising research and education, the "information era" has become the "open era", and everybody involved is recognised, rewarded and stimulated in the best way possible.

Open Science

TU Delft holds a prominent position in Open Science and Open Education and envisions expanding in those areas. Its Open Science programme includes four Open Science initiatives (Open Access, FAIR Data & Software, Civic Engagement, Open Hardware), in addition to three Open Education initiatives (Open Educational Resources, Open Pedagogy, Open Learning Systems).

The effort responds to developments in society and within TU Delft. Core values include equity, privacy, safety and security. Important preconditions to these values are legal

aspects, recognition and rewards, and knowledge security. TU Delft sees Open Science as a valuable means of contributing to a just society and an open research and education culture. The aim here is to operate as openly as possible and as closed as necessary.

Open access and data management have become integral parts of research at the faculty and TU Delft as a whole. Open access is facilitated through three main actions:

- Collective agreements between Dutch universities and publishers;
- The TU Delft Open Science Fund, which reimburses APCs;
- Inclusion of secondary publishing rights in the Dutch Copyright Act.

By 2025, virtually all academic articles published by TU Delft staff have become open access.

Data Management

Data management is supported through faculty-embedded Data Stewards who provide disciplinary support for research data management and open-science practices. Every TU Delft faculty has a dedicated Data Steward to answer questions, provide advice and help develop appropriate solutions for research data management and research output sharing, such as:

- Tailored consultations on best data management practices, including suitable data storage, first-stage ethics and privacy compliance issues, and long-term data archiving;
- Project support regarding open science and research data management requirements at the grant writing stage and project implementation stage;
- Assistance with data management and open science requirements in line with national and European research funders' policies and journals' requirements;
- Information about data repositories, including the 4TU.Centre for Research Data.

Cutbacks

The previous Dutch government cut back on education and research. As a result, TU Delft had to reduce spending by up to €79 million per year from 2028. The faculties were tasked to economise by 10%, or €5.1 million in the case of BK. Effectively, this means that those who leave the faculty (for instance due to retirement) will not be replaced until the faculty hits its target in 2030.

Case studies

Sector Plan Natural Science and Technology II

In the 2018 coalition agreement, the Dutch government allocated 60 million euros annually to university research and education in the natural and technical sciences (Sector Plan for Natural Sciences and Technology). A second injection of 90 million euros was added to this in 2022 (Sector Plan for Natural Sciences and Technology II).

These sector plans strengthen the foundations of research and education in these sectors, partly by attracting new scientific talent. In doing so, they create stability and breathing space for the universities. Furthermore, the sector plans encourage collaboration and joint, focused decision-making between and within institutions. With these boosts, the sectors can take a significant step forward.

The so-called Design Engineering Sciences (OIW) were not included in the first sector-plan Natural Science and Technology. To overcome this they formulated an own agenda that was to be integrated in the Second Sectorplan. TU Delft's Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment took the lead in formulating the part of the agenda that addressed the Design of the Built Environment ("Ontwerp Gebouwde Omgeving), together with partners from 4TU Built Environment (Wageningen University, University of Twente and Eindhoven University of Technology) and the University of Groningen.

Ontwerp Gebouwde Omgeving (OGO)

Ontwerp Gebouwde Omgeving (OGO) is an applied scientific field concerned with the analysis, design, engineering, planning and management of the built environment. The discipline encompasses architecture, urban planning, landscape architecture, structural engineering, construction management, spatial planning and development. As such, the design of the built environment covers all aspects of spatial design across the whole of the Netherlands. This includes the development, dissemination and application of new knowledge, as well as links with related disciplines. Research and teaching within OGO focus on improving the design, performance and experience of buildings, neighbourhoods, districts, cities and regions, to meet the wishes, requirements and expectations of owners, users and society on a scientific basis.

OIW Technologie en Maatschappij in Balans: Sectorbeeld

OIW Vraag en Capaciteit in Balans: Sectorplan

OGO underscored that the Netherlands faces major transformations across the country: the energy transition and climate adaptation, circularity and sustainability of the existing housing stock and infrastructure, the housing crisis, sustainable and smart urbanisation, a healthy living environment, buildings for health and healthcare, future-proof heritage, and a sustainably designed rural landscape.

The discipline needs to innovate to address new knowledge questions where there is simultaneously a high level of societal urgency, such as the expansion of the housing stock (new-build) and the upgrading of the existing built environment in view of the major transitions (repurposing, circularity, sustainability, energy transition, etc.) and necessary restructuring in rural areas (such as nitrogen, energy generation, water management). It is essential here that design-oriented engineering sciences are combined with the humanities, public administration and social sciences.

To facilitate innovation in the field, the design of the built environment will increasingly draw on new key enabling technologies and key enabling methodologies through design-led research, including digitalisation, artificial intelligence, and virtual/augmented/mixed reality.

This requires additional efforts to develop knowledge, skills, teaching resources and pedagogical methods. At the same time, the sector has for years been grappling with growing student numbers, which in some universities are even regulated by a numerus clausus, whilst societal challenges are leading to greater demand for well-trained engineers.

Challenges for the universities involved in the Sector Plan

- Innovation in teaching and course provision: there is a need for engineers who can think in terms of history, context and theory, and who utilise new key enabling technologies to address complex challenges holistically and make the country liveable and future-proof. This requires innovative, structural adjustments to the curriculum;
- Refining research profiles: the major transitions call for the strengthening and expansion of design-oriented research capacity to respond to national and international knowledge needs and urgent bottlenecks across the entire built environment;
- Structural funding: the discipline plays a crucial role in the liveability and future-proofing of the Netherlands as a whole. However, design does not have a fundamental place in the programmes and funds of the government and NWO. As a result, the necessary resources for the design disciplines are not readily accessible.

An injection of € 2.8 million annually

The Sector Plan resulted in 4.4 million euros of funding annually for the faculties involved in OGO, of which TU Delft's Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment has a share of 2.8 million, which translates into 14 permanent positions and additional PhDs or support staff distributed equally over all four departments.

The Sector Plan funds are being used to further develop knowledge and incorporate it into education regarding the following aspects:

- Investment in small-scale, design-oriented education linked to multidisciplinary academic research. This means investing in both teaching staff and academic staff;
- Innovation and digitalisation in the physical and institutional design of buildings, outdoor spaces, infrastructure and landscapes. This includes research into and development of design methodologies, concepts and solutions for urbanisation and the organisation of the agricultural landscape with a view to sustainability and climate adaptation, multifunctional land use, the integration of infrastructure systems, healthcare, and heritage approaches based on a circular economy approach. Investments in (living or digital) labs, materials, technical support staff, public participation and open science to accommodate the experimental and iterative nature of design-oriented engineering sciences;
- Structural funding for PhD students and postdoctoral positions to purposefully accelerate the acquisition of new knowledge in key areas, for example as part of induction packages for newly appointed academic staff or to be deployed strategically to strengthen specific groups where the balance within a faculty or discipline so requires.

BK LABS

To support the research and teaching by the departments, the faculty has established a framework that combines the various laboratory initiatives that have emerged over the years: BK Labs.

The faculty observed that the research labs lacked clarity on decision-making and (day-to-day) finances. Each of the research labs had separate leadership with few powers. Overarching representation in the faculty structure was lacking, and visibility in the organisation was low. To remedy the situation, the faculty made a good start by clustering the first batch of labs in the west wing of the faculty building, thus increasing recognisability and providing an opportunity to improve logistics, management, accessibility and strategy around the labs. The faculty took over responsibility for daily management while the departments remained autonomous regarding teaching and research.

BK Labs facilitate novel ideas across a range of disciplinary fields and address relevant social issues, such as promoting energy saving and improving the sustainability of the built environment. Existing labs include:

- Biobased Materials Lab;
- Bucky Lab;
- Data Refinery Lab;
- Environmental Research in Climate (ERiC) Lab;
- Geo-Database Management Centre;
- GlassLab;
- Heritage & Technology Lab;
- Hortus Botanicus;
- Laboratory for Additive Manufacturing in Architecture (LAMA);
- MATE lab;
- Model Hall;
- Product Development Lab;
- Robotic Building Lab;
- SenseLab;
- XR-Design Lab.

Over the last five years, the BK Labs have grown in number and capability, and a few more have been very recently established. They are playing an increasingly important role in both research and education, and together they form a significant and distinctive critical mass. Each lab has a distinctive vision and mandate of its own. The next steps for the BK Labs involve setting a shared vision and strategy that optimises efficiency, ensures continuity, and fosters the growth of BK Labs by, for example, promoting the sharing of laboratory facilities and technical staff across research and education.

New BK Labs initiatives are strongly linked to the six strategic faculty themes and new initiatives in the field of education and research.

XR Design Lab Cave

Data Refinery Lab

XR-Design Lab for the Built Environment

Recently, BK Labs established the Extended Reality (XR) Design Lab for the Built Environment – a laboratory for design-oriented research and education using Virtual, Augmented and Mixed Reality. The lab is a state-of-the-art facility for analysing, understanding, exploring, experiencing, visualising and designing the built environment across all scales, from building to landscape, and will act as a driver of digital innovation within the faculty.

The lab will strengthen design-oriented research and education by integrating XR technologies in three main domains:

- Scientific knowledge development – developing methods and insights about and for design through immersive, data-driven simulations using machine learning;
- Design exploration and experimentation – generating and testing ideas in virtual environments with real-time feedback;
- Education and knowledge transfer – embedding XR in curricula through virtual excursions, simulations and interactive design studios.

Over the next five years, the XR Design Lab will evolve into a faculty-wide innovation ecosystem that connects research, design and education through immersive technologies.

Data Refinery Lab

The Data Refinery Lab is a new space within BK Labs dedicated to exploring how architects, planners and engineers can experiment directly with source data to advance quantitative, multimodal, data-informed design practices. The lab aims to:

- Formalise and share knowledge on how built environment datasets are created – how raw data such as images, videos, architectural drawings and maps are curated, refined and published in ways that are both ethical and legally sound;
- Make BK's data assets open and FAIR – findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable – for research and education worldwide, positioning TU Delft as a hub for open architectural datasets and refinement pipelines;
- Create machine-learnable datasets that enable the development of intelligent systems capable of recognising spatial patterns in architectural and urban data, thereby facilitating the efficient navigation of large datasets and the formulation of impactful design hypotheses;

Through weekly data chats, educational workshops, invited talks and lectures, the lab aims to build a stronger data culture within the faculty.

BioBuild Lab

The TU Delft BioBuild Lab is a new research and education laboratory focused on exploring biobased materials. It is funded through close collaboration between the Executive Board and BK, and is located at the Green Village. The lab provides a design and fabrication space for full-scale (1:1) timber and biobased prototypes. The building will offer space, professional tools and ancillary equipment to support students and researchers in the hands-on fabrication and testing of experimental structures and constructions, helping to advance the faculty's future-facing, climate-driven construction agenda.

The lab's design – comprising entirely timber, glass and recycled materials – is conceived as a didactic demonstration of BK's commitment to progressive sustainable architecture and engineering. The opening of the building is scheduled for spring 2027.

Hortus Botanicus

The TU Delft Hortus Botanicus became part of BK on 1 January 2026. It is a 'living lab', an educational showcase space and a public botanical garden. This combination creates a unique place in both the city of Delft and TU Delft. The Hortus includes several dedicated research areas, in addition to a diverse 2.4-hectare site featuring an arboretum, an herb garden, a water garden and several glasshouses.

The Hortus is utilised as an experimental field lab by a growing number of TU Delft departments and faculties, as well as local and national organisations, to host and showcase projects such as building with nature, biodiversity, urban greenery, sustainable agriculture, bio-inspired innovations and biobased materials. Having been redesignated as a research facility in April 2024, its research and educational opportunities will be expanded, particularly within BK, while continuing to develop collaborations with other faculties and organisations across the TU Delft community. The in-house plant expertise of the Hortus staff, together with its facilities, enables the Hortus both to support and actively contribute to nature-based and environmental projects.

Hortus Botanicus TU Delft

In the coming years, the aim is to continue renovating and upgrading the facilities, particularly the historical Van Iterson Glasshouses, to ensure they endure, evolve and become future-proof. At the same time, a growing number of research spaces and sections have been and will continue to be developed. In addition, educational spaces will be created to showcase research projects to a wider audience. The Hortus looks forward to collaborating across multiple disciplines to strengthen the faculty, and to being strengthened by the faculty in return.

CBE Hub

The Circular Built Environment Hub (CBE Hub) is a cross-departmental initiative that advances a broader movement toward circularity in the built environment. The hub was established as an interdisciplinary platform for integrating circular economy and regenerative principles into the built environment in a systemic way. It fosters collaboration between researchers and educators at the Faculty and serves as a space for engagement with public, private, and academic stakeholders. It operates as an inclusive platform driven by the active participation of its members, who contribute to ongoing discussions and share their research and outputs related to circularity. In return, they benefit from increased visibility and new connections.

Who we are

The CBE Hub accounts for more than 70 members and has a non-hierarchical organisation. A steering committee channels all activities and guides the Hub's development. At present, the steering committee comprises dr. Alex Wandl (Urbanism), dr.ir. Olga Ioannou (AET), dr. Vitalija Danivska, and dr. Ilaha Abasli as academic staff representatives, as well as Nicolet Mansveld-Olsthorn and Romy Fischer as support staff representatives. The Hub also supports the faculty's PhD group of researchers working on circularity.

CBE's approach

The Hub has a unique approach to circularity by connecting across all scales: from materials to components to buildings, and from neighbourhoods to cities to regions. Circularity calls for a systemic approach and is therefore situated in the connection of each scale with the six aspects of technology, management, design, economy, resource flows and the dynamic relations of all stakeholders involved. Our tentative definition for a CBE reads:

The Circular Built Environment (CBE) is a system designed for slowing, narrowing and closing resource loops at different spatial-temporal levels, which enables a society to live within planetary boundaries, by transitioning cultural, environmental, economic, spatial, and social values towards a sustainable way of living.

Our Vision

The CBE Hub is determined to continue its systematic efforts to facilitate the transition to a circular and regenerative society. We will continue expanding our network and increasing our impact by forming strategic partnerships with individuals and organisations at different levels. We will also continue to offer a safe space for collective reflection and experimentation.

At Faculty level, a second round of definitions and philosophy workshops will produce a second position paper on value transition. Meanwhile, we will continue to support our students and their circular endeavours through teaching and graduation.

At Campus level, CBE Hub has formed and will continue to form alliances with representatives from other faculties, TGV, Hortus Botanicus, and the upcoming Blue Village, and has a close link with the newly established Materials Movement.

At Regional level, we aim to develop an LLL festival to bring together partners from academia and industry for training and networking. At International level, we will continue to promote the CBE Hub research and education activities and strengthen our network with new partners through the through the Circular & Regenerative Built Environment Collective (CiRBEC) and the several European projects we are participating in or leading.

At National level, the CBE Hub will strengthen collaboration with other educational institutions through 4TU and LDE, but also other Dutch organisations and foundations. It also continues to grow its links to industry and practice, with several of them joining CBE Hub monthly meetings and the public debates. Many of the CBE Hub members' research projects are funded by NWO, further establishing a strong network of partners from Dutch Universities.

What we do – RESEARCH

The CBE Hub members lead or are part of several European or national research projects. For these activities, we embrace a living lab approach to translate and test new findings through live-scale projects and experiments in a cooperative effort between scholars, public institutions, industry, involving students and users;

- Several CBE Hub research projects already seek to integrate principles of circularity and circular economy into urban and spatial planning. [ASSET, Pop Machina, REPAIR, Cities of Making, Circular Area Development Binckhorst, TU Delft Sustainable Campus Initiative, Campus NL];
- A part of the CBE Hub research involves developing policies and incentives and changing behavioural patterns across the key domains of building and construction. [Trancibo, SUBLIME, Facades Leasing, AEGIR, EIT Raw Materials IRTC & SusCritMat, Samen Versnellen: het ontwikkelen van Het Nieuwe Normaal (HNN), ACT];
- A large body of research supported by the CBE Hub aims at decreasing the level of dependency on global material resources while also exploring synergistic opportunities between value chains. [CINDERELA, FCRBE, SeRaMCo, AEGIR, Lean Manufacturing, CiRCLETECH, FoWaBa-Bio, MASS, Biobased Materials Catalogue, Intrinsically Circular, FABRIX];
- CBE Hub research expands into research on circular education. [NEB Academy, Collaboration with Zuyd University of Applied Sciences, Circular Impulse Initiative].

Read more about our RESEARCH here: <https://www.tudelft.nl/bk/onderzoek/onderzoeksthemas/circular-built-environment/projects>

1st CBE Summer School, 2022

What we do – EDUCATION

The Hub has developed a multifaceted programme of learning activities for on-campus and online education:

- On-campus courses or course modules on CBE, such as the Circular Product Design Technoledge (AET) and graduation projects;
- Online courses for an international audience interested in circularity in the form of MOOCs, namely the Circular Economy for a Sustainable Built Environment (since 2020), CRM, Sustainable Building with Timber;
- Online education courses for professionals are developed up to the level of individual consulting of companies, namely the Circular Building Products for a Sustainable Built Environment (since 2021), and Spatial Circularity Strategies for Sustainable Regional Development (since 2021);
- Teaching the teachers programmes, namely the 'Circularity for Educators' and 'Educators for Circularity' online platforms as well as live training programmes for the faculty's staff members (funded by Kwaliteitvoorschotmiddelen, WSV);

2nd CBE Summer School, 2023

- The Circular Design Atlas, as a repository of analysed circular case studies across all scales of the BE (peer-to-peer learning);
- The Circularity in the Built Environment Graduation Awards recognise the contribution BK graduation students make to the transition toward a circular built environment and further stimulate research and innovation in the field of circularity in the built environment. The prizes are awarded and judged by the Circular Built Environment Hub of the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment;
- A yearly Summer School on Circularity in the Built Environment (since 2022);
- A newly established pilot programme for developing cross-level educational exchanges in collaboration with Zuyd University of Applied Sciences with an overall duration of four years.

Our collaborations

- The 4TU Domain Acceleration Team (DAT) on Circularity and Sustainability. Together we seek to establish strategic agendas to secure funding and accelerate the transition to a circular society. These efforts are described in a white paper published in March 2024, entitled: Accelerating the transition to a Circular and Sustainable Built Environment in 2035: Role and vision of the four Dutch Technical Universities (https://www.4tu.nl/bouw/Research/Circularity_and_Sustainability/).

3rd CBE Summer School, 2024

- The Circular Educators' Network (CEN). Established in November 2024, the network currently comprises more than 60 partners from 22 institutions and 19 countries, mainly in Europe. The CEN initiative is a continuation of the 2022 Symposium on Architectural Education in Times of Uncertainty. Partners of the network have been working together and have already identified several themes they are interested in pursuing further together.
- The BauHow5 network & the IDEA League network. We frequently collaborate with partners of the two networks in research projects and educational activities. IDEA: [1] We were invited to participate in the POLIMI 2024 Summer School. The CBE Hub was represented by Cecilia Furlan; [2] Postdoc researcher Stanimira Markova (RWTH) visited us for two months (May-June 2025) thanks to the IDEA League fellowship programme (AET/ supervised by Olga Ioannou).
- UCL. Consolidated in autumn 2023 by Ellen van Bueren and Joanna Williams, the collaboration with UCL has already produced frequent and systematic exchanges between researchers (TUD public lecture by Joanna Williams took place 18/9/2023) and a book entitled, *Going Circular: Unlocking the potential of regions and cities to drive the circular economy transition*. For more on the collaboration please visit: <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/global/news/2024/mar/ucl-and-delft-university-technology-scale-circular-economy-collaboration>

4th CBE Summer School, 2025

- Campus Real Estate Facility Management (CREFM) group. Collaboration with CREFM started as early as 2022. Efforts to strengthen the rapport culminated in 2023, leading to one Postdoc position for two years and several smaller scale on-campus projects, namely the Biobased Catalogue, The Reuse Catalogue, and the CRM project (ongoing).
- Zuyd University of Applied Sciences. Since September 2025, Zuyd and TUD have been collaborating on developing a cross-level circular education programme. Our strong alliance further strengthens CBE Hub's connection with the European Center for Circular Building Transformation.

Our OUTREACH | INTERNAL

- Monthly lunch meetings are organised that are visited by 20 or more members at a time. These include presentations of ongoing projects, research calls, publications, communication, and cooperation both inside the faculty, between different TU Delft faculties and outside TU Delft;
- News alerts on ongoing activities and funding opportunities are sent out to Hub members;
- Philosophy debates. First paper published (<https://doi.org/10.1080/02697459.2025.2589890>) on the 'Scales to Aspects' model and a tentative definition for CBE. A new discussion on value transition follows in 2026 coordinated by the MBE department's REVALUE Research Group.

7th public debate on Unlocking the Value of Circularity in Real Estate – From Paradigm Shifts to Practical Solutions

Our OUTREACH | EXTERNAL

NATIONAL SCALE

- As an academic institution, we acknowledge our responsibility in the transition to a circular built environment and assume an active role in doing so. Through our open public debates (4 times a year) we facilitate a more inclusive and active dialogue for envisioning shared circular futures and co-creating values together with multiple stakeholders and interested parties;
- Yearly participation in the Dutch Week of CE with a PhD Event and other national events such as DAN-CE and Cirkelstad meetings;
- Keynote delivery at several national events organised by companies or regional organisations.

Circularity graduation awards ceremony 2022

INTERNATIONAL SCALE

- Starting in 2022, we initiated the Circularity in the Built Environment Summer School series. These events are organised on a yearly basis in late June-early July and host around 40 participants from all over the world (professionals, PhD researchers, MSc and BSc students);
- We have over the years accommodated the visits of individual researchers or consortia from other countries and engaged in presenting the work we are doing on circularity at the faculty. We have also offered several online presentations to representatives of international universities;
- We secure a coherent online presence, by sharing:
 - Our Research Stories about finished projects and projects underway;
 - Our Output Overview;
 - the Outputs of our Public Debates and Summer Schools.

Our Impact

MOOCs

- Circular Economy for a Sustainable Built Environment (2019–today), with more than 20,000 individual attendees;
- Critical Raw Materials: Managing Resources for a Sustainable Future (2023–today);
- Sustainable Building with Timber (2024–today).

PROFEDS

- Circular Building Products for a Sustainable Built Environment (2020–today), with more than 50 participants over its four runs;
- Spatial Circularity Strategies for Sustainable Regional Development (2021–today), with more than 50 participants over its four runs.

Summer Schools

- Held in the years 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025
- Overall, 140 people have participated in all four summer schools (average of 35 people per event)

Public Debates

Over a period of two years, CBE Hub has hosted a series of open public debates with the aim of facilitating an open and inclusive dialogue with society. The debates were supported by several invited guests and were attended by more than 250 people.

- July 2023: Making the Built Environment a Reality;
- December 2023: Dissolving Borders in the Transition Towards a Circular Built Environment;
- February 2024: The Often-Overlooked Role of Space in the Circular Economy Transition;
- April 2024: People Matter – Exploring the Social Relevance of Circularity;
- July 2024: The Transition to a Circular Society in the Eurodelta;
- October 2024: Material culture – A Broader Vision on Heritage;
- March 2025: Unlocking the Value of Circularity in Real Estate – From Paradigm Shifts to Practical Solutions;
- July 2025: REUSE;

Education

- LLL and educators' programmes;
- Pioneering cross-level education;
- New MSc in collaboration with the AMS-Institute.

A Leading Voice in International Architectural Research

Recent Research Day of the Department titled "Let's Talk Content" bringing together colleagues from all five Research Sections to discuss how and why their research matters on a personal, professional, societal, environmental and technological level, 2026 Image credit: Stavros Kousoulas

Architecture

The Architecture Department aims to champion open science and societal engagement by bridging architectural practice with academia. The Department aims to actively disseminate diverse research outputs to industry and society in order to address real-world needs.

Internally, the Department's mission is to foster a cohesive culture of intellectual exchange, empowering its staff through inclusive strategic planning and transparent communication.

As such, the Department is deeply dedicated to nurturing the next generation of scholars by enhancing PhD training and ensuring equitable support to all researchers. Furthermore, the Department is committed to addressing systemic barriers, guaranteeing research time, and building a diverse, fully resourced academic community where innovation and societal relevance thrive.

Summary

The connective tissue that binds the research taking place in the Department of Architecture is a clear focus on spatial practices, architectural and urban design with a strong foundation in history and theory. In the last four years, the Department of Architecture restructured its research organisation, formulating a cohesive cohort of Research Sections that work towards building recognisable research themes and trajectories while allowing for heterogeneity and research diversity as well. Based on this new structure, the most significant concerns raised in the 2022 assessment have been addressed, while a robust approach to necessary future steps has been outlined. The document that follows has been developed through a broad interdepartmental discussion that welcomed and involved multiple levels of input, culminating in a forward-looking mission that can shape the Department's research for the coming years.

The Department's researchers actively contribute to the contemporary scientific discourse by publishing peer-reviewed journal articles, book chapters and books, while also developing research grant proposals. Their work also actively enriches the architectural discourse beyond academia with contributions to professional magazines, conferences (that cater to a variety of audiences), and exhibitions, such as the Venice Biennale.

From a faculty-wide perspective, balance is achieved through the diverse strengths of the different Departments. The Department of Architecture is the primary driver of the Faculty's educational operations. This is crucial to the Department's financial health. This foundational work in education is also what enables other Departments to successfully focus on securing grants and building partnerships with civil society. For the past decade, the Faculty has enforced a strict financial policy requiring baseline staff costs to be covered by primary funding streams – specifically, revenue generated from education. As a result, the Department of Architecture is the only one with a truly healthy, self-sustaining budget. Furthermore, a key strategic decision of the Department has been to closely align its education and research efforts. Rather than operating in silos – where researchers and teachers pursue entirely separate goals – the Department promotes their integration. This cohesive approach has allowed the Department to strategically reduce its reliance on external research grants.

The Department is committed to expanding its societal impact while simultaneously strengthening its internal research culture. By adopting an outward-facing strategy, it aims to foster closer ties with professional stakeholders, align academic work with practical societal needs, and broaden the recognition of diverse research outputs, including both scholarly and design-oriented work. To support this mission, the Department has hired staff who bridge the gap between architectural practice and academia. Internally, the focus is on creating a cohesive research community by involving all staff in strategic goals, improving communication to clarify research structures, and bolstering initiatives that promote intellectual exchange and cross-departmental collaboration. Concurrently, the Department is prioritising the support, diversity, and development of its researchers at all levels by addressing systemic barriers.

For doctoral candidates, efforts are directed towards improving completion rates, tailoring postgraduate training, and increasing demographic and geographic diversity, with a special emphasis on supporting self-funded doctorate candidates. The Department is exploring incentives, such as teaching reductions, to boost competitiveness for external grants while actively investigating and correcting systemic barriers that hinder dedicated research time. Underpinning all of these operational goals is a strong commitment to establishing a well-resourced infrastructure for diversity, ensuring the recruitment and retention of a highly diverse and empowered research staff.

1.2

Introduction

Architecture is one of four Departments in the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment at TU Delft, led since 2025 by Georg Vrachliotis. The research carried out by the Department of Architecture distinguishes itself by the focus on architecture as an expanded cultural field of expertise; a discursive field in which making and thinking, design and research, history and theory are inextricably linked. The Department's research addresses contemporary architectural production as a projective moment in which cultural, social, functional, philosophical, economic, and ecological factors are articulated as a concrete spatial and material configuration. Since January 2026, the Department's research programme has been coordinated by two research leaders, Angeliki Sioli and Stavros Kousoulas. Currently the Department of Architecture employs 83 research staff, resulting in 38.5 FTE research time. To better connect its large number of researchers and create opportunities for collaboration and meaningful exchange, the Department restructured its research organisation after the 2021 research visitation. The research of the Department of Architecture is now carried out by five Research Sections, each with its own approaches, methodologies, and relationships to the current state of affairs in contemporary architecture. The five Research Sections consider the different practices, genealogies, types, phenomenologies, and theories in and of architecture.

1.2.1

Research Sections

Each Section has a Research Coordinator, working closely with the Department's Research Leaders. The five Sections bring together two to four academic/teaching groups (as seen in the organisational chart below). Within each Section, these groups collaborate in both education and research. This new structure thus ensured a better connection between research and teaching in the Department. The five Research Sections, in alphabetical order, are:

BK Talks

The BK Talks invite conversations among specialists and experts on pressing and emerging topics that shape the research on and creation of the built environment

- **Building Knowledge** (research coordinator: Dr. Manuela Triggianese)
- **History, Form and Aesthetics** (research coordinator: Dr. Carola Hein)
- **Public Building and Housing Design** (research coordinator: Dr. Stefano Corbo)
- **Situated Architecture** (research coordinator: Dr. Eireen Schreurs)
- **Theories, Territories, Transitions** (research coordinator: Dr. Heidi Sohn)

In a nutshell, the topics, methods and approaches of each one of the five Research Sections are:

- **Building Knowledge** examines the reconceptualisation of the building and the repositioning of architecture in the age of New Technology through critical thinking, analysis, and the integration of knowledge in both education and research;
- **History, Form and Aesthetics** studies long-term developments, design processes, and perceptions of architectural and urban forms. Seen through the lenses of history and form, the activities of History, Form and Aesthetics relate to both past and present, and to built and imagined places, from ruins to paper projects;
- **Public Building and Housing Design** investigates the multiple forms through which inhabitation takes place, by focusing attention on the spatial continuum that stretches from the scale of the domestic to that of public building. The section also explores curatorial practices, examining how research, installations, exhibitions, publications, and public programmes engage diverse audiences and inspire action;
- **Situated Architecture** recognises that the experience of architecture is bound to 'situations' that architecture both articulates and produces. The consideration of these situations includes questions of experience, languages and representation, as well as material cultures;
- **Theories, Territories, Transitions** starts from the assumption that theory is never just applied, and that practice is never non-theoretical. In such a transitional understanding, theory and practice relate through relays, through borderings and liminal crossovers that are not just facilitative but generative: the transitional act produces both a thinking and a doing.

1.2.2

Research Lines

To promote cross-sectional collaborations on topics of more general focus, colleagues from all five sections come together and contribute to the following two overarching Research Lines:

- **Architectural Pedagogies** (led by Dr. Roberto Cavallo);
- **Design Research** (led by Salomon Frausto, director of the Berlage Center for Advanced Studies in Architecture and Urban Design).

TU DELFT DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE ORGANISATIONAL CHART RESEARCH

FIG. 1.2 Organisational Chart Architecture Department

In a nutshell, each of the two Research Lines focuses on:

Architectural Pedagogies coordinates and strengthens research on architectural pedagogy, represents the Department in faculty-wide and institutional educational research initiatives, and positions its pedagogical research within international academic and policy-oriented debates on architectural education.

Design Research is inherently linked to the practice of architecture and explores opportunities to apply knowledge from professional practice into academia; while, at the same time, enriching academia with knowledge gained from professional practice. A taskforce comprised of many of the Department's professors of practice (all of them award-winning international architects: Nathalie de Vries, Kees Kaan, Daniel Rosbottom, Paul Vermeulen); junior colleagues with upcoming architectural offices; and researchers who work on AI and design, is currently investigating the concrete development of this trajectory.

Departmental Research Committees and Activities

Two Departmental Research Committees ensure productive exchanges on shared research themes between the five Research Sections. The research leaders, research coordinators and two research lines representatives meet twice every month during the Big and the Small Research Committee. The Big Research Committee meets to discuss research updates on the faculty level, research activities and initiatives on the Department level, research outreach on a societal level and research promotion. The Small Research Committee meets to discuss and evaluate the applications for prospective PhD candidates and guest researchers (see diagram below).

The researchers from all five sections also collaborate and interact during various research activities organised by the Department's two Research Leaders, such as the Department Research Days and the Department PhD Colloquia. The PhD Colloquia offer PhD candidates the opportunity to present their work and receive feedback from the Department's senior researchers as well as invited guests. The Research Days (three per academic year) focus on various research topics, connections with stakeholders, and literacy on valorisation and grant acquisition.

Department Research Networks

The Department of Architecture has an extensive research network, both within the Netherlands and beyond. In the Netherlands, the Department maintains close ties with other institutes for higher education, such as Erasmus University Rotterdam, and with funding bodies, such as the Dutch Research Council (NWO). The Department is also actively involved in several centres and programmes that have been set up as part of the Leiden-Delft-Erasmus (LDE) strategic alliance, including the Centre for Governance of Migration and Diversity, the Centre for Global Heritage and Development, and the PortCityFutures programme.

Many staff members maintain close ties with architectural practice. Some are architectural practitioners themselves, running award-winning international architectural offices (like MVRDV, Kaan Architecten, Mecanoo), while others collaborate with architectural practitioners, as well as other professional architecture organisations, such as the Branchevereniging Nederlandse Architectenbureau (BNA), the Atelier Rijksbouwmeester and Architectenregister. The Department's researchers are also actively involved in national heritage and history organisations, such as the Nieuwe Instituut, the Koninklijke Nederlandse Oudheidkundige Bond (KNOB) and the Cultural Heritage Agency, as well as with municipal and regional bodies, such as Nij Begun.

Internationally, the Department of Architecture is actively involved in BauHow5, a European alliance of five leading research-intensive European universities in Architecture and the Built Environment that seek to push the boundaries of current practices in architectural research, practice and pedagogies. The Department also has ties with the IDEA League, a strategic alliance among five leading European universities of technology, science and engineering, committed to bringing science to society. Many of the Department's researchers are members (sometimes even board members or presidents) of international academic societies and associations, such as the European Architectural History Network (EAHN), the European Association for Urban History (EAUH), the European Association for Architectural Education (EAAE), and the Architectural Research Network (ARENA). Several staff members also collaborate closely with intergovernmental agencies, such as UN-Habitat, philanthropic organisations, such as the Aga Khan Development Network, and international cultural associations, such as the International Confederation of Architectural Museums (ICAM).

1.3

Mission and strategic aims since the last assessment

The Department's Research Mission and Strategic Aims (as an active response to the 2021 Research Assessment) is to champion open science and societal engagement by bridging architectural practice with academia. The Department aims to actively disseminate diverse research outputs to industry and society in order to address real-world needs. Internally, the Department's mission is to foster a cohesive culture of intellectual exchange, empowering its staff through inclusive strategic planning and transparent communication. As such, the Department is deeply dedicated to nurturing the next generation of scholars by enhancing PhD training and ensuring equitable support to all researchers. Furthermore, the Department is committed to addressing systemic barriers, guaranteeing research time, and building a diverse, fully resourced academic community where innovation and societal relevance thrive.

In brief, the Department aims to:

- Strengthen research output in regard to open science;
- Critically expand research and academic culture to include a wider range of research outputs;
- Improve PhD policy and training to ensure an inclusive and progressive academic environment;
- Review and update (when necessary) Human Resources Policy.

Open Science Dissemination and Active Societal Engagement

The Department recognises the importance of open science dissemination and active societal engagement. To achieve this, it adopted in its mission an outward-facing position that (1) could foster closer relationships with professional and societal stakeholders; (2) facilitate new networks for research staff; and (3) help disseminate, promote, and apply new research findings to speed their adoption by the profession, industry and broader society. In addition, the Department considered it crucial to develop stronger strategies that could identify evolutions in societal needs and develop the relationship between practice and academia in order to increase societal relevance (see Paragraph 1.4.1). A direct outcome of these strategies was the hiring of new Academic Career Track Assistant Professors with profiles that balanced knowledge of practicing architecture and academic work. Finally, one of the aims of the Department in the past years has been the inclusion of a broader range of formats in monitoring research output data that recognise both the scholarly and design-oriented research of the Department.

Fostering Inter-Departmental Connections

To critically update and empower its research and academic culture, the Department placed as a central goal the involvement of all research staff in developing Department-wide research goals, with carefully articulated strategic and implementation plans. To achieve this, one of the goals of the Department was to develop a communications strategy that could help clarify the Department's research organisation. This action would support broader awareness of the various research foci among the Department's many researchers, fostering collaborations and alliances based on shared content and interests. The clarification of the Department's research organisation would also benefit outsiders and newcomers unfamiliar with the Department's research structure. Fostering stronger inter-Departmental connections, part of the strategic aims was to concurrently monitor the output and funding of the research units. Moreover, part of the Department's mission was to critically review the infrastructure and programmes that have been created during 2016-2021, aiming to create a culture of intellectual exchange, while bolstering (through additional funding or other means) those that have performed well to ensure the stability and permanence of this foundation. This included the Theories of Architecture Fellowship pilot programme.

1.3.3

Improving PhD Completion Rates and Training

Continuing to value the importance of PhD research, the Department's mission placed special attention on investigating the factors that would help doctoral students to improve completion times, increase gender parity among the funded students, as well as expand the geographical areas of recruitment. Specific focus was placed on the self-funded PhD candidates of the Department. Moreover, the Department developed post-graduate training and education that would better respond to the needs and interests of its PhD researchers.

1.3.4

Tracing Systemic Barriers

As part of the Department's mission for the past years was the attempt to explore incentives (such as a reduction in teaching) that could encourage research staff to apply for external grants and seed-money funding, making the Department more competitive for larger grants. Moreover, as part of this effort, the Department decided to study whether systemic barriers prevent honouring the contractual obligations for assistant, associate, and full professors regarding the allocation of research time and, if needed, take corrective measures. In addition, the Department committed to continue developing recruitment and retention strategies that could increase the diversity of research staff across ranks, particularly with regard to gender and national diversity, as well as create a robust infrastructure of diversity in the Department so that it is adequately resourced, visible, and empowered. Finally, the Department committed to take steps on the systemic university-wide social safety issues that were brought forward by the education inspectorate report.

1.4

Strategy (including the strategic process) since the last assessment

This strategy has been prepared by the Department of Architecture in response to the previous Research Assessment Report and the position statement that the CvB formulated. Input for this strategy has been gathered through: (1) a series of conversations with each of the Department's group representatives who met with the assessment

FIG. 1.3 The Architectural Data Refinery Lab explores the potential of data for spatial design and research through various activities / Image credit: Georg Vrachliotis.

committee in November 2022; (2) extended conversations with the entire Department's staff during a Departmental Research Day in March 2023. This Research Day was organised around multiple short workshops in which colleagues came together to discuss the 2022 assessment results and suggestions, exchanging ideas on how to best address them. Based on the results, the Department prioritised strategies and actions that correspond to the recommendations referred to in the letter by the CvB. In brief, and in order of importance, the top strategic priorities became:

- Consider the creation of an outward-facing position to foster closer relationships with professional and societal stakeholders; facilitate new networks for research staff; and help to disseminate, promote, and apply new discoveries to speed their adoption by the profession, industry and broader society;
- Develop stronger strategies to identify evolutions in societal needs and develop the relationship between practice and academia in order to increase societal relevance;
- Involve all research staff in developing Department-wide research goals, with carefully articulated strategic and implementation plans, to position the Department for future success;
- Include a broader range of formats in monitoring research output data to recognise both the scholarly and design-oriented research of the Department.

Below we present in more detail and in accordance with the four aspects of Open Science, Academic Culture, PhD Policy and Training, and Human Resources Policy, the Departmental priorities, their relevance, the strategic actions developed in response, as well as the responsible actors and timeframe assigned to them.

Research Dissemination, Stakeholder Relations and Open Science

The Department highly valued the recommendations referring to research dissemination and open science, thus establishing a strategy to address them in an intertwined way. In more detail, the Department decided to develop an inventory of existing relationships and networks with professional and societal stakeholders. This was developed at the end of 2023 by Dr. Janina Gosseye, the research leader at the time, and now the faculty Research Council has taken over the task.

Moreover, the Department explored how widely the faculty research themes (which have high societal relevance) were supported within the Department, and whether we, as a Department, would like to add other themes to this list. To this effect, the March 2023 Research Day (organised by Department Chair Kees Kaan and Department research leader Dr. Janina Gosseye) also addressed, among other concerns, the question of the societal relevance of the Department's research. The input gathered during this event was discussed by the Department's Big Research Committee, which advises the Department's Daily Board. This is still an ongoing process that will be reflected in the currently developed faculty Multi-Annual Plan.

To enhance its stakeholder relations, the Department decided to appoint a committee with one member from each of the Department's Sections (5 members in total) who would act as liaisons with stakeholders and organise stakeholder events. Following a process of EOIs (expressions of interest) and nominations, the Department Chair would appoint the 5-headed committee by the end of 2023. While this process was initiated, it was eventually not successful and is in need of revision. This is a point that we address in the strategy for the upcoming period (**see 1.7.2**).

Continuing on the Department's engagement with stakeholders, the strategy involved the conception and organisation of events and formats that would allow the Department to engage in fruitful exchanges with professional and societal stakeholders. This was supposed to be a task of the aforementioned stakeholder outreach committee. The committee, composed of members from various sections, met once and tried to organise a Research Day with Q5 stakeholders. Q5 is a new educational initiative that is meant to bring external stakeholders into the courses of the fifth quarter (Q5). In the end, this Research Day did not take place because not enough Q5 partners could join on the proposed day. While successful educationally, the Q5 courses did not eventually provide the opportunity for the fruition of further collaborations with stakeholders. A revisited strategy for improvement for the upcoming period is presented later in this document (**see 1.7.2**). The Department also examined whether it could increase the number of design-based PhD candidates through the further development of the Design Research Line. This Research Line is still under development (as already mentioned in Paragraph 1.2) and it merits further attention.

The Department also placed special attention on broadening the range of formats in monitoring research output data so that it could correspond to the specific scholarly and design-oriented research it produces. Although some questions were raised

regarding 'monitoring' and 'measuring' – especially given that DORA suggests we focus more on quality than quantity in our research efforts – the Department believes that it should ensure that the diversity of its research output is well captured in the available platforms (i.e., PURE), and saw this as an invitation to think more carefully about how we present what we as a Department do.

To achieve this, the Department decided to follow a three-step plan, comprising: 1) gathering advice about what outputs are captured by existing platforms and how; 2) based on the advice received in step 1, the Department would develop formats to better capture the value and impact of outputs – such as exhibitions, designs, and invited lectures – that are important for our Department; and 3) an overview of the Department's output would be tabled annually at the Department's Daily Board for evaluation. Different colleagues and groups were responsible for addressing the three points listed above. In more detail, the Department research leader initially gathered information about what (and how) outputs are captured by existing platforms by the end of 2022. The Department research committee would then establish a taskforce that by the end of 2023 would have developed templates/formats for specific outputs, as well as a plan for how these templates can be effectively used (and integrated into existing platforms), eventually assisting the research leader in presenting the annual Departmental outputs at the Department's Daily Board.

During multiple research committee meetings, the question of output monitoring and formats was discussed, where it transpired that PURE (TU Delft's online output registering platform) offers the option to capture all various kinds of output. Through these discussions, the Department research committee came to the conclusion that the problem is not the platform per se, but (a) what we register and (b) how it is valued in the Department, faculty and university as a whole.

1.4.2

Research Structure, Management and Academic Culture

To encourage greater exchange between the different research agendas and foster closer relationships between research and education, the Department reassessed its research programme. The Department optimised its organisational structure based on the content and foci of its research, as a result of the 2021 assessment. As of 2023, the Department has five new Research Sections (comprising smaller educational groups), as mentioned in Paragraph 1.2 of this report. These five Sections are responsible for the education and research of the department, incorporating the former structure of the 10 research agendas and creating larger research groups with a greater critical mass of colleagues. In addition, the Department Research Days (3 per year) and PhD Colloquia (2 per year) were used strategically to foster collaborations within and across the research sections and outline a strong Departmental agenda. The Department Chair, Kees Kaan, and Department Research Leader, Dr. Janina Gosseye, introduced the new section structure at a Strategic Meeting (*Heidag*) of 11 May 2023; the new research structure

was subsequently presented at a plenary meeting of the Department in June 2023, and was fully implemented by the start of the following academic year, September 2024.

Moreover, to make optimal use of the ideas of new research staff, who bring expertise from other schools and institutions, and to create opportunities for the Department's mid-career researchers to gain experience in research management, a 4-year term for members serving on the Department's research committee was instated, as well as a 6-year term for the Department Research Leader(s). From one, the Department moved to employing two Research Leaders as of January 2026, to better accommodate the needs of the position within a Department as large as the Department of Architecture. In addition, two PhD representatives were added to the Department's large research committee, encouraging the exchange of ideas and ensuring that issues arising in the PhD cohort can be dealt with effectively.

Finally, the Department decided to continue the Theories of Architecture Fellowship programme, with its new iteration (presented as a case study in **B.1.3.2**) commencing in September 2023.

1.4.3

Postgraduate Research, Education and Policy

The Department allocated resources from the *Sectorplan* to be used for creating funded PhD positions. The Department fully supported the need to achieve gender parity among funded students and has incorporated this in the funded PhD positions that were announced after the research assessment. It was decided that every 4 years at least 2 new funded PhD positions will be created with the budget that has become available through the *Sectorplan*. Since 2022, a total of 6 PhD positions have been created using this funding stream, while 3 more will open in the coming two years.

In addition, the Department decided to investigate what factors play a role in PhD candidates taking longer than the allocated time to complete their research. The first step in this investigation was a questionnaire developed by the PhD representatives of the research committee that was later distributed to all Department candidates. The Department's working hypothesis was that completion times would significantly improve if we: 1) develop and clearly communicate a robust PhD policy that outlines the benefits and burdens (*lusten en lasten*) of embarking on a PhD – be it funded or self-funded – in our Department (a document that was produced at a faculty-wide level); 2) strive for a better balance between funded and self-funded PhDs; 3) more actively promote a PhD based on publications rather than the book-length dissertation; and 4) assess how many PhD students we can accommodate to ensure effective supervision.

In response to this, the Department followed specific actions. In more detail, the Department Manager developed and communicated a thorough PhD policy in August 2023. In tandem, the Department's Big Research Committee discussed strategies for attaining a better balance between funded and self-funded PhD candidates.

FIG. 1.4 Deleuze and Guattari Studies Conference, organised by the Architecture Philosophy and Theory group, 2024 / Image credit: Stavros Kousoulas

The result of these two processes was a revised PhD policy in 2024 that called a halt to self-funded PhD candidates who have not obtained financing from a recognised institution. This would ensure that non-TU Delft funded PhD candidates would not encounter the financial and completion struggles reported extensively through the aforementioned questionnaire. In addition to these steps, the Department committed to communicate all various PhD formats to both supervisors and PhD candidates; this was eventually done in the form of a revised faculty PhD policy that was centrally circulated in 2025. Moreover, the Department decided to assess how many PhD students it could accommodate in order to ensure effective supervision. This was discussed at the Department Research Day of June 2024, where it was decided that the supervisors of PhD candidates who have been going for more than 5 years should report to the small research committee, and give an update on (a) why it is taking longer, and (b) how the Department might be able to help the PhD candidate towards completion.

FIG. 1.5 Posthuman Symbioses Masterclass: A Thinking-With Donna Haraway and Rosi Braidotti, 2023 / Image credit: Alex Kirschstein

In addition, the Department committed to offer postgraduate training and education that would better respond to the needs and interests of its PhD researchers. As a result, and through discussions that took place in both the Big Research Committee as well as at the Department Research Day of April 2025, the Department now offers five new Graduate School courses (in addition to an existing selection of university-wide courses). These courses are presented as a case study further in this document (**see B.1.5**). Finally, the Department committed to address systemic social safety issues that were central to a university-wide debate after the education inspectorate report of 2022. Department townhall meetings were held to raise awareness and share concerns. In addition, all Department members that hold a leadership position have followed training sessions on social safety. Given the importance of the issue, the Department remains alert and committed to continuously updating its approach and necessary toolkit in safeguarding the social safety of its employees.

Research Funding and Human Resources Policy

The Department decided to explore incentives that could enhance the research staff's capacity to competitively apply for external grants, as well as examine the presence of systemic barriers that would hinder the research time of its employees. In doing so, questions were raised with regard to what the ideal proportion might be for the Architecture Department between base funding (*eerste geldstroom*: first money stream) and research funding. At present, the Department of Architecture can cover the salaries of its staff from its base funding. This is positive, as it ensures stability and research freedom, but results in proportionally lower acquisition of grants, in comparison with the Faculty's other three departments. Given that architecture has an important educational task within the faculty, it raises the question whether each department within the faculty should operate in a similar way, or if we should accept differences. With regard to systemic barriers, the Department's hypothesis was that these barriers have to do with the balance between teaching and research obligations. This is why a shared strategy was developed for both these issues (grant acquisition and workload).

The Department decided to implement a new system of 'teaching-free periods' that entitles staff who have been continuously employed at the Department for a minimum of four years (and who have both a teaching and research assignment) to one teaching-free semester every four years, or one teaching-free quarter every two years, or something equivalent, during which they can spend (minimally) 80 per cent of their time (exclusively) on research. Section heads and group leaders will discuss with individual members of their section which model best suits their needs during annual appraisals. Teaching responsibilities of the person on research leave will be divested to other members of the section and/or to staff with a temporary contract. The cost and feasibility of this scheme were assessed in September 2023 while each section head was asked to develop a strategy for the next four years to better gauge what the implications would be on the staffing (needs) in relation to their education programme. The new system was eventually implemented from 2024 onwards but very few employees made actual use of this option. The Department is evaluating the reasons for this and is proposing a revised strategy (presented later in this document).

Finally, the Department acknowledged the need to continue developing recruitment and retention strategies that increase the diversity of research staff across ranks. To achieve this, the Department asks for a continuous and updated faculty-wide conversation about the sort of intersectional diversity that we should aspire to, and what sort of diversity policy framework we should adopt. Facilitating such a faculty-wide conversation about the desired intersectional diversity is eventually organised by the faculty's newly appointed Diversity and Inclusion team; the Department is actively involved in this discussion, through both its research leaders and coordinators, as well as its regular research staff.

Evidence

Coupling fundamental and applied research, theory and practice, the Department of Architecture has a long tradition of valorising its research not only through standard academic channels, such as peer-reviewed journals, academic books, book chapters, book series and academic lectures, conferences and seminars, but also through contributions to professional magazines, books with a broader (both academic and non-academic) readership, media appearances, exhibitions for a broader public, educational formats for lifelong learning such as MOOCs and ProfEDs, and alternative media such as serious games. Furthermore, embedding and entangling research and education, one of the strongest expressions of the relevance of the Department's output for society is the work of the numerous practitioners trained at the Department who are today shaping our built environment, both in the Netherlands and beyond.

TABLE 1.1

SELECTED INDICATORS FOR RESEARCH QUALITY AND SOCIETAL RELEVANCE ARCHITECTURE

	RESEARCH QUALITY	RELEVANCE TO SOCIETY
Demonstrable products	Research products for peers Journal articles Books Book chapters Conference papers PhD dissertations (see appendix 2: 'completed doctoral dissertations')	Research products for societal target groups Exhibitions Articles published in professional magazines and newspapers Books with a broader readership Conferences
Demonstrable use of products	Use of research products by peers Downloads and reads of articles, book chapters and books	Use of research products by societal target groups Citations in popular media, including newspapers and online platforms (e.g. Dezeen and ArchDaily) Contract research Projects in collaboration with societal partners, including architectural offices, governmental ministries, etc.
Demonstrable marks of recognition	Marks of recognition from peers Research grants Editorship of book series and academic journals Membership of scientific councils and committees Organisation of international scientific events Honorary doctorates	Marks of recognition by societal target groups Invitations to curate (or contribute to) international exhibitions, such as the Venice Biennale Membership/chairpersonship of societal organisations (see appendix 3: 'connections')

Accomplishments during the past four years – research quality and societal relevance

To present the research accomplishments of the Department over the last four (2022-26) years, this section is structured around five main clusters: 1) the ways that the Department of Architecture engages with broad societal concerns; 2) the ties it has created with creative industries; 3) what role the Department plays in shaping the research agenda of the Faculty; 4) how it acts as a leading voice in architectural research internationally; and 5) how it monitors and updates its PhD education. Each of these clusters is presented in more detail below.

TABLE 1.2

RESEARCH FUNDING ARCHITECTURE								
	2022		2023		2024		2025	
	k€	%	k€	%	k€	%	k€	%
Direct funding (1)	9.270	82%	10.003	87%	11.561	92%	11.959	93%
Research grants (2)	443	4%	451	4%	257	2%	35	0%
Contract research (3)	1.492	13%	1.024	9%	678	5%	851	7%
Other (4)	92	1%	76	1%	114	1%	50	0%
Total funding	11.297	100%	11.554	100%	12.610	100%	12.895	100%
Personnel costs	10.346	94%	11.958	94%	12.617	95%	13.171	95%
Material costs	106	1%	164	1%	278	2%	169	1%
Other costs	606	5%	541	4%	434	3%	465	3%
Total expenditure	11.058	100%	12.663	100%	13.329	100%	13.805	100%
	239		-1.109		-719		-910	

TABLE 1.3

RESEARCH OUTPUT ARCHITECTURE				
	2022	2023	2024	2025
Refereed article	57	57	67	37
Non-refereed article	2	12	16	10
Professional publications	33	18	12	5
Books	1	8	6	6
Book chapter	45	44	37	30
Professional publications	33	18	12	5
Conference papers	6	26	20	23
PhD theses	10	9	7	5
Other research output	63	59	50	30
Total	217	236	216	148

TABLE 1.4

RESEARCH STAFF ARCHITECTURE								
SEP categories	2022		2023		2024		2025	
	#	FTE	#	FTE	#	FTE	#	FTE
Assistant professor	24,1	8,3	23,9	8,3	24,7	8,6	24,0	8,4
Associate professor	8,0	2,8	7,4	2,6	8,0	2,8	9,3	3,3
Full professor	8,0	2,1	9,2	2,4	10,0	2,6	10,0	2,5
Postdocs	3,2	2,1	3,5	2,6	4,8	3,3	3,4	2,7
Researchers (other)	12,3	6,0	12,9	6,8	10,3	5,4	11,3	6,4
PhD candidate (HR)	10,3	9,9	12,5	12,2	12,2	12,1	14,2	14,0
Total	65,8	31,1	69,4	34,9	70,0	34,7	72,1	37,3
Support staff	4,8	2,9	1,8	0,5	2,4	1,1	2,4	1,2
Grand Total	70,6	34,1	71,3	35,4	72,4	35,8	74,5	38,5

TABLE 1.5

PHD CANDIDATES ARCHITECTURE									
	Enrollment			Success rates cumulative					
	Male & other	Female	Total	Graduated totals		Not yet finished		Discontinued	
Start	#	#	#	#	%	#	%	#	%
2022	9	4	13	1	8%	12	92%	0	-
2023	3	8	11	0	-	10	91%	1	9%
2024	5	4	9	0	-	9	100%	0	-
2025	5	3	8	0	-	8	100%	0	-
Total	22	19	41	1	-	39	-	1	-

TABLE 1.6

PHD CANDIDATES ARCHITECTURE PROGRESS																	
	Enrollment			Success rates cumulative													
	Male & other	Female	Total	Graduated ≤ 4 years		Graduated ≤ 5 years		Graduated ≤ 6 years		Graduated ≤ 7 years		Graduated totals		Not yet finished		Discontinued	
Start	#	#	#	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
2016	5	8	13	0	-	0		2	15%	6	46%	9	69%	2	15%	2	15%
2017	2	4	6	1	17%	1	17%	1	17%	1	17%	2	33%	4	67%	0	-
2018	6	5	11	0	-	6	55%	7	64%	7	64%	7	64%	1	9%	3	27%
2019	5	5	10	1	10%	2	20%	4	40%	4	40%	4	40%	4	40%	2	20%
2020	3	0	3	1	33%	2	67%	2	67%	2	67%	2	67%	1	33%	0	-
2021	6	7	13	0	-	1	8%	1	8%	1	8%	1	8%	12	92%	0	-
Total	27	29	56	3	-	12	-	17	-	21	-	25	-	24	-	7	-

FIG. 1.6 Proportion male (blue) / female (orange) in research staff 2022-2025 (excl. guests).

FIG. 1.7 Proportion of nationality (NL/EU/non-EU) (excl. guests). Dark green = NL, medium green = EU, light green = non-EU.

Engaging with the World

In the Department of Architecture, research addresses global concerns through direct engagement with local communities and societal groups. Through both academic paths and hands-on societal initiatives, the architectural researchers of the Department address pressing issues of the built environment, from the level of buildings to that of urban interventions and from the level of infrastructure to that of natural resources. The international conference Thirst and Mirage explored the technocratic, extractive, and colonial approaches to water that have led to disentangled ecologies. Through contributions that demonstrated the engagement of various communities around the world with desert areas and water bodies, the symposium explored the imposition of borders, conflicts, and wars throughout various desert landscapes. **(see B.1.1.1)** The international conference Technogeographies of Care: Future Healthspaces addressed the topic of care in a digital age. From homes and hospitals to platforms and planetary systems, care today unfolds across physical and digital infrastructures alike, affecting the livelihood of a heavily ageing population in the developed world and the livelihood of thousands of children and infants in the developing world. **(see B.1.1.2)** The international conference Living Data brought together global thought leaders to investigate how living data concepts are entwined with the design processes that visualise and shape spaces for living. The conference was based on the premise that data art, data visualisation, designing with data, and data-making can be helpful tools for bridging the empirical methods of science and the creative processes of architecture, leading to promising new ways to address climate challenges. **(see B.1.1.3)** The international symposium Posthuman Symbioses Masterclass invited a discussion between Donna Haraway and Rosi Braidotti, focusing on the urgent question of our 'becoming-with' environments, aiming to find conceptual tools for redirecting future architecture and urban design towards a more sympoietic direction that may mitigate the increasingly complex crises in the Anthropocene. **(see B.1.1.4)**

The COST ACTION: Writing Urban Places created a network of 200 researchers (from architects and literary scholars to geographers and artists) from 35 European countries, who examined how narrative methods can be employed to develop human understanding of communities, their society, and their situatedness in mid-sized European cities. In-situ workshops in cities like Osijek (Croatia), Skopje (North Macedonia), Tirana (Albania), and Porto (Portugal) brought together researchers with various local communities and their architectural particularities. **(see B.1.1.5)** The Testaccio Collective is an interdisciplinary research collective that explores the implications of a circular building culture, as a dialogue between human and non-human actors. In collaboration with various stakeholders from practice (municipalities, contractors, clients), DEMOLIRE conceptualises demolition as a critical and generative phase within processes of transformation. Approaching demolition as a social-material practice, the project traces how materials re-enter economic and cultural value chains. **(see B.1.1.6)**

Initiatives that have a more hands-on effect on global communities are also a vital part of the Department's research. The 2ALL Addis Ababa Living Lab is a transdisciplinary initiative that focused on improving the livelihood of urban dwellers in Ethiopia's capital. It developed and used a co-creation model that instigates collaboration

amongst multiple entities. The Lab involves the participation of faculty members from TU Delft, the Ethiopian Institute of Architecture Building Construction and City Development (EiABC), as well as governmental agencies, international design practices, and non-profit organisations. The Lab was awarded a research grant by NWO – WOTRO (Dutch Research Council – Science for Global Development). **(see B.1.1.7)**

1.6.2

Creating Ties with the Creative Industry

The research conducted in the Department of Architecture in the last few years has been very successful in securing funding from the KIEM MV (*Maatschappelijk Verdienvermogen*) programme. This is a research funding instrument of the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO), developed to stimulate applied, practice-oriented research within the creative industries. Closely connected to the ClickNL Design Agenda, KIEM MV provides a structured framework through which academic institutions collaborate with design practices, industry partners, and societal stakeholders. Its primary objective is to bridge the gap between scholarly research and professional application by supporting small-scale, experimental projects with clear pathways to impact.

Within the Department, the KIEM MV programme has proven particularly effective at translating academic research into design practice. By requiring close collaboration with external partners from the outset, KIEM MV projects embed real-world constraints, expertise, and ambitions directly into the research process. This ensures that research outcomes are both theoretically grounded and practically relevant, contributing simultaneously to knowledge production, design innovation, and professional practice. The alignment of KIEM MV with the ClickNL Design Agenda further strengthens its relevance. The ClickNL Design Agenda articulates national priorities for design-led innovation, emphasising societal challenges such as sustainability, digital transformation, inclusivity, and the future of the built environment. KIEM MV projects operationalise these priorities by enabling researchers and practitioners to co-develop methods, tools, and prototypes that respond to these challenges through design research. Several KIEM-funded projects within the Department of Architecture exemplify this connection between academic research and practice. The programme's collaborative structure enabled projects to operate across disciplinary and professional boundaries, reinforcing the reciprocal exchange between research and practice. In the last few years, six initiatives by respective colleagues from the Department of Architecture (with a wide variety of research foci) have been granted KIEM funding. These projects demonstrate how applied research funding can function as a catalyst for collaboration, innovation, and societal relevance — ensuring that architectural research actively informs and transforms design practice while contributing to broader academic and cultural agendas. **(see B.1.2.1)**

Shaping a Faculty-wide Research Agenda

The Department of Architecture has a leading role in both shaping and implementing the research agenda of the Faculty. An example is the case of the Architectural Data Refinery Lab, a cross-Departmental platform for research and innovation that brings together scholars, designers, and practitioners who seek to rethink how data shapes the built environment (**see B.1.3.1**). As part of its wide research initiatives, the Department is also hosting the Theories of Architecture Fellowship Program, a research and curatorial initiative of the Department of Architecture that raises questions about the multiplicity of theories surrounding architecture, its interactions and overlaps with other fields, and the expansion of its theoretical horizons vis-à-vis research and practice (**see B.1.3.2**). The Jaap Bakema Study Center, led by the Department, is a collaboration between the Faculty and the Nieuwe Instituut in Rotterdam for scientific research in the field of architecture and urban design together with third parties. The collections of the National Collection for Dutch Architecture and Urban Planning (hosted in the Nieuwe Instituut) form the basis for a research programme that is situated at the intersection of advanced historical and theoretical research and urgent social issues (**see B.1.3.3**). In addition, the Department has a sustained and strong presence in open access publication initiatives that, while based and funded by the Department of Architecture, gather researchers from various other Faculty Departments, such as the Footprint Delft Architecture Theory Journal, the Ecologies of Architecture TU Delft Open Book Series, the Writingplace TU Delft Open Book Series, the City of Innovations TU Delft Open Book Series, and DASH: Delft Architectural Studies on Housing (**see B.1.3.4**). Moreover, the Department plays a key role in shaping the public research programme of the Faculty, through initiatives such as the Berlage Keynotes & Sessions, an ongoing public lecture and seminar series that brings internationally prominent architects, designers, and critical thinkers into dialogue around pressing issues in architecture, urbanism, and contemporary culture (**see B.1.3.5**). Finally, special attention has been given to developing an Architectural Pedagogies Departmental research line as a transversal structure across the Department and in collaboration with other Departments within the faculty, representing the Department in faculty-wide and institutional educational research initiatives, as well as positioning the Department's pedagogical research within international academic and policy-oriented debates on architectural education (**see B.1.3.6**). Expanding the research on architectural pedagogies, the Speculative Urban Futures Erasmus+ LSI project investigates the role and purpose of design in the twenty-first century – understood as an ecology of knowing, imagining and making that is deeply involved in the complex worlding dynamics shaping contemporary reality (**see B.1.3.7**). Driving cross-faculty collaborations within TU Delft and beyond, the department is leading the AI Insight series, with two symposia on the Future of Healthcare and Mobility (**see B.1.3.8**), and is actively involved in the TU Delft Vision Team 2050 Mobility Futures (**see B.1.3.9**).

Theories of Architecture Fellowship Program
Department of Architecture

TA

20 Nov **PUBLIC LECTURE** ROOM B
17:00-18:30 **By S. Sumartojo**
Atmospheres, Ineffability and Powers of Attention: Attuning to Architecture

17 Nov **Research Meeting** ROOM P
13:00-18:30 **Guidance & Feedback**

15 Nov **Research Group Meeting** BG, Court, NE
14:00-18:00 **Shared Experiences**

14 Nov **Mini-Exhibition Exhibition** ROOM K
09:00-12:30 **Work in Progress**
Work in Progress of Spatial Experimentation
The exhibition is a part of the TA's weekly 'Work in Progress'

10 Nov **ADVANCE PhD Seminar** Via LANGE
09:00-18:30 **Preparation for research**

LECTURE: ATMOSPHERES, INEFFABILITY AND POWERS OF ATTENTION: ATTUNING TO ARCHITECTURE

Atmospheres: ineffability and powers of attention: attuning to architecture

Shanti Sumartojo

Shanti Sumartojo

Theories of Architecture Fellowship Program
Department of Architecture

TA

[theoriesofarchitecture](https://theoriesofarchitecture.com)

17 Oct **Public Lecture**
17:00-18:30 **Decentering Future Imaginaries: A Decolonial Approach to Spatial Thinking**
Room D

22 Oct **PhD Seminar**
10:00-13:00 **The Role of Positionality and Decolonial Perspectives in Research**
01 West, 010

LECTURE: DECENTRING FUTURE IMAGINARIES: A DECOLONIAL APPROACH TO SPATIAL DESIGN THINKING

Dr. Lakshmi Priya Rajendran

Decentering Future Imaginaries: A Decolonial Approach to Spatial Design Thinking

Dr. Lakshmi Priya Rajendran

UCL Bartlett

Theories of Architecture Fellowship Program
Department of Architecture

TA

[theoriesofarchitecture](https://theoriesofarchitecture.com)

11 Jun **Public Lecture**
17:30-19:00 **Second Materiality: Theorising Reuse, Recycling and Landfilling in Architecture**
Stage 1

13 Jun **PhD Seminar**
09:00-13:30 **Production of Nature: Materialist Theory of Environment in Architecture**
BG, Oss, E20

LECTURE: SECOND MATERIALITY: THEORISING REUSE, RECYCLING, AND LANDFILLING IN ARCHITECTURE

Second Materiality: Theorising Reuse, Recycling and Landfilling in Architecture

Dr. Adam Przywara

UNI Fribourg

Theories of Architecture Fellowship Program
Department of Architecture

TA

[theoriesofarchitecture](https://theoriesofarchitecture.com)

02 Dec **Public Lecture & Film**
17:30-19:00 **From Extraction to Translation: The Afterlife of a West African Utopia**
Orange Hall

04 Dec **PhD Seminar**
13:45-17:45 **Transacting Post-Conflict Landscapes**
West C

LECTURE: FROM EXTRACTION TO TRANSLATION

Translation and Post-Conflict Landscapes

Dr. Killian O'Dochartaigh

University of Edinburgh | Architectural Field Office

Dr Killian O'Dochartaigh

FIG. 1.8 Selection of posters from the Theories of Architecture Fellowship Program.

A Leading Voice in International Architectural Research

Between 2022 and 2025, the Department's researchers and staff have published a total of 236 journal articles, 29 books, 39 edited volumes and 202 book chapters, covering a range of diverse interests from a multitude of perspectives, further establishing the Department as a leading voice in contemporary architectural research (**see 5.4**). The breadth of the research interests pursued at the Department is expressed in the wide range of themes and topics in the refereed and peer-reviewed journal publications of its researchers (**see B.1.4.1**).

Next to journal publications, the books published by the Department's researchers also cover a heterogeneous field of interests, and include monographs such as Georg Vrachliotis' *The New Technological Condition* (2022), Stavros Kousoulas' *Architectural Technicities* (2022) and Athens (2025), Amy Thomas' *The City in the City* (2023), Stefano Corbo's *Exteriorless Architecture* (2024) and Sang Lee's *Architecture in the Age of Mediatizing Technologies* (2024) — among others (**see B.1.4.2**); as well as a number of edited volumes such as *Design Commons* (2022), *Datapolis* (2023), *Architectures of Resistance* (2024) and *The Space of Technicity* (2024) (**see B.1.4.3**).

Other significant research outputs produced by the Department of Architecture are conferences (in addition to the ones mentioned earlier) and exhibitions. Several members of the Department are the driving forces behind recurring (annual) conferences, such as the Jaap Bakema Study Centre Annual Conference, the CA²RE Community for Artistic and Architectural Research Conferences, or the Deleuze and Guattari Studies International Conference and Camp (**see B.1.4.4**). The Department has also taken a leading role in exploring contemporary pressing issues, placing special attention on design data literacy through The New Open project, an expansive collective which explores the notion of openness through conferences and workshops (**see B.1.4.5**).

Further exploring the relation between architectural design and contemporary developments in artificial intelligence, the Department has developed the AIBlocks online podcast platform, sharing knowledge about artificial intelligence and its potential to empower architectural design research and practice (**see B.1.4.6**). Finally, as part of its public programme, the Department has organised a series of exhibitions on a broad range of topics, including BK Africa, Building with the Delta and Indigenous Intelligence (**see B.1.4.7**), as well as BK Talks, a series of public events that cross Departmental limits and address contemporary concerns on a diverse range of topics (**see B.1.4.8**).

FIG. 1.9 Architecture Department Book Market, 2026 / Image credit: Stavros Kousoulas

1.6.5

Critically Updating PhD Education

To advance the level of PhD research, the Department of Architecture worked collectively to create five new PhD courses tailored specifically to the needs of research within the architectural field. In 2025, the Department dedicated one of its recurrent research days to the development of these courses. Each of the five Research Sections was assigned to develop one course, with the premise that the five courses will collectively work to complement each other, offering a significant addition to the existing PhD education offered both in the Faculty and Department itself. As of the academic year 2025/26, the Department has started to offer these courses in collaboration with the Faculty Graduate School, actively responding to one of the most pressing demands of its PhD researchers, namely a contemporary and architecture-oriented postgraduate education curriculum (see **B.1.5**).

Strategy for the time until the next assessment and beyond

SWOT analysis through qualitative comparison

For this research report, the Department of Architecture evaluated its current mission, aims and strategy (as established in the previous research assessment) as well as its accomplishments during the past four years. Through this qualitative evaluation, the Department's major strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats were identified, while the Departmental strategy for the coming two years (2026-28) was further refined (together with the addition of new elements to it).

Strengths

- **Paid Research Component:** The Department of Architecture offers its staff members strong structural financial support for research. As part of the 'basisfinanciering' that the Department receives from the Dutch government, all academic staff can devote 40% of their time to research.
- **Teaching Free Period:** In the last three years, the Department has initiated the teaching free period programme. This is meant for researchers who have a tangible research project to work on (from a grant to a book publication). A researcher can apply for this teaching exception for one quarter every three years or for a semester every six years.
- **Department Research Structure:** Since the 2021 assessment, the Department of Architecture improved its research structure to better align with its education structure as well. The Department now comprises five Research Sections, each one of which is led by a dedicated research coordinator. The research coordinators organise section research meetings for the section's junior and senior researchers, invite external researchers, participate in the selection of PhD candidates and guest researchers, and have a clear knowledge of the individual researchers' work and future research steps. The doctoral candidates of the Department have the opportunity to receive feedback not only from their immediate supervisory team but also from a wider range of colleagues, at the research meetings of their sections.
- **Department Research Activities:** The Department regularly organises Research Days to discuss research topics, grant and valorisation opportunities, societal challenges and connections with relevant stakeholders. These research days take place three times per year and are dedicated to a specific topic each time (January: Content

| June: Valorisation | September: Stakeholders). The Department also regularly organises PhD Colloquia to support the research of its doctoral candidates. These colloquia allow candidates – at various moments of their research – to present their work publicly and receive feedback from colleagues but also invited guests.

- **100% Research Office:** The Department of Architecture has a strong management structure in place to monitor and support research within the Department and to respond effectively to opportunities and problems that (may) arise. The office of 100% Research involves dedicated colleagues who can assist with administrative and financial processes/documents.
- **Societal Relevance:** Due to its close relationships with practice, its strong focus on design, its varied output (including exhibitions, media appearances, contributions to professional journals, etc.), and its efforts in publishing predominantly open-access, the research conducted at the Department of Architecture resonates strongly beyond the walls of academia and has a strong societal impact.
- **International Networks:** Multiple members of the Department of Architecture are actively involved in national and international networks, contributing to the Department's leading (inter)national reputation.

Weaknesses

- **External Funding:** Over the past four years, external grants (both obtained in national scientific competitions and research contracts for specific research projects obtained from external organisations, such as industry, government ministries, European organisations and charitable organisations) accounted for 11% of the Department's research funding. Although successes have been achieved in attracting personal research funding for young/emerging scholars (mostly PostDocs), the success rate has been lower for those at the mid-career level and the Department's senior scholars.
- **Workload & Lack of Research Monitoring:** The Department has a very rigorous system for counting the teaching hours of academic staff. The formulas used to calculate these hours (including course preparation | contact hours | grading, etc.) do not always reflect the amount of time needed for teaching. The result is that academic staff make use of the time allocated to research for educational purposes – even unofficially. The fact that there is not an equally rigorous system in place to count research hours helps this to happen.
- **Limited Promoting Capacity:** The steep increase in numbers that has occurred since the previous research assessment in PhD candidates enrolled in the Department of Architecture, against only a marginal increase in staff who hold the Ius Promovendi (promotion rights), limits the overall promoting capacity of the Department. Furthermore, most full professors at the Department of Architecture (6 out of 10) are 'professors of practice', focused on teaching. They have part-time appointments (commonly two days per week) and, thus, limited time allocated to research in their contracts. This places a large burden on the other (full-time) full professors and those (few) associate professors who have already obtained the Ius Promovendi.

- **100% Research Office:** Although the team of 100% Research, which operates at the faculty level, provides excellent support and advice to those within the Department of Architecture developing grant applications, they do not possess expertise specific to the topic of each grant proposal. The feedback thus often remains on a more general level.

Opportunities

- **New Staff:** Since the 2021 assessment, the Department has had a further influx of new staff (mostly early and mid-career researchers). Space should be created for these emerging scholars to help set the course for the Department's future research agenda without creating more fragmentation within the Department's research structure.
- **Funded PhD Research:** Since the previous assessment, the Department has secured a satisfactory number of salaried PhD candidates, who work either in cross-Departmental research or research that is directly related to the sections to which they belong. Their contribution to the Department's research agenda, as well as the perspectives that each candidate brings, should be harvested and capitalised in setting up the Department's research strategy.
- **Increased Gender Balance:** Over the past 4 years, the gender diversity of the research staff has increased. Since 2021, two women have been appointed full professors (Janina Gosseye and Marina Tabassum), equalling the total number of five female and five male full professors affiliated with the Department of Architecture. Since 2021, efforts in correcting the gender imbalance have been made at the level of assistant professor (the FTE of female assistant professors now stands at 41%). This is slightly reduced compared to 2022, but it has to do with the successful completion of academic career tracks and promotion to associate professors (the FTE of female associate professors increased from 42% to 54%). The Department of Architecture should nurture and support the careers of all female researchers so that further gender balance is achieved at all levels.
- **Diverse Nationalities:** The nationalities of the research staff affiliated with the Department of Architecture have diversified since the previous research assessment. However, the stark difference between the lack of diversity in the cohort of senior researchers (full and associate professors) and the cohort of younger/emerging scholars (assistant professors and doctoral students), as shown in Fig. 1.8, is noteworthy. The Department of Architecture should nurture and support the careers of young non-European scholars to create greater diversity among senior staff.
- **Strategic Investments:** The Department has invested in AI; the Architectural Data Refinery Lab is an indicative example. These strategic investments create opportunities to expand the Department's research in this field while additionally strengthening the Department's contribution to open science.
- **Funding Opportunities:** The Department has been successful in securing funding from the KIEM MV (Maatschappelijk Verdienvermogen) programme. Funding opportunities that bridge the gap between scholarly research and professional application by supporting small-scale, experimental projects are an indication of the Department's strengths in valorisation efforts.

- **Open Access Initiatives:** The Department has a strong presence in open access initiatives (such as the Footprint Delft Architecture Theory Journal, the Ecologies of Architecture TU Delft Open Book Series, the Writingplace TU Delft Open Book Series and the City of Innovations TU Delft Open Book Series, among others), indicating that its capacity for sustained and consistent engagement with open access output is something that should be further fostered and supported.
- **Relations with Practice:** A significant portion of the staff working in/for the Department of Architecture are (part-time) practitioners. At present, this staff is not optimally involved in the Department's research programme. A huge opportunity lies in better integrating and involving these practitioners in the Department's research and in valorising the contributions to knowledge that they make through their designs.
- **Collaboration Network:** The Department has a significant network of close collaborators in academic, societal and industrial domains. This network, together with a network of former alumni, should be properly documented since it presents a great opportunity when it comes to the Department's future valorisation efforts and potential.

Threats

- **Workload Pressure:** The staff in the Department of Architecture has a very high workload. They play a key role in the educational programme of the faculty. Although time for research is contractually guaranteed, education often eats into staff's research time. This means that if staff members choose to spend their research time writing a grant application, there is typically limited research time left for doing other kinds of research tasks (such as writing a paper). If the grant application is not awarded, this can have a negative impact on someone's research profile. Therefore, many staff members work more hours than contractually obliged, leading to stress and sometimes also burnout.
- **Practice Professors and Design Tutors:** While the career paths for those joining the Department with an academic background (a PhD degree) are clearly defined – they typically progress from assistant professor to associate professor and, sometimes, full professor – this is not the case for staff with a more mixed/diverse profile. Those who work part-time in practice and part-time in academia either join the Department as (full) professors of practice or as design tutors. Those in the latter category have no clear career path within the Department of Architecture – and therefore, no clear research opportunities and requirements – unless they commit to pursuing a doctoral degree.
- **Fewer PhD Researchers:** To ward off the threats presented by increasing living costs for self-funded PhD candidates, and the various ways that they impact their research as well as successful completion rates, the Department decided to follow stricter financial requirements and monitoring of incoming PhD candidates. As a consequence, the Department no longer accepts self-funded PhD candidates. While this is a necessary measure to ensure the well-being of its researchers as well as ensuring proper completion times, it presents a threat in significantly limiting the amount of PhD research conducted in the Department.

- **Economic Measures:** The recent economic measures in tertiary education in the Netherlands have reduced the capacity of the Department to consistently support certain research activities (i.e., support in publications, event organisation) without necessarily resorting to the pursuit of external monetary support; this can present a threat for the Department, given the volatile nature of external funding. These measures also present the danger of potential loss of critical knowledge and expertise in research positions that are not replaced after retirement.

1.7.2

Strategy for the next six years

Research Dissemination, Stakeholder Relations and Open Science

In the following two years, the Department will:

Advocate for new formats of research output and research dissemination. One such format will be to create a Department Podcast Series that will help make its researchers' work known beyond the strict confines of academia.

Strengthen the societal relevance of research conducted within the Department by ensuring that the professors of practice (practicing architects with offices in the Netherlands, Belgium, UK, and Bangladesh) will be given a greater presence in the Department's research programme.

Cultivate a broader stakeholders network. The stronger connection between the researchers and practicing architects will also ensure further collaborations at societal level and grant projects.

Explore new manners and formats of network activation, e.g., a think tank could be developed to connect the department with industry and societal partners.

Dedicate one of its three recurring Research Days to stakeholders, which will also be strategically organised to develop a stronger network for the Department's researchers, leading to creative and successful collaborations and grant proposals with industry representatives and other partners.

Explore new formats for PhD projects supported by external stakeholders, such as Practice-Based PhD research and EngD.

Research Structure, Management and Academic Culture

The Department wishes to:

Strengthen the Research Sections organisation. The sections bridge research and educational cohorts of colleagues together; colleagues who share common interests and pursue related research goals. These sections allow for more predictive collaborations and more efficient PhD guidance.

Further develop the Design Research Line and give it a distinct profile which will make it internationally competitive. Recent changes in pedagogical programmes of the Department will allow the colleagues involved to dedicate more focused energy to this line, which at the moment has delivered one PhD.

Further activate the communication and collaboration between the research leaders and research coordinators. We have currently instigated a quarterly meeting between the research leaders and each one of the coordinators in order to detect research opportunities and strategise more efficiently towards future research plans.

Update the format and content of the Department Research Days to assist the researchers in their actual work and grant acquisition. Ranging from workshops where previously submitted (but not awarded) research proposals can be analysed, studied and reworked, to workshops with colleagues from the University's Impact and Innovation Centre to help with specific disciplinary specificities (as design is not considered scientific research, for example), the Department will dedicate Research Days in the forthcoming years to tackle such difficulties.

Create a more inclusive culture of research output. Research conducted by architectural researchers requires means of dissemination that go beyond the written form. Exhibitions, podcasts, drawings, and models are other means to conduct research in architecture, and the Department will ensure that such outputs can find a proper place in the academic culture of the Department and most importantly beyond.

Initiate the Delft Architectural Symposium Series, bringing to the fore our colleagues' research qualities and creating relationships that bridge individuals from the different sections with varied research interests and international researchers. The form of the symposium will include various ways of research dissemination (from presentations to exhibitions and from workshops to roundtable conversations), actively advocating for the new academic culture the Department is embracing.

Postgraduate Research, Education and Policy

The Department will:

Continue using the Sectorplan funds. This additional funding that has become available since 2022 through the government's Sectorplannen will be used to create more funded PhD positions within the Department and use this opportunity to encourage cross-sectional collaboration.

Utilise the assistant professor starting funds for supporting its recruitment of PhD researchers and ensuring a steady influx of PhD candidates while facilitating the research initiatives of early-career academics.

Evaluate the current and newly added Graduate School courses and assess their success in offering postgraduate training and education that responds to the needs and interests of its PhD researchers. Depending on that assessment, further modifications or additional Graduate School courses will be considered.

CA2RE+Delft_2022_Talking House
by Hinnerk Utermann, 2022

Image credit: Roberto Cavallo

Case Studies Architecture

B.1.1

Engaging with the World

B.1.1.1

On Thirst and Mirage: Rethinking the Desert

The focus of this symposium was twofold. On the one hand, the symposium explored the technocratic, extractive and colonial approaches to water that have led to disentangled ecologies, the imposition of borders, conflicts and wars throughout various desert landscapes. On the other hand, the symposium paid attention to the complex relationship between the entangled milieus (of water, soil and air) which have formed the deserts through weathering processes, as well as how such entanglements have been materialised in the vernacular built environment, crafts, technique of chasing (hidden) waters and indigenous modes of governance and management. In short, the organisers and participants investigated the interconnection between culture, nature, power, techniques, and infrastructures. This symposium established a long-term research inquiry and a community to focus on desert landscapes where topics of water scarcity alongside the practices of spatial demarcation, migration, transgressions and even ongoing colonisation, adaptation and justice can be discussed and investigated. The symposium was organised by Negar Sanaan Bensi.

For more information, see: <https://www.borders-territories.space/on-thirst-and-mirage-rethinking-the-desert>

B.1.1.2

International Conference: Technogeographies of Care: Future Healthspaces

The conference focused on contemporary care practices, which occur increasingly online and are supported by a diverse range of digital infrastructures and actors. Putting on the foreground the fact that who performs care work is a deeply political question, it explored the critical question: How can we care well in a digital age? Since caring has become a set of complex, nuanced processes that require deeper understanding, it is harder and harder to pinpoint where care actually happens. Is it in the cloud, in clinics, or in chatrooms? More importantly, why does this matter? The question of where care takes place was investigated in depth through various contributions, as it is particularly relevant for architects and designers who are charged with imagining and shaping spaces that can support good care in a changing world. The conference's title 'technogeographies of care' was borrowed from Nelly Oudshoorn's work, who used it to capture how technologies «create interdependencies and distribute dependencies between people, places and technical devices» and «connect previously distinct places (...) creating new sites where care takes place». The conference engaged critically with these new sites, asking where to care well in a digital age, and was organised by Dara Ivanova.

For more information, see: <https://www.aanmelder.nl/167325/home>

B.1.1.3

Living Data International Conference

Data art, data visualisation, designing with data, and data-making can be helpful tools for bridging the empirical methods of science and the creative processes of architecture, leading to promising new ways to address climate challenges. The Living Data Conference explored how these practices promote exchange between scientific and artistic disciplines with the fundamental purpose of seeking responsive and innovative solutions for the design of the built environment. Four main thematic areas were explored during the symposium, via keynote lectures, discussion sessions and workshops. These thematic areas were: 1. Practicing Data for Design; 2. New Vision for Living Data; 3. Designing Data: Natures of Living; and 4. Data for People: Situated Society. The conference was organised by Angela Rout.

For more information, see: <https://www.livingdatastudies.com/conference-2025>

B.1.1.4

Posthuman Symbioses Masterclass: A Thinking-With Donna Haraway and Rosi Braidotti

Focusing on the urgent question of our 'becoming-with' environments, the 'Posthuman Symbioses Masterclass' aims to find conceptual tools for redirecting future architecture and urban design towards a more sympoietic direction that may mitigate the increasingly complex crises in the Anthropocene. As the posthumanist philosopher Rosi Braidotti argues, the environmental, social, and technological transformations that define the present can no longer be addressed separately by the sciences, humanities, and engineering.

This disciplinary separation along divisions of nature, culture, and technology prevents the approach of these immense and irreversible problems as processes that are created, co-constituted, and co-individuated by design. The concept of sympoiesis elaborated in Donna Haraway's well-known work critically extends autopoietic notions of self-organising systems by attending more closely to the forms of co-evolution in which things always 'become-together-with' other things. The event is conceived as an intergenerational experience of 'learning-with' Haraway and Braidotti as leading (eco) feminist/posthumanist theorists, and (PhD) students with a keen interest in adopting and adapting their approaches in their own research and designerly work.

The wider intention is to generally foster inter- and trans-disciplinary approaches to architecture and urban design that embrace the life sciences or humanities, and especially posthuman/sympoietic approaches, situated forms of knowledge, and 'minor' angles. The event was organised by R. Gorny and A. Radman. For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/bk/over-faculteit/afdelingen/architecture/organisatie-1/secties-en-groepen/theories-territories-transitions/architecture-philosophy-and-theory/research-publications/posthuman-symbioses-masterclass>

B.1.1.5

2ALL Addis Ababa Living Lab

The 2ALL Addis Ababa Living Lab is a transdisciplinary project awarded a research grant by NWO – WOTRO (Dutch Research Council – Science for Global Development). The project involved the participation of faculty members from TU Delft, the Ethiopian Institute of Architecture Building Construction and City Development (EiABC), as well as governmental agencies, international design practices, and non-profit organisations. The complete team consists of: Elias Yitbarek, Marja Elsinga, Dick van Gameren, Zekarias Sebsbie, Nelson Mota, Frederique van Anandel, Henk Jonkers, Rahel Shawl, Edo Abraham, Haral Mooij, Anteneh Tesfaye Tola, Brook Teklehaimanot Haileselassie,

Mahlet Yared, Yonas Alemayehu Soressa, Mulu Haile, Maartje van Eerd, Haregewoin Bekele, Tsegaye Moshe Fireh.

The goal of the Addis Ababa Living Lab was to improve the livelihood of Addis Ababa's urban dwellers via the contribution of different disciplinary territories – from urban planning, to design, to ethnography. More concretely, the project's goal was to: 1) provide adequate, safe, healthy, and affordable housing; 2) improve skills and capacity of local planners, developers and contractors for co-creation; 3) increase the knowledge for implementing housing programmes towards resource efficiency.

Within the framework of the Addis Ababa Living Lab project, four main work packages were developed:

- 1 **Patterns of inhabitation:** a PhD project developed by Brook Teklehaimanot Haileselassie on ethnographic patterns in Addis Ababa's housing typologies;
- 2 **Processes of Urban Resettlement:** a PhD project developed by Yonas Alemayehu Soressa on Addis Ababa's urban planning and infrastructure;
- 3 **Participatory Planning and Design:** an experimental housing project by architecture firms Mecanoo and RAAS;
- 4 **Holistic Approach to Urban Resettlement:** a post-doctorate research by Anteneh Tesfaye Tola on the development of new urbanisation policies in Ethiopia.

The 2ALL Addis Ababa Living Lab constitutes an example of a multi-faceted project that blends traditional academic research with societal collaborations and education. In fact, the project included the development of master's-level courses at TU Delft and the development of two PhD projects.

The output of this project has been varied and continues to reverberate through other forms. The 2ALL Addis Ababa Living Lab's results have included conventional publications (papers, books, contributions to edited volumes), but also design proposals and interactive online interfaces that simulate design scenarios (Housing for All: <https://addis-ababa-living-lab.com/serious-game/>). More recently, part of the work initiated by the Addis Ababa Living Lab has become a short film titled «When I came to your Door.» The film was directed by Antonio Poletti and co-produced by Frederique van Aniel and Marja Elsinga. It has been presented at different venues, and won different prizes, including first prize at the Venice Architecture Film Festival. <https://iffr.com/en/iffr/2025/films/when-i-came-to-your-door>

The Addis Ababa Living Lab not only built a bridge between the Dutch and the Ethiopian contexts, but it also favoured the production of a body of knowledge that is accessible and agile in its multiple formats of dissemination, and transdisciplinary both in its methods and in its application. Lastly, the Addis Ababa Living Lab constituted, for the Department of Architecture and TU Delft in general, the chance to tackle global issues from a non-Western perspective, sensitive to the complexity of the Ethiopian context and eager to activate long-term engagement with this reality. Within the body of research developed at the Department of Architecture, the Addis Ababa Living Lab has paved the way for similar future opportunities.

For more information, see: <https://addis-ababa-living-lab.com/>

COST ACTION: Writing Urban Places

Writing Urban Places proposed an innovative investigation and implementation of a process for developing human understanding of communities, their society, and their situatedness, by narrative methods. It focused particularly on the potential of narrative methods for urban development in European medium-sized cities.

By recognising the value of local urban narratives – stories rich in information regarding citizens' socio-spatial practices, perceptions and expectations – the Action articulated a set of concrete literary devices within a host of spatial disciplines, bringing together scientific research in the fields of literary studies, urban planning and architecture, and positioning this knowledge vis-à-vis progressive redevelopment policies carried out in medium-sized cities in Europe.

Writing Urban Places comprised three thematic targets to be explored theoretically as well as in case studies:

- 1 **Meaningfulness:** offering local communities and professionals the ability to improve their understanding of their built environment;
- 2 **Appropriation:** empowering communities by improving their ability to project their feelings onto their built environment;
- 3 **Integration:** offering concrete tools and methods for the construction of common ground among communities, based on relations of meaningfulness and appropriation of their built environment.

Based on a robust investigative tradition in these fields, the Writing Urban Places Action brought together solid experience in linking the literary and narrative and the built, and offers the necessary scientific background for the assessment of the contemporary city, while cherishing and enhancing the specificity of local urban cultures in the European context. The Action organised numerous international conferences and meetings, while it produced various journal issues, edited books, films and in situ workshops.

The project is run by Professor Klaske Havik and core team Dr. Jorge Mejia, Dr. Aleksandar Stanicic, Dr. Angeliki Sioli, among other international colleagues.

For more information and a complete list of outputs see here: <https://writingurban-places.eu/>

Creating Ties with the Creative Industry

KIEM GRANTS (last four years)

2026-2027: ToolGether; Generating Engagement and Trust in Housing Environments for Resilience

Addressing housing vulnerability in the Caribbean by creating a gamified design tool that enables collaborative development of resilient, affordable homes. It blends local insights with expert knowledge, engaging residents, builders, and professionals. A transdisciplinary consortium leads the effort, aiming to scale solutions for low- and middle-income communities living in hazard-prone regions.

For more information, see: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/projects/pwzwk28916>

2025-2026: Carb-hub; Climate-Adaptive, Resilient, and Balanced Hubs

Addressing environmental and carbon-related challenges in the built environment through a design-driven research framework. By integrating data analysis, material research, and spatial design, the project demonstrates how academic research can support architectural practice in developing actionable strategies for carbon awareness and reduction.

For more information, see: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/projects/sbrex58302>

2024-26: Creating Changemakers; A Serious Game for Disaster Preparedness]

Facilitating the emergence of resilient citizens and communities by making them aware of potential challenges before disasters strike. To achieve the emergence of such resilience, the project works to create a cultural change that brings disaster response from the public level to the local citizen and to communities. To increase disaster awareness, build capacity, facilitate local action and train trainers, this project develops a serious game on a physical tabletop that allows individuals and communities to work with a moderator and to simulate disasters along with individual and collective action in their locality. This grant continues the work done with serious gaming earlier in the Water Values game (KIEM grant 2020).

For more information, see: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/projects/awqyh40057>

2023: Intelligent Carbon Footprint Prediction from Architectural Design Visuals

Helping architects and engineers to validate their strategies for sustainable design practice. The focus is the development of intelligent tools to predict a building's carbon footprint in the early stages of architectural design. This project offers a method to automate the exchange between designer and environmental advisor, in which computer vision is used to determine CO2 emissions directly from architectural drawings.

For more information, see: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/projects/gocikiem02017>

2022-2023: Walk-In; Weighting Sustainable Mobility Network Impact on Nodes

Exploring inclusive spatial design strategies by combining architectural research with direct collaboration between designers, users, and institutional partners. The project translated academic insights into practical design approaches while simultaneously enriching education and further research through empirical findings. Link: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/projects/gocikiem01045>

The older, 2021, KIEM [«Time Travel»: Amsterdam Quaywalls and Bridges] has led to participation in the 2023-2028 Groeifonds Multifunctional Quaywall project that occurs in participation with AMS and the City of Amsterdam, where the HAUP leads WP7.

A presentation of the project can be found here: <https://www.portcityfutures.nl/projects/multi-functional-quay-walls-towards-methods-and-concepts-for-connecting-past-present-and-0>

First results are published here: <https://bluepapers.nl/index.php/bp/article/view/217>

Shaping a Faculty-wide Research Agenda

Data Refinery Lab

The Architectural Data Refinery Lab at TU Delft's Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment is part of the BK Labs. The BK-Labs are laboratories within the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment. They are involved in both education and research, stimulating lively collaboration between students, academics, and public and private partners. The BK-Labs facilitate novel ideas across a range of disciplinary fields and address relevant social issues. The Data Refinery Lab is a cross-Departmental hub for design, research, and innovation. It is dedicated to rethinking the role of data in architecture, planning, and heritage. Hosted by the Department of Architecture, the Data Refinery Lab offers a platform where data, design, and responsibility converge. All BK researchers, educators, and students of any academic level are invited to participate. Topics might include practical concerns, such as data structuring, annotation, and processing; but foundational issues like data sharing, ownership, and ethics are also welcome. On top of that, the lab offers support or advice when organising seminars, workshops, and debates centred on data.

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/en/architecture-and-the-built-environment/research/bk-labs/data-refinery-lab>

Theories of Architecture Fellowship Program

The Theories of Architecture Fellowship Program (ToA FP) is a research and curatorial initiative of the Department of Architecture that raises questions about architecture, its disciplinary constraints, its interactions and overlaps with other fields, and the expansion of its theoretical horizons vis-à-vis research and practice. ToA FP looks beyond the research produced in the Architecture Department towards insights being produced elsewhere in the field, creating opportunities for the academic exchange of knowledge on the theoretical and practical dimensions of architecture today. Its main aim is to generate a space where different ideas, perspectives, approaches, and methodologies are discussed as they shape contemporary architectural research (theories and practices). As a platform, it provides a public forum that fosters the encounter of

our research community and student body with the work of researchers and practitioners active in other contexts via a visiting fellowship programme. In this way, the programme promotes the sustained interactions of young researchers, early career academics, emerging thinkers, established scholars, as well as artists and practitioners from other institutions with our community over an extended period, instead of one-time lectures or punctual interventions. Over a period of two weeks, visiting fellows interact in different modalities with our researchers, PhD candidates, students and the wider community of the Faculty of Architecture. Through public lectures, PhD workshops, participation in student reviews, and discussions with research groups within the Department, the invited fellows bring research topics, methods and points of view that enrich and inspire the research of our faculty.

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/bk/onderzoek/onderzoek-bij-bouwkunde/architecture/theories-of-architecture-fellowship-program>

B.1.3.3

Jaap Bakema Study Centre

The Jaap Bakema Study Centre is a collaborative project of the Nieuwe Instituut and the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment of TU Delft. It initiates and undertakes research projects that result in exhibitions, publications, and public events, often in collaboration with third parties and within international networks. The Jaap Bakema Study Centre combines contemporary social issues with fundamental research and knowledge development in the field of the creative industry: design, culture and society.

The Jaap Bakema Study Centre was founded at the end of 2013 by the Nieuwe Instituut and the Faculty of Architecture of Delft University of Technology (TU Delft) to initiate scientific research in the field of architecture and urban design together with third parties. The collections of the National Collection for Dutch Architecture and Urban Planning form the basis for a research programme that is situated at the intersection of advanced historical and theoretical research and urgent social issues. The activities are divided into several long-term projects.

The Jaap Bakema Study Centre is directed by Dirk van den Heuvel with the support of an international academic advisory board. Board members are Tom Avermaete (ETH Zurich), Sofie De Caigny (Nieuwe Instituut), Maristella Casciato (Getty Research Institute), Carola Hein (TU Delft) and Georg Vrachliotis (TU Delft).

For more information, see: <https://nieuweinstituut.nl/en/projects/jaap-bakema-study-centre>

Open Access Publications

Footprint Delft Architecture Theory Journal

Footprint is an academic journal dedicated to publishing architecture and urban research. The journal promotes the creation and development – or revision – of conceptual frameworks and methods of inquiry. It is engaged in creating a body of critical and reflexive texts with a breadth and depth of thought which would enrich the architecture discipline and produce new knowledge, conceptual methodologies and original understandings.

For more information, see: <https://journals.open.tudelft.nl/footprint>

Ecologies of Architecture TU Delft Open Book Series

The Ecologies of Architecture Book Series promotes a transdisciplinary approach to architectural thinking and doing by extending its interest to topics that bring together the three ecological registers, namely the environment, the social and the individual. Such an approach accounts for what the built environment will come to be, and speculates about who will become alongside it. The series focuses not only on the why, what and how of architecture, but also on the who, with whom and for whom. The Ecologies of Architecture presents scholarly work in the form of peer-reviewed monographs and edited volumes on the following themes and areas of expertise: the ecological turn, affect & affordance theory, philosophy of science & technology, digital humanities, AI, new materialisms, agential realism, geophilosophy & geopolitics, and decolonial, queer and feminist theories.

For more information see: <https://books.open.tudelft.nl/home/catalog/series/ecologies-of-architecture>

Writingplace TU Delft Open Book Series

Writingplace for Architecture and Literature is a peer-reviewed, open-access book series, published by nai010 publishers and TU Delft OPEN Publishing. It was originally launched as a journal series in 2018, after the international Writingplace conference on literary methods in architectural research and design (2013) and the subsequent book publication Writingplace: Investigations in Architecture and Literature (2016). After nine journal issues, Writingplace moved to a book series in 2025 and continues to act as a vehicle for the exchange of knowledge on the relationship between architecture and literature. Its mission is to address and promote alternative ways of looking at and designing architecture, urban places and landscapes through literary methods. By acknowledging the possibilities of literature as a field of academic research, able to explore architectural imaginations, Writingplace establishes a common ground to investigate the productive connections between architecture and literature. The book series presents thematic issues ranging from pedagogy, spatial analysis and critical theory to artistic practices, individual buildings, landscape and urban design.

For more information, see: <https://journals.open.tudelft.nl/writingplace>

City of Innovations TU Delft Open Book Series

The City of Innovations series explores the intersection of architecture, urban mobility, and sustainability through collaborative and interdisciplinary design. It tackles urgent challenges such as urbanisation, inclusivity, climate adaptation, material scarcity, renewable energy, and the societal impacts of AI and automation. A key focus is the transformation of urban transportation infrastructure and its role in shaping how people interact with cities. The core question of the series is how Design Research can integrate architecture, urban design, and human experience to respond to rapid societal, environmental, and technological changes. It explores how design can serve as a tool to foster dialogue, identify opportunities and constraints, and finally create spaces that are functional, inclusive, and resilient in the face of constant transformation. By investigating the relationships between these fields, the series aims to uncover strategies for creating cohesive, sustainable, and human-centred urban environments in times of shifting conditions. The series is developed by the Complex Projects group within TU Delft's Department of Architecture, with contributions from academics, students, and professionals.

For more information, see: <https://books.open.tudelft.nl/home/catalog/series/city-of-innovations>

B.1.3.5

Berlage Keynotes & Sessions

The Berlage Keynotes is an ongoing lecture series featuring internationally prominent architects, designers, and thinkers who are at the forefront of design discourse and innovation. A selection of speakers working from different disciplinary perspectives and in different geographic, cultural, and political contexts present how their work engages with contemporary issues and debates. Next to it, the Berlage Sessions is a thematic seminar series focusing on scholarly research and critical approaches to the history and theory of architecture and urban design.

For more information, see: <https://theberlage.nl/events>

B.1.3.6

Architectural Pedagogies Research Line

The Department recognises its institutional responsibility to educate future professionals capable of addressing complex and urgent challenges in the built environment. Meeting this responsibility requires ongoing, structured research into the

methodological and epistemological foundations of architectural education. Research and education are therefore institutionally integrated, and architectural education is understood as both a pedagogical practice and a distinct field of research. The Department's core commitment is to develop, consolidate, and advance knowledge produced through and in relation to architectural education.

Academic staff operate at the intersection of teaching and research, with the studio environment functioning as a central research infrastructure in which research questions, methods, and outcomes are developed, tested, and evaluated. Student work plays a key role in this process, serving as a primary medium for research exploration and dissemination. The plurality of pedagogical positions within the Department is regarded as a strategic research asset, enabling comparative reflection on educational models and supporting students in developing independent, critical, and responsible architectural positions. Through the systematic collection and critical reflection of research projects, pedagogical experiments, and publications emerging from educational practice, the Department positions architectural pedagogy as a recognised research domain within the faculty and in external academic and professional contexts.

This Research Line operates as a transversal structure across the Department and in collaboration with other Departments within the faculty, rather than as a conventional research unit centred on internal PhD projects. Its objectives are to coordinate and strengthen research on architectural pedagogy, to represent the Department in faculty-wide and institutional educational research initiatives, and to position its pedagogical research within international academic and policy-oriented debates on architectural education. Selection of projects and publications:

Projects

- 1 Comenius research grant Angeliki Sioli 'The Space of Words: Modelling Spatial Atmospheres from Language' (2022)
- 2 Comenius research grant Nelson Mota 'Housing as Healthcare: Mapping the correlation between housing design, microbiodiversity and health in The Hague' (2023)
- 3 Horizon 2020 grant 'TACK / Communities of Tacit Knowledge: Architecture and its Ways of Knowing' (2019-2023); see info: <https://www.tudelft.nl/bk/onderzoek/projecten/communities-of-tacit-knowledge-architecture-and-its-ways-of-knowing>
- 4 Erasmus+ Strategic Partnership grant 'CA²RE+; Collective Evaluation of Design Driven Doctoral Training'; see info: <https://www.tudelft.nl/bk/onderzoek/projecten/ca2re>

Books

- 1 CA²RE+ Delft Recommendation: Conference for Artistic and Architectural Research & Collective Evaluation of Design-driven Doctoral Training Programme (2023) <https://books.open.tudelft.nl/home/catalog/book/61>
- 2 City of the Future Graduation Lab: Experiences in Multidisciplinary Education (2023) <https://books.open.tudelft.nl/home/catalog/book/66>
- 3 Teaching Architecture: Insights from TU Delft – Research on Education Innovation in Architecture & the Built Environment (2025) <https://bookrxiv.com/index.php/b/catalog/book/60>
- 4 Architectural Education In Times Of Uncertainty (2023) <https://books.bk.tudelft.nl/press/catalog/book/806>

Speculative Urban Futures Erasmus+ LSI Project

Speculative Urban Futures (SURF) investigates the role and purpose of design in the twenty-first century – understood as an ecology of knowing, imagining and making that is deeply involved in the complex worlding dynamics shaping contemporary reality. The version of design that emerged in the early twentieth century continues to play a dominant role in shaping the model upon which the (global Western) world is founded. While the potential of design as a worlding dynamic is clear, it is less evident how its objectives, metrics and methodologies have contributed to the construction of a world that is increasingly showing signs of failure and collapse. The once dominant world model reveals itself as fragile, broken and highly unsustainable, adding to the sense that its future continuation is uncertain. This raises fundamental questions about this particular world model, how we represent and render it, how we adapt to or challenge it, and, importantly, how we may dare and care to imagine and speculate – through novel design methods – other possible, plausible, potential, and preferred worlds that are seated in difference. To this end, SURF aims to develop, test and share a host of new design methods and pedagogical tools that may help us foster the conditions needed to achieve key reforms and meaningful, fundamental changes that are necessary to align design with some of the demands and challenges of the twenty-first century. In short, based on speculative design approaches in situated urban settings, SURF focuses on the development of new design methodologies and epistemologies that may guide us towards mitigating existing environmental devastation as well as building other worlds. These will exist as five pilot packages that encompass all the educational materials required to replicate each course in other academic, civic and corporate contexts.

SURF is an educational project funded by ERASMUS+, the European Union programme for education, training, youth and sport, with the aim of strengthening design education by collecting and exchanging existing knowledge and experience while developing new methods in the field of design. This three-year project (1 September 2023 – August 2026) brings together leading European academic/research institutions from design practice, education and research. The consortium is led by the ENSCI les Ateliers (France), and consists of Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), Elisava Barcelona School of Design and Engineering (Spain), The University of Split (Croatia) and the Estonian Association of Architects (Estonia).

The project is run by Stavros Kousoulas, Andrej Radman and Heidi Sohn.

For more information, see: <https://surfutures.eu/>

B.1.3.8

AI Insights

AI Insights is a forward-thinking series for students, PhDs, and educators passionate about shaping the future of design. It explores how emerging technologies are transforming the values and institutions of our built environment, framed by five foundational pillars of society: Health and Well-Being, Mobility and Connectivity, Safety and Justice, Education and Knowledge, and Housing and Habitat.

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/en/architecture-and-the-built-environment/research/research-at-bk-bouwkunde/digitalisation-and-artificial-intelligence/ai-insights-series>

B.1.3.9

2050 Mobility Futures

A multidisciplinary team of TU Delft mobility researchers, known as The Mobilisers, embarked on a journey to explore the future of mobility and how it is embedded in various socio-technological contexts. They developed four radical, yet realistic scenarios for the Dutch Mobility System in 2050, taking into account the Netherlands' position as part of Europe and its role as an international hub. Read more about our method Strategic Foresight.

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/transport-mobility-institute/mobility-futures> and <https://www.tudelft.nl/transport-mobility-institute/mobility-futures/expert-perspectives>

A Leading Voice in International Architectural Research

Refereed and Peer-reviewed Journal Publications

Our Department's most important journal outlets are *Urban Planning*, *Planning Perspectives*, *Bulletin KNOB: Koninklijke Nederlandse Oudheidkundige Bond*, *Sustainability and Spool: Journal of Architecture and the Built Environment*. Apart from these five key outlets, research of members of the Department of Architecture is also regularly featured in *ABE Journal*, *Architectural Histories*, *Architectural Theory Review*, *Architecture and Culture*, *ARQ: Architectural Research Quarterly*, *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*, *Grey Room*, *Historic Environment: Policy and Practice*, *History and Technology*, *Home Cultures*, *International Journal of Islamic Architecture*, *Journal of Architectural Education*, *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences*, *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, *Journal of Planning History*, *Journal of Urban History*, *Oase: Tijdschrift voor Architectuur*, *Political Geography*, *JSAH*, *The Journal of Architecture*, and *Urban Geography*. The breadth of the research agendas pursued at the Department of Architecture is reflected in the wide range of topics addressed in these refereed articles. They, for instance, examine the efficacy of participatory workshops as a tool for building inclusivity in new towns in Africa, analyse living concepts suitable for elderly homeowners, study port city infrastructures and petroleumscapes, question the contemporary value of traditional craftsmanship, highlight the effect of climate change on cultural heritage, bring to light the work of female architects, scrutinise the impact of global flows on architectural design, ponder theoretical/philosophical questions, propose the implementation of new methods (e.g., literary methods) in architectural education and even address the design-to-robotic-production of underground habitats on Mars. This list only offers a glimpse of the multitude of topics that are addressed in refereed articles published by members of the Department of Architecture, which contribute both to local architectural culture and global questions of architectural design.

Book Publications (Selection)

Rem Before Koolhaas: Journalism by an Architect

— Antonio Cantero (nai010publishers, 2026)

Rem Before Koolhaas is the first book to explore Rem Koolhaas's early journalistic work for the Haagse Post between 1963 and 1967. In this publication, Antonio Cantero takes a fresh look at this period and interviewed Koolhaas specifically for this book. Cantero explores how Koolhaas's interviews evolved into essays that reveal power dynamics and cultural shifts. Featuring original newspaper layouts and texts translated into English for the first time, Cantero's book reveals Koolhaas as both an observer of his time and an interviewer for whom writing became a space for learning. Rather than viewing this period as simply a prelude to his architectural career, *Rem Before Koolhaas* presents this work as an essential part of his oeuvre, underscoring the importance of journalistic storytelling for architecture and capable of being read in its own right.

For more information, see: <https://www.nai010.com/product/rem-before-koolhaas/>

Athens: Notes on Urban Immanence

— Stavros Kousoulas (Routledge, 2025)

Focusing on the city of Athens, this book examines architecture as something that produces culture and ideology — rather than the opposite. Therefore, this book aims to complement architectural and urban theories that are based only on historical overviews or typological assumptions; to do so, it boldly opens architectural discourse to philosophy, affect theory, and social and cognitive sciences.

By examining Athens after its denomination as Greek capital in 1834, the moments, actors, and transformations that assist the individuation of the Athenian urban ecologies are problematised. Opting for theoretical speculations, the readers will witness architecture as a collective equipment that produces modes of life that can either enhance or diminish our collective potentials. As such, the ambition of this book is to provide the theoretical and methodological groundings for thorough extrapolations on how new collectivities can be produced.

Readers of this book will be exposed to a transdisciplinary approach that identifies and addresses shared problems and concerns regarding the production of contemporary urban environments. This book will also explore theoretical innovations that can inform and trigger new ways of speculative thinking and offers a non-reductionist account of the development of Athens from the perspective of multiple architectural technicities. This book is of interest to researchers and students of architecture, architectural theory, architectural history, and philosophy.

For more information, see: <https://www.routledge.com/Athens-Notes-on-Urban-Immanence/Kousoulas/p/book/9781041095767>

Exteriorless Architecture: Form, Space, and Urbanities of Neoliberalism

— Stefano Corbo (Routledge, 2024)

The current phase of capitalist development manifests itself through a very diverse range of spatial byproducts: data centres, warehouses, container terminals, logistics parks, and many others. Generally considered as mediocre and banal examples that sit outside of pre-established disciplinary canons, these architectural episodes are

extremely relevant. They are relevant not for their aesthetic or historic qualities but for what they represent – for the system of values these spaces embed. They express specific power relations, exacerbate issues of labour, and generate dramatic processes of subjectivity. Most importantly, these architectures, despite their formal and typological heterogeneity, belong to a common paradigm: the EXTERIORLESS.

How can an architecture of the EXTERIORLESS be defined? How does it differentiate from examples and manifestations of the past? How do notions of legibility, form versus function, and typological articulation come into play?

In situating the spatialities of contemporary capitalism within the larger debate on Anthropocene, Post-Anthropocene, and Capitalocene, the book attempts to answer those questions by delineating three main characteristics for an architecture of the EXTERIORLESS: its physical and symbolic role as interface; its ambiguous condition of being at the same time local and global, isolated and connected, compressed and expanded; and, lastly, its contribution to new forms of urbanity in the absence of the traditional city. These three defining aspects constitute the main sections of the book. Each section includes two chapters covering a wide spectrum of themes and examples. In its tripartite organisation, the book describes the influence that the experimental architecture of the 1960s has exerted on late-capitalist spatial byproducts; it analyses the impact of logistics on the redesign of the territory; and it introduces the radical processes of urban transformation generated by the EXTERIORLESS.

For more information, see: <https://www.routledge.com/Exteriorless-Architecture-Form-Space-and-Urbanities-of-Neoliberalism/Corbo/p/book/9781032170824>

Architecture in the Age of Mediatizing Technologies

– Sang Lee (Routledge, 2024)

This book offers a novel perspective on contemporary architecture, exploring its position in mediatization, attained through technological apparatuses. It introduces the novel concepts of apparatus-centricity and mediatization of architecture, which have significant disciplinary and cultural ramifications.

Highlighting key technological and theoretical developments, the book's narrative traces the transformation of architecture from the modernist era to the present digital age. En route, it reflects on how architecture becomes a crucial element of shifting dispositives through its confluence with technologies of aestheticisation and virtualisation, and by emblematising ecological ideals. It also illuminates the reconfiguring of architectural practice through examining surprising interactions and analogies between architecture and music, whose developments in notation and codification continually change the relationship between composer and performer. The book explores how architecture is reshaped by broader theory and practice in media and ultimately serves as a cognitive agent. It underscores that architecture profoundly influences our phantasmagoric, image-driven affective world through its increasingly apparatus-centric approach to conception, design, production, and mediatization.

Architecture in the Age of Mediatizing Technologies brings into focus the behaviour of architecture in mediatization for researchers and advanced students in architectural design, theory, and history. As an investigation into the interdisciplinary impact of architecture in a mediated culture at large, it also provides a valuable resource for cultural and media studies.

For more information, see: <https://www.routledge.com/Architecture-in-the-Age-of-Mediatizing-Technologies/Lee/p/book/9781032060590>

The City in the City: Architecture and Change in London's Financial District

— Amy Thomas (MIT Press, 2023)

An exploration of the dramatic transformation of London's financial district after 1945, viewed at four spatial scales: city, street, facade, interior.

In *The City in the City*, Amy Thomas offers the first in-depth architectural and urban history of London's financial district, the City of London, from the period of rebuilding after World War II to the explosive climax of financial deregulation in the 1980s and its long aftermath. Thomas examines abstract financial ideas, political ideology, and invisible markets as concrete realities; working on four spatial scales — city, street, facade, and interior — the book explores the grand plans, hidden alleys, neo-Georgian elevations, and sweaty dealing floors that have made the financial centre work.

Moving from politics to sociology, institutions to bodies, development plans to office desks, Thomas unravels the rich entanglements between the structure of the UK's financial system and the structure of the environment in which it operates. Despite its physical and political centrality, this period of the City's architectural history occupies an academic lacuna. Longstanding prejudices about developer-led architecture and the real estate industry have obscured the postwar City's relevance. The book shows how, as currents of local government reform, nation-building, and globalisation swept across Britain, the City became an ideological battleground for debates between politicians and financial institutions, real estate developers and architects, preservationists and so-called «proactive» planners throughout the latter half of the century.

The City of London is a place steeped in rich cultural and architectural heritage of immense national significance, yet it is also a highly privileged citadel at the core of global financial networks. *The City in the City* is both a critique and a celebration of this unique and complex place.

For more information, see: <https://direct.mit.edu/books/monograph/5705/The-City-in-the-CityArchitecture-and-Change-in>

Architectural Technicalities: A Foray Into Larval Space

— Stavros Kousoulas (Routledge, 2022)

This book poses a simple question: how is this architecture possible? To respond, it will embark on a captivating journey through many singular architectural concepts. The entasis of Doric columns, Ulysses and desert islands will outline an architectural act

that moves beyond representation. A ferryman who stutters will present two different types of architectural minds. A stilus and a theory of signs will reconsider the ways architects can develop a particular kind of intuition, while architectural technicities will bring forth a membranous and territorial understanding of architecture. Finally, as a melody that sings itself, a larval architecture will be introduced, bringing space and time together.

Assisting this endeavour, the thought of philosophers like Gilles Deleuze, Felix Guattari, Gilbert Simondon and Raymond Ruyer will meet the latest developments in fields like affect theory, cognitive sciences, environmental studies and neuroanthropology. Eventually, by the end of this book, the readers – from architecture students and researchers to academics and practitioners with an interest in theory – will have been exposed to a comprehensive and original philosophy of architecture and the built environment.

For more information, see: <https://www.routledge.com/Architectural-Technicities-A-Foray-Into-Larval-Space/Kousoulas/p/book/9781032235257>

The New Technological Condition: Architecture and Design in the Age of Cybernetics

– Georg Vrachliotis (Birkhäuser, 2022)

In the era of cybernetics, architects suddenly encountered entirely new ways of operating technical systems: buildings could be calculated using circuit diagrams, creativity and imagination were confronted with the technical intelligence of thinking machines. Architects found themselves in the crosshairs of cybernetics. At stake was nothing less than the continued existence of the architect's inventive intelligence in a techno-scientific world.

Today, we see computing machines, once so heavy, losing weight while gaining power. Computers are fully colonising the human environment, creating their own digital ecosystems, and giving rise to forms of society and ways of being that cannot even be explained without big data. Available for the first time in English as a new edition.

For more information, see: <https://www.architectura.nl/architecture/the-new-technological-condition-architecture-and-design-in-the-age-of-cybernetics.html>

B.1.4.3

Edited Volumes (Selection)

Poetics of Place

– Klaske Havik, Angeliki Sioli (TU Delft), Vincent A. Cellucci (TU Delft Library),
Jeremy Allan Hawkins (University of Strasbourg) (TU Delft Open and nai010publishers, 2025)

Architects and poets alike experiment with writing as a spatial act, using verse and reflection to navigate landscapes both real and imagined. But how does poetry emerge from place, and what knowledge of place can poetry reveal for architects, designers, and spatial practitioners? This inaugural volume of the Writingplace book series investigates the fertile ground where architecture and poetry meet, revealing how their intersection can deepen our understanding of spatial experience and the making of place.

Poetics of Place brings together literary and spatial perspectives in articles, reflections, and creative works that consider how language itself shapes spatial perception. Poet, educator, and activist contributors — using literature or poetic writing as a means of investigating place — examine how poetry evokes a sense of situatedness and how writing itself can act as a spatial practice. Through poems, a visual essay, and conversations, Poetics of Place becomes a textured space of its own — one that informs, inspires, and invites place-curious readers of all kinds to experience how poetry and place continually create one another.

For more information, see: <https://books.open.tudelft.nl/home/catalog/book/215> and <https://www.nai010.com/product/poetics-of-place/>

Datapolis: Exploring the Footprint of Data on Our Planet and Beyond

— Negar Sanaan Bensi (TU Delft) and Paul Cournet (TU Delft Open and nai010publishers, 2023)

Data has become a critical component of our lives — when was the last time that you spent 24 hours offline? Despite such ubiquity, we hardly comprehend the mechanisms of this 'infosphere', a complex world that can be glimpsed through tangible and intangible means.

DATAPOLIS looks into the materiality of data, its inherent ethical and political contradictions as well as cultural and environmental footprints, by following two main trajectories: the first one attempts to define what 'the cloud' is and how it operates. From the systems and infrastructures behind the Internet to the apparatus, gizmos and buildings that can transcend scales and temporal dimensions. The second one explores how data penetrates our existence, not only by affecting the ways we live and work, or design and make cities, but by offering distinct ways of life and organisation that otherwise would not have been possible.

Through various visual and textual materials, this book speculates on the ways in which architecture can engage with data and digital technology beyond its mere instrumental use in making (smart) cities.

For more information, see: <https://books.open.tudelft.nl/home/catalog/book/91> and <https://www.nai010.com/en/product/datapolis/>

Architectures of Resistance: Negotiating Borders Through Spatial Practices

— Angeliki Sioli (TU Delft), Nishat Awan (UCL), and Kristopher Palagi (LSU) (Leuven University Press, 2024)

Borders between countries, neighbourhoods, people, beliefs, and policies are proliferating and expanding despite what self-proclaimed progressive societies wish or choose to believe. For a wide variety of reasons, the early 21st century is caught struggling between breaking down barriers and raising them. Architecture is complicit in both. It is central to the perpetuation of borders, and key to their dismantling. *Architectures of Resistance: Negotiating Borders Through Spatial Practices* approaches borders as sites of meaningful encounter between others (other cultures, other nations, other perspectives), guided not by fear or hatred but by respect and tolerance. The contributors to this volume — including architects, urban planners, artists, human geographers, and political scientists — address spatial boundaries as places where social and political conditions are intensified and where new spatial practices of architectural resistance arise. Moving across contemporary, historical, and speculative conditions of borders, *Architectures of Resistance* discusses new and innovative forms of architectural, artistic, and political practice that facilitate constructive human interaction.

For more information, see: <https://lup.be/book/architectures-of-resistance/>

The Space of Technicity: Theorising Social, Technical and Environmental Entanglements

— Robert Gorny (TU Delft), Stavros Kousoulas (TU Delft), Dulmini Perera (Limerick University), and Andrej Radman (TU Delft) (TU Delft Open, 2024)

Desperate times demand optimistic transdisciplinary measures. This volume unites a select group of thinkers who courageously traverse disciplinary boundaries. What brings them together is the least stratified 'component': a shared problem. It is widely recognised that a problem gets the solution it merits. However, only a few acknowledge that a problem seldom neatly fits within a single discipline, nor does it conform to the principle of general equivalence. Handling its irreducibility and non-entailment is a skill possessed by very few. Even fewer take the quasi-causal capacity of what we term the 'space of technicity' seriously.

The Space of Technicity allows us to evade techno-determinism without adopting an anything-goes attitude. That which has become manifest could have individuated differently. However, the potential of a body cannot be discerned before intervening in the causal fabric of agential reality to extract the singular points that make certain outcomes more likely than others, surpassing mere probability.

When operating within the ethico-aesthetic paradigm, where sense becomes intricately dependent on sensibility, and vice versa, the volume's attitude might be said to approximate the Spinozian third kind of knowledge that intuits design (and its space of technicity) beyond mere imagination or reason.

For more information, see: <https://books.open.tudelft.nl/home/catalog/book/95> and <https://www.japsambooks.nl/products/the-space-of-technicity>

Design Commons: Practices, Processes and Crossovers

— Stavros Kousoulas (TU Delft) and Gerhard Bruyns (Hong Kong Polytechnic University) (Springer, 2022)

This book directly links the notion of the commons with different design praxes, and explores their social, cultural, and ecological ramifications. It draws out material conditions in four areas of design interest: social design, commons and culture, ecology and transdisciplinary design. As a collection of positions, the diversity of arguments advances the understanding of the commons as both concepts and modes of thinking, and their material translation when contextualised in the domain of design questions. In other words, it moves abstract social science concepts towards concrete design debates. This text appeals to students, researchers and practitioners working on design in architecture, architecture theory, urbanism, and ecology.

For more information, see: <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-95057-6>

B.1.4.4

Conference Organisation

Jaap Bakema Study Centre Annual Conference

Since the inception of the Jaap Bakema Study Centre in 2014, it has hosted an annual conference. Over the years, the centre's various research areas of interest have been addressed in these events.

For more information, see: <https://nieuweinstituut.nl/en/projects/jaap-bakema-study-centre/conferenties>

CA²RE Community for Artistic and Architectural Research Conferences

This event is a part of the CA²RE+ Erasmus+ Strategic Partnership. It is the 6th Intensive Study Programme for Doctoral Candidates within the Strategic Partnership. The project was developed as a parallel and a trigger to the continuity of the CA²RE Conferences for Artistic and Architectural REsearch. CA²RE+ develops a collective learning environment through Evaluation of Design Driven Doctoral Training. Design Driven Research (DDr) is taken as a multidisciplinary example of an experiential learning-through-evaluation model, appropriate for identification and promoting relevance of research singularity, its transparency and recognition, to award excellence in doctoral training for creative and culturally rooted solutions of contemporary design-driven developments. The conference was organised by Roberto Cavallo and Alper Semih Alkan.

For more information, see: <https://delft.ca2re.eu/>

Deleuze and Guattari Studies International Conference and Camp

The 16th International Deleuze and Guattari Studies Camp and Conference focused on the processes of subjectification. This has been a longstanding concern of Deleuze and Guattari since their ground-breaking work, *Anti-Oedipus* (1972), which provides a tripartite theory of the production of subjectivity. Guattari further developed a schizoanalytic approach to social formations, extending *Anti-Oedipus*'s three syntheses

into a more general account of three broader ecologies that are differentially enacted by environmental, social, and mental technics. Today, these ecologies can no longer be addressed in isolation by the sciences, humanities, and arts. Fifty years since Anti-Oedipus, this line of transversal thinking seems more pertinent than ever for thinking through becomings and subjectivation processes in the milieus of digital media ecologies, the changing techno- and noo-spheres engendered by hyperautomation, algorithmic governance, and increasingly systemic forms of disempowerment. The conference was organised by Stavros Kousoulas, Andrej Radman and Heidi Sohn.

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/en/bk/over-faculteit/afdelingen/architecture/organisatie/groepen/theories-territories-transitions/architecture-philosophy-and-theory/research-publications/16th-deleuze-guattari-camp-and-conference-2024-intelligence-instituting-and-archiving>

B.1.4.5

The New Open

The New Open is a magazine for those who see design as a form of critical thinking, questioning, observing, and reshaping the systems that govern public and private space, culture, and collective life. It brings together essays, interviews, experiments, and archives that reflect on how data shapes the built environment.

The New Open aims to rethink the politics of information by fostering new forms of architectural literacy and public knowledge. The New Open is open-access and non-peer-reviewed, but carefully curated and professionally edited.

The New Open invites contributions from across disciplines and geographies. It publishes incrementally, with new materials released throughout the year. The New Open is produced by the Design, Data and Society group at TU Delft Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment. The editor-in-chief is Georg Vrachliotis.

For more information, see: <https://newopen.design/>

B.1.4.6

AIBlocks Podcast

AIBlocks is a platform for sharing knowledge about artificial intelligence and its potential to empower architectural design research and practice. We are a group of AI researchers who are passionate about design. We break down the latest academic papers, chat with industry leaders and designers about what's happening out there, and share tutorials and lectures – covering everything from the basics of AI to the big ideas on how it's shaping our homes, cities, planets, and beyond. Whether you're an AI

researcher curious about the application of AI in architecture, or an architect/architecture student looking to dive into AI-driven and data-driven design, we think we have something here for you.

For more information, see: <http://www.youtube.com/@TheAIBlocks>

B.1.4.7

BK Public Programs

The Public Programs of the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment, TU Delft, are a platform for those involved in the fabrication of the city to share their ideas about the understanding, conception and production of the built environment.

On Tuesday evenings throughout the academic year, the Public Programs include the BK Talks and the Berlage Keynotes (mentioned already in 7.3.4), as well as exhibitions, workshops, seminars and colloquia. These events are aimed at connecting our faculty, students and scholars with the myriad disciplines and cultures that shape our world, with an eye towards cultivating public activities beyond the Delft Campus.

The Public Programs build the Faculty's relationships with allied institutions and the scholarly community at large. They are an invitation to the broader academic community and public to engage in discussions about the world in which we want to live and reflect on ideas to achieve its transformation.

The Department of Architecture has contributed actively to both BK Expo and BK Talks, with several of its members being returning guests throughout the programme of the past years.

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/en/architecture-and-the-built-environment/current/public-programs>

Critically Updating PhD Education

New PhD Courses for Architectural Research

To advance the level of PhD research, the Department of Architecture worked collectively to create five new PhD courses, tailored specifically to the needs of research within the architectural field. In April 2025, the Department dedicated one of its recurrent research days to the development of these courses. Each of the five Research Sections was assigned to develop one course, with the premise that the five courses collectively will work to complement each other. During the research day, which was open to all research colleagues and PhD candidates, first draft ideas on the courses were presented, discussed, workshopped and refined, following the European Competence Framework for Researchers. Based on the work of this research day, all courses were then finalised and submitted for approval at the Faculty's Graduate School. The result is the following new PhD courses, which have been already implemented and started running in the 2025-26 academic year.

Cultural Contexts and Dissonant Sources

Research is always embedded in cultural contexts, through the background of the researcher, the situation of the research topic, the collection process, the availability and sensitivity of primary sources, and the ensuing implications of research for design, theory and practice. In this PhD course, PhD candidates will develop awareness and expertise in working with primary sources. They are encouraged to frame their research topics through critical analysis of cultural contexts, in light of their positioning as researchers, while exploring potential sensitivities and analytical 'dissonances' of the research material. This course is intended to help PhD candidates refine their thesis topic, assess and interpret archival and other primary sources, and communicate (in speech and in writing) with peers and broader audiences about the cultural and historical contexts of their research topics. Methodologically, the focus of the course lies on primary sources, hermeneutical research, and empirical evaluation. The course also comprises on-site research visits, to underscore the relevance of academic research within an expanded professional context.

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/bk/onderzoek/graduate-school-a-be/doctoral-education/discipline-related-courses/abe020>

Situated Writing

Situated Writing helps PhD researchers to develop a solid understanding of different modes of writing used in architectural and urban research. The course familiarises

participants with a set of methodologies for written architectural research and their underlying historiographic and epistemological underpinnings.

It allows them to articulate situated accounts of selected topics and areas of (inter-, cross- or transdisciplinary) research. During the course, participants will be discussing, studying, and experimenting with a set of writing approaches from discourse analysis to cartographies, from narrative approaches to site-writing, from micro-histories to oral history. The main goal of these exercises is to showcase the potential of certain modes of writing, so that researchers can more consciously position themselves vis-à-vis their research subject, their sources and their way of writing about them.

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/bk/onderzoek/graduate-school-a-be/doctoral-education/discipline-related-courses/abe-021>

Architectural Research and Problematisation

Building on a transdisciplinary ethos and ambition, the proposed GS course wishes to assist PhD researchers (of the Architecture Department and the Faculty as a whole) in developing a speculative approach through their (initial) research trajectories, as well as positioning their research aims and ambitions. It will bring into action an approach where theory and practice relay transitionally with one another through the development of speculative research questions. In other words, the course will underline the importance of problematisation: the productive development of research problems, crucial for any research interest and trajectory, especially at an early stage. In doing so, it will also assist PhD researchers in exploring the potential format of their PhD (e.g., monograph, paper publications, etc.).

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/bk/onderzoek/graduate-school-a-be/doctoral-education/discipline-related-courses/abe-027>

Working with Primary Sources

As PhD researchers, you are increasingly confronted with a vast and complex array of primary materials, which extend far beyond traditional documents to include archival records, large-scale datasets, exhibitions, interviews, and even existing buildings. Each medium possesses its own unique evidentiary value, epistemic potential, and inherent biases. This course will focus on working with and through these diverse primary materials to generate situated arguments. We will examine together how these sources can be curated, activated, disrupted and re-narrated through different methodological lenses. You will experiment with your own primary material using digitisation, datafication, animation, and spatial storytelling techniques.

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/bk/onderzoek/graduate-school-a-be/doctoral-education/discipline-related-courses/abe-028>

Socio-material Entanglements. Forms and Patterns of Inhabitation in the Built Environment

This Graduate School course aims at dissolving the strict separation between the scale of the domestic and that of public buildings. The course will delve into the different

forms and patterns of inhabitation that characterise the relationship between humans, non-humans and the built environment, with a particular focus on practices of everyday life. Students will be introduced to methods that allow the investigation of those relationships, such as architectural ethnography, occupancy and post-occupancy evaluations. At the same time, through a series of lectures, readings and collective discussions, they will also be exposed to concepts such as the commons, place/world-making, publicness, and genius loci, so as to develop a comprehension of spatial phenomena which is not only related to the built form but mostly to its social and cultural components. In other words, opposed to traditional typological taxonomies, this PhD course will investigate socio-spatial phenomena as well as explore transdisciplinary methodologies. The overall goal is to find inter- and cross-sectional approaches that can be applied to the comprehension of different domains. Therefore, the course welcomes participants from fields other than architecture, by suggesting a perspective on the investigation of the everyday that goes beyond rigid disciplinary boundaries.

For more information, see: <https://www.tudelft.nl/bk/onderzoek/graduate-school-a-be/doctoral-education/discipline-related-courses/abe-029>

AE+T is positioned at the interface of engineering sciences and architecture

Architectural Engineering + Technology

At AE+T, we focus on the design and technologies that make buildings function: structure, envelope and environmental systems. Traditionally, this has required large quantities of materials and energy, with significant impacts on human well-being and the environment. The built environment contributes substantially to major socio-environmental challenges, including the climate crisis, resource scarcity and the vulnerability of buildings. AE+T is positioned at the interface of engineering sciences and architecture, enabling us to develop and advance strategies and technologies that address pressing societal needs by building on recent developments in the fundamental sciences. In doing so, we make notable contributions to both the fundamental sciences and real-world applications.

Summary

The Department of Architectural Engineering and Technology (AE+T) at TU Delft focuses on the design and development of technologies that enable buildings to function efficiently and effectively across scales, from materials to individual buildings and entire districts. Our mission is to drive transformative change in the built environment so that resources are used responsibly, resilience to climate challenges is strengthened, and positive value is created for both people and nature

Our department

AE+T consists of five sections: Structures & Materials; Building Design & Technology; Digital Technologies; Environmental & Climate Design; and Heritage & Architecture. The sections are supported by a transparent governance structure that includes the Management Team, the Strategic Board, and a renewed PhD Admission Advisory Committee. In 2025, a new Department Head initiated further strategic alignment and internal dialogue.

Our Research Vision

Our research addresses urgent societal challenges: climate change, resource scarcity, and health in the built environment. Until 2025, our work was organised under four broad themes: sustainability, circularity, health and comfort, and digitalisation. AE+T has since identified three purposeful ambitions to address these challenges and is reshaping its long-term strategy accordingly:

- A **resource efficient** built environment;
- A **resilient** built environment;
- A **regenerative** built environment.

These ambitions reflect our commitment to reducing environmental impact, strengthening the capacity of buildings and communities to adapt to change, and developing solutions that deliver net positive outcomes for both ecosystems and society.

Achievements

AE+T researchers have secured significant national and international funding, including the Faculty's first NWO Veni in the engineering domain. We have published widely in leading journals, produced books for both experts and the general public, and developed open access software and datasets to advance digital innovation. Simultaneously, new and expanded laboratories, including GlassLab, SmartLAB and MateLab, have reinforced AE+T's strong experimental identity.

Our work has had tangible impact beyond academia: prototypes and full-scale demonstrators were executed with industry partners; research informed public policies on energy, circularity, and indoor environmental quality; and AE+T projects and student work appeared in museums, festivals, exhibitions, and (inter)national media.

Synergy with Education

AE+T maintains a strong link between research and education, especially through the MSc Building Technology programme. Students contribute to research-driven design courses often involving realworld prototyping, and their work frequently features in public exhibitions.

Looking Ahead

The coming years present both opportunities and challenges. AE+T benefits from its strong reputation, interdisciplinary culture, and broad external networks. At the same time, national budget cuts, hiring restrictions, heavy teaching loads, and limited seed funding pose threats to long-term viability. In response, AE+T will continue to sharpen its strategic focus, strengthen collaboration, expand open science practices, provide structured support to research initiatives, and increase the visibility and accessibility of its research for society.

FIG. 2.1 Organisation diagram AE+T Department

Introduction

Research at the Department of Architectural Engineering and Technology (AE+T) spans the full technological spectrum of the built environment, focusing on how buildings are conceived, engineered, operated, and transformed. Our work addresses:

- resource efficiency and circularity;
- developing new materials;
- manufacturing methods;
- product systems that close and slow material loops;
- environmental and climate design;
- improving indoor environmental quality;
- resilience to climate change, and energy performance;
- digital technologies, including computational design methods, digital twins, and large-scale spatial analysis;
- heritage and architectural transformation;
- integrating technological innovation with the preservation;
- adaptive reuse of existing and historic buildings.

The AE+T Department comprises five sections, each led by a section leader and supported by a management assistant:

- **Structures & Materials (SM)**, led by Stijn Brancart;
- **Building Design & Technology (BDT)**, led by Thaleia Konstantinou;
- **Digital Technologies (DT)**, led by Michela Turrin;
- **Environmental & Climate Design (ECD)**, led by Craig Martin;
- **Heritage & Architecture (HA)**, led by Wido Quist.

Mauro Overend has headed the Department since October 2025, preceded by Michiel Kreutzer (2021-2025). The Department head leads the broader Department dialogue, both strategic and operational, as well as representing the Department to the Faculty, University, and the external world. All topics formally mandated by the Department head, including the allocation of staff and financial resources, are discussed and collectively decided on by the AE+T management team (MT). The MT consists of the Department head, Department manager, *the five section leaders, the education manager, the MSc Building Technology coordinator, the research coordinator, the HR advisor* and business controller* (the asterisk indicates non-academic staff). The section leaders are responsible for education and research matters, operational and strategic HR management of the section, and financial administration and reporting, in line with departmental norms. They coordinate the decision-making process across the section and take part in departmental management team decisions on behalf of the section. AE+T's Strategic Board (SB) includes the MT and all full professors of the Department. The SB is the department's scientific think tank and advises the Department on longer-term non-operational matters: policy, strategy, positions and goals. Finally, department-wide meetings are held regularly to involve and interact with all Department staff members.

AE+T has its own PhD Admission Advisory Committee (PAAC). The PAAC assesses the quality of prospective PhD and post-doctoral candidates, the fit with the research agenda of the Department, and the quality of their research proposals, and advises the

intended promotor (i.e., supervisor) and MT. The PAAC is composed of two members with *ius promovendi* (i.e., academic staff who can serve as primary supervisor) from each. They meet once a month.

2.3

Mission and strategic aims of the past four years

2.3.1

Mission and research themes in the period 2022-2025

AE+T is at the forefront of one of the most important challenges of the 21st century: meeting the demand for better-performing buildings considering our planet's finite resources and the negative impacts of construction and building usage on the environment. This major challenge requires a fundamental shift in the way the built environment is valued, designed, built, exploited, maintained, transformed and dismantled. Therefore, in the past few years our mission has been: **Through integrated research and education in architectural engineering, we advance technology to enable the design of a better-built environment considering our planet's finite resources and with added value for people and nature.**

AE+T's research was centred on the following four major themes, aligned with the strategic Faculty research themes:

- A **sustainable built environment** for new, existing and heritage-designated buildings, with attention to a broad range of values, climate adaptation and mitigation, resilience, energy positivity, renewable energy and nature inclusion;
- A **circular built environment**, focusing on already existing buildings, efficient use of resources, product design, manufacturing and new product service systems;
- A **safe, healthy and comfortable built environment**, addressing aspects of indoor environmental quality, including ventilation and the prevention of the spread of diseases, as well as aspects of the outdoor climate of the built environment, such as the local micro-climate, human liveability, nature-inclusiveness and biodiversity;
- A **digitally enhanced built environment and decision-making processes**, supporting data, information and knowledge in design, manufacturing, construction and use.

Previously set strategic aims for operational approach 2022-2025

In the 2022 full-term research assessment, we had set out eight strategic aims, as summarised here. Management-related aims took the priority in our plan, in view of the ongoing changes in the department's policies that needed to be addressed. Other aims, such as those related to academic culture, visibility and open science, are still under development and will come to the fore in the coming years, as presented in [Paragraph 2.7].

- **Academic profile.** Development and creation of more leadership positions strongly related to architectural and building technology, via internal career development or, when needed, external hires. [achieved];
- **PhD Policy.** Aim to reduce the number of self-funded PhD candidates (i.e., not hired as research staff and without sufficient financial support from external scholarships), who experience more pressure and unequal conditions compared to salaried PhDs. Stimulate interaction within the PhD community and active engagement of PhDs in Department activities. [achieved, although under debate];
- **Financial strategies.** Cover all costs for permanent positions with first-stream money (structural funding), while using third-stream money (temporary funding) to cover only temporary positions. [achieved];
- **Academic culture.** Foster a collaborative and respectful environment that encourages cooperation and benefits from the strengths of a diverse community. [ongoing];
- **Governance.** Shift financial and managerial responsibilities to sections rather than chairs, to streamline the complex internal structure and make it more transparent. [achieved];
- **HR Policies.** Widen the hiring procedure to include views and promote strategic discussion by the entire Department. Reduce uncertainty and internal competition created by the Tenure Track policy, in line with University-wide new policies. Promote diversity in career paths and reward non-academic experience. [ongoing];
- **Visibility.** Increase our visibility and connections with strategic stakeholders, by prioritising visibility-related tasks over educational pressure. [ongoing];
- **Open Science.** Develop further open science practice by educating existing and new scientific staff. [ongoing].

Feedback from previous review

Overall, the committee assessed the AE+T Department as having very good research quality, with elements of excellence; excellent societal relevance; and good viability, with potential to be excellent but challenged by the financial situation, in which part of the permanent staff was funded by the third money stream. The feedback from the 2022 assessment concerned four major points: strategic topical aims (feedback further emphasised by the University Executive Board); relation to industry and larger society; engagement of PhD community; and leadership profiles.

Strategic topical aims and resulting workload. We were urged to reduce the number of aims and sharpen them to work more cohesively and strategically across sections, and to form a more distinctive profile of our Department and its characteristic strengths.

Actions: We have been working on a new framework to focus and showcase our research towards three key aims: a resource-efficient, resilient and regenerative built environment. We are also in the process of rephrasing our mission to better reflect this shift. [Paragraph 2.7] presents a work-in-progress mission and aims for the coming years.

Relation to industry and larger society. Feedback recommended exploring opportunities for patent applications and spin-offs from our applied research. At the same time, while recognising the importance of industrial collaboration and our excellence in industry-relevant research, the committee felt that any risk of compromising research independence and integrity should be mitigated early on through dedicated internal policies. In terms of relationships with the larger society, the committee recommended continuing to focus on research that works *with* society rather than only *for* society, emphasising the importance of co-creation, action research and citizen-led initiatives.

Actions: We maintain a strong connection with industry and we work on industry-relevant research, as clearly shown in the accomplishments highlighted in [Paragraph 2.6]. We considered the suggestion on patents and spin-offs but concluded that this is not in line with our research strategy. Rather, we prioritise efforts towards Open Science practices and generation of knowledge that is independent from commercial interests. We strive to maintain the same independence and integrity at all levels of academia-industry collaborations. As for our relationship with the larger society, we recognise that we still need to place more emphasis on it in our research portfolio, starting from the planning of research proposals and leading on to effective valorisation initiatives. Collaboration, co-creation and action research will remain points of attention in our contacts with societal stakeholders. These points are part of our future strategy presented in [Paragraph 2.7].

Engagement of PhD community. The committee praised the decision to create a common space for PhD candidates to work side by side but suggested offering flexible alternatives as well, namely for candidates who need a different work environment for specific tasks and at specific stages of their doctoral programme. The importance of keeping PhD candidates engaged with other departmental activities was also stressed, starting from a smoother and more structured onboarding procedure at the beginning of their programme.

Actions: We promoted new policies to cater for the diverse needs of our PhD community, by offering options for seating arrangements (common space or office of the related section), within the constraints of limited office space in our building. We created onboarding procedures for all new staff and clarified the distribution of responsibilities between supervisors and departmental officers. This was part of our strategic process for the past years as described in [Paragraph 2.4].

Leadership profiles. The committee took note of the scarcity of senior staff who can take leadership positions and recommended striking a balance between junior and senior staff when strategising new hires. At the same time, a balance should be found between practice-oriented and research-oriented full professors, to guarantee competitiveness in building science and research. Furthermore, efforts of junior staff who take on more administrative or educational roles than typically expected from them should be acknowledged with transparent but flexible promotion criteria that map the Recognition and Rewards programme.

Actions: Our hiring and promotion strategy was aligned with these objectives and had a notable impact on our staff composition and academic profile, particularly in balancing early- and advanced-career staff and industrial and academic expertise, as outlined in [Paragraph 2.4]. There is still a worrying pressure on junior staff tasked with administrative and educational roles and a general lack of clarity about promotion criteria for alternative career paths. We are addressing these points as part of our future strategy presented in [Paragraph 2.7].

2.4

Strategy (including the strategic process)

Our Department strives to be at the forefront of architectural engineering and building technology. To do so, we need a strong and agile academic profile that leads innovation in the built environment by responding to the latest developments in the fundamental sciences and to societal needs. In the past four years, we prioritised the enrichment and cohesiveness of our academic profile through new hires and collaborations, supported by improvements in our financial and governance structure. We worked on the transparency and openness of our processes, embracing the necessary self-reflection brought by the broader University-wide discussion on social safety. We continued our successful efforts in disseminating our research findings to academic, industrial and societal audiences, while working on even greater visibility of the department's strengths and talents that can leave a lasting impact on society.

Concept development and positioning

The mission and research themes of AE+T have remained largely unchanged for several years, including the last four-year period, but more recently we engaged in new discussions about potential revisions to both mission and themes. In doing so, we are responding to the evolving context around us and to the new capabilities from recent hires, laboratory facilities, etc. These new additions to our academic profile gave us new perspectives to tackle urgent societal challenges. This is still an ongoing process, but the first results have been used to shape our new strategic process, described in Paragraph 2.7.

Increase departmental cohesion

As a first key step, efforts were taken to bring the whole Department together when discussing strategic goals and future vision, mostly materialised in two key activities: a new hiring procedure for academic staff that involves the entire department, rather than being confined to the chair/section responsible for the new position; and regular weekly lunch seminars (AE+T Bites) open to all staff (junior, senior, academic and non-academic). Several workshops and away-days were also organised for the entire department, exploring connections and synergies that the Department could leverage to sharpen its strategy and common vision.

Strategic partnerships

We strengthened our links with other faculties and University services such as The Green Village and the Campus Real Estate directorate, and our role within University-wide networks such as the Climate Action Programme (with our flagship project Cool and Clean Buildings), through collaboration in projects and research proposals, with the goal of working more synergistically within TU Delft. At international level, the Department has successfully engaged with policymakers and funders across a range of stakeholders. Examples include representation on the board of a multi-billion Euro EU funding programme on materials and working on setting the agenda and actions for the proposed FP10 EU Horizon programme. The Department has representation on EU DG working groups (JRC, Grow - HADeA, Trade) on materials research agendas.

We established new partnerships in key research areas, such as circularity (CIRCLETECH Hub, partnership with the University of Miskolc and Lappeenranta–Lahti University of Technology), pandemic preparedness (Pandemic & Disaster Preparedness Center) and heritage and the reshaping of urban conservation for sustainability (UNESCO Chair). We continued successful partnerships that keep us connected with centres of excellence worldwide and provide numerous opportunities for academic collaborations, such as the European Façade Network and DOCOMOMO, which moved its secretariat to our Department in 2022. We have also launched initiatives to partner with industrial excellence, for example by establishing the Jaap Oosterhoff Chair, which brings recognised experts from industry to visit our Department every six months for five years (2025-2030), and with the multi-year funding framework with Syntus Achmea to boost research and education in bio-based materials.

Personnel and funding acquisition

Our acquisition strategy operated at two levels: acquiring research funding and resources for our existing expertise, and identifying key disciplines or key talents to add to our portfolio through external hires. The Department implemented mechanisms to develop new funding proposals that engage more experienced staff with earlier-stage researchers. Regular meetings are held to discuss opportunities for national, EU (mainly Horizon Europe) and other sources of funding.

Strengthening of our academic profile

We opened several academic positions with the explicit goal of attracting internationally recognised talents, current and future leaders in forward-thinking architectural engineering approaches, and experts in disciplines that are critical for addressing the grand societal challenges. Funding for some of these positions was the result of our strategic positioning within the Sector Plan scheme, a national initiative to boost capacity in recognised centres of excellence and to entrust specific universities, faculties and departments with strategically important areas of research.

Our overarching criteria for the selection of new staff were academic excellence, teaching potential and collegial attitude. We established a search and multi-stage selection framework that involved all staff in the department, thereby improving transparency, impartiality and inclusivity in the selection process. The framework had the knock-on benefits of increasing department-wide collaboration and aligning new hires with the mission of the entire Department. A mix of internal promotions and external hires guaranteed both continuity and diversity of our academic portfolio and departmental culture. All new assistant professors were given a start-up package equivalent to one PhD position and joined the new Academic Career Track (ACT) programme, which replaced the Tenure Track (TT) programme. These are some of the steps taken to better support early-career talents in the initial stages of their work at the Department. In doing so, we help them build an even stronger profile that can compete nationally and internationally for highly competitive grant applications and other high-impact opportunities. In addition to these goals, these new positions also provided an opportunity to further improve our gender and diversity balance. Table 2.1 provides insight into new academic staff hired after 2021, including their diverse backgrounds. In the process, we took significant steps towards recruiting more non-EU staff and addressing gender balance, which respond directly to comments received at the previous assessment. We recognise that it will take time for this gender balance and diversity to ripple through to the more senior positions. This positive action also brings new challenges, primarily related to Dutch language proficiency, which is a prerequisite for teaching in our BSc programme. International staff members are therefore encouraged to follow language courses, including one offered by the Faculty, but reaching a high level of language proficiency from a standing start takes significant time and effort and comes at the expense of other activities. Meanwhile, the shrinking number of Dutch-speaking staff risks being overloaded with teaching duties.

TABLE 2.1

NEW ACADEMIC STAFF HIRED BY AE+T					
	Position (Section)	Alma Mater (PhD)	Previous employer	Gender	Nationality
2023					
Telesilla Bristogianni	Asst Prof (SM)	TU Delft	TU Delft	F	EU
Alex de Rijke	Prof (SM)	-	dRMM Studio	M	Non-EU
Annemarie Eijkelenboom	Asst Prof (ECD)	TU Delft	EGM Architecten	F	Dutch
2024					
Lidwine Spoorans	Asst Prof (HA)	TU Delft	TU Delft	F	Dutch
Gabriele Mirra	Asst Prof (DT)	The University of Melbourne	University of Southern Denmark	M	EU
Zhikai Peng	Asst Prof (ECD)	University of Cambridge	TU Delft	M	Non-EU
Nan Bai	Asst Prof (HA)	TU Delft	Wageningen University	M	Non-EU
Simona Bianchi	Asst Prof (SM)	Sapienza University of Rome	TU Delft	F	EU
2025					
Pei-Yu Wu	Asst Prof (DT)	Lund University	ETH Zurich	F	Non-EU
Ronald Schleurholts	Prof (HA)	-	Cepezed	M	Dutch

In addition to fostering a diverse community, there is an ongoing discussion on promoting diversity in career paths (Recognition and Rewards movement), acknowledging excellence that is not necessarily limited to 'traditional' research indicators and activities, but that values contributions towards tackling societal, pedagogical or institutional aspects of academic work. In our field, we value leading-edge design and consulting experience, as evidenced by the hiring of two new full professors from architectural design studios. Meanwhile, our esteem for a research-focused profile is undiminished, as demonstrated by the internal promotion of Martin Tenpierik to full professor in 2025, through the rigorous research-focused career path, thereby paving the way for current more junior staff.

Supporting our PhD community

We secured a steady intake of PhD candidates primarily through Sector Plan funding and several successful grant-aided research proposals. In the past years, we streamlined the selection, hiring, and onboarding processes for our PhD candidates, in accordance with Faculty Graduate School best practice. The hiring process for PhD positions funded within projects secured by AE+T staff is under the responsibility of the mentoring team for all vacancies, which follows a well-structured process and includes training on unconscious bias. The procedure is different for externally funded (scholarships and industry funding) and self-funded candidates; the Department PhD Admission Advisory Committee (PAAC) was reorganised from earlier committees in 2023 to guarantee strict selection criteria on academic excellence that are comparable to those applied for salaried positions, thus ensuring a consistently high bar for admitting PhD candidates. In 2025, a University-wide policy halted the intake of self-funded PhD candidates and of candidates with scholarships that did not meet the minimum stipend requirements in the Netherlands and the University tuition and bench fees. The vulnerability of the PhD community was also at the centre of the University-wide debate

on social safety, sparked by the education inspectorate report. As part of the department's commitment to address socially unsafe behaviour, all AE+T staff members in leadership positions followed training sessions on social safety and on being an active bystander. All staff were invited to participate in department-wide townhall sessions to raise awareness and share concerns about the issue. We raised the number of PhD mentors at AE+T from two to three and we took further actions to promptly implement tools and strategies provided by the Faculty Graduate School and more broadly by the University (e.g., publicising the new reporting procedure and decision map). Further discussions were held in smaller settings (e.g., at section level), where people felt more at ease to speak up about their worries and negative experiences.

2.4.3

Project set-up, research execution and project management

Our governance structure and internal administrative procedures went through some major changes in the past four years, mostly aimed at increasing transparency and streamlining processes within the Department. Some of these changes were met with broad departmental support while others are the subject of ongoing discussion and possible reshaping to increase effectiveness and achieve broader consensus.

Governance, finance and HR policies

The administrative and financial structure underlying the department's research units went through major changes. We moved away from the annual targets of funding acquisitions that were previously set to cover part of the base salary costs of permanent staff, and we achieved a more robust structure where base funding is used for permanent salaries and external funding is used for temporary positions. This shift was successfully completed before the national budget cuts (effective from 2025 and with expected repercussions until 2030). Some unresolved issues and challenges remain in the funding of strategic department assets (e.g., maintenance and technicians for our laboratories, seed funding for junior staff, etc.). At the same time, the budget cuts have resulted in fewer temporary teacher hires and are thus putting more pressure on all permanent academic staff to fill the breach in education capacity. Meanwhile, many of the responsibilities that were assigned to chairs have been reassigned to the sections (e.g., decisions on finance and career progression), which operate directly under the head of Department and coordinate themselves within the management team, with the aim of increasing transparency and reducing hierarchical stratification. This is still an ongoing process that needs to be further embedded and collectively shaped by all members of the Department and that plays a key role in our current and future research strategy. Furthermore, it is a relevant discussion for our visibility to external parties, as it influences the way we present different aspects of our collective academic profile. These points have been central in workshops and discussions held in these years and will be brought forward in our future strategy.

New onboarding procedure

Several steps were taken to make it easier for new staff, including PhD candidates, to navigate the large structure of our Faculty and University, and to facilitate onboarding. The new procedure included the creation of an AE+T Guide that offers an overview of the organisation and explains how things operate at AE+T, as well as a checklist for the secretariat to ensure proper facilities are arranged, and welcome and introduction meetings are scheduled to make our new colleagues feel welcome. These are key measures to support a more inclusive academic environment. By improving the clarity of structures, procedures and expectations, the Department helps reduce barriers and supports colleagues with different backgrounds and levels of familiarity with the Faculty and University. In this way, the initiatives contribute to Equity, Diversity and Inclusivity (EDI) goals through improved access, support, and a sense of belonging.

2.4.4

Communication, dissemination, impact and exploitation

To improve our visibility and dissemination strategies, we first focused on strengthening our departmental profile and identity. This required us to coordinate and frame our two most tangible assets: our experimental facilities and our digital strategy. Our first step was to clearly delineate our role and contribution within the Faculty and within the University, in coordination with the other departments. By identifying our unique selling points and the precise societal challenges that we are responding to, we are better positioned to work on our external visibility.

Experimental facilities

Staying true to our departmental experimental and 'hands-on' nature, we continued to valorise and expand our laboratories within BK Labs. Besides the established Lama Lab, SenseLab, Heritage & Technology Lab, VR-Lab, Bucky-Lab, Light Van, ERiC Lab and Geo-Database Management Center, new labs and facilities were inaugurated in the 2022-2025 period: the GlassLab, located in the BK building, which includes water-jet cutting facilities and a digital microscope able to produce high-resolution images with depth composition; the SmartLAB, which has transformed two office floors of our own building into a Living Lab; and the MateLab, a testbed for innovative facades, building system controls and human-centred comfort models, located at The Green Village. These new additions consolidated our profile in two of our research spearheads: glass and façade technologies. Their clear identity and visibility within and outside the BK Faculty provide plenty of opportunities to showcase our work to visitors, students and other stakeholders. New funding was secured for the construction of a brand-new laboratory building, the BioBuild Lab, which is currently under construction at the Green Village and will add significant capabilities to our research on bio-based materials and construction.

FIG. 2.2 MateLab

FIG. 2.3 GlassLab

FIG. 2.4 Impression of the upcoming BioBuild Lab

opdrachtgever	
TU Delft	
exploitatie	ontwerp
THE GREEN VILLAGE	Alex de Rijke wood
directievoering	bouwkundig tekenwerk
theo kopers architecten	RONDON
contracteur	brandveiligheid
abt / adviesbureau in bouwtechniek	dGm^R
hoofdaannemer	W-installatie
WAM Van Duren / bouwbedrijf	W3 / installatie
E-installatie	hoofconstructie
compass	woodteq
gevelpanen	glasgevels
W wienerberger	SI-X
THE GREEN VILLAGE	provincie Zuid-Holland
kw / kansen voor west	Co-fundat by the European Union

Digital strategy

The development of our 'digital assets' was also addressed, and we promoted the creation of software and datasets as part of wider efforts towards Open Science practices. The AE+T department's contribution to the Faculty's 'digital pillars' is characterised by its technology and engineering approach to design, putting emphasis on the development of computational methods and techniques, digital tools and technologies. AE+T explores and develops new computational methods for modelling, designing, manufacturing and using the built environment, and promotes their development and application to address architectural engineering challenges of varying complexity and scales. We operate through a T-shaped structure of diffuse use and in-depth expertise as an asset to interconnect disciplines. Each section is engaged in using, testing, and prototyping computational methods in support of their scientific domain, contributing to the department's collective digital capacity and knowledge base. One specialised section in AE+T (Digital Technologies) develops in-depth expertise in digitalisation, clustering critical mass with technical expertise on computer science (related) subjects. This T-shaped structure allows us to enhance and complement the digitalisation efforts across the entire Department. AE+T is a key pillar of the BK digitalisation strategy – complementary to other BK digital pillars.

Synergies with education

We further reinforced the strong links between our research and our educational programme, especially at MSc level. We embedded our research methods and findings in our flagship programme, the Building Technology master track, and in the Geomatics master track, while offering technical expertise to other BSc and MSc programmes within our Faculty and to other faculties as well (mostly Civil Engineering and Geosciences and the interFaculty Sustainable Energy Technologies MSc programme). We consider the link with the Architectural master track and related graduation studios to be an essential strategy for our technical knowledge transfer to the broader architectural profession, especially through technology-led design, hands-on experimentation and creation of prototypes.

Evidence

The AE+T Department has a significant impact on the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) sector, at academic and societal level. This is evidenced in the next section by the quality indicators presented here. Such indicators show how our efforts span from fundamental scientific research to industrial applications, to impact for citizens. These indicators are primarily a source of qualitative impact rather than purely quantitative metrics. Consequently, we might place less importance on the quantum of outputs in a specific category, but we highly value the breadth and depth of outputs listed here as a strategy to engage and influence our various stakeholders in an effective manner.

TABLE 2.2

INDICATORS AE+T	
RESEARCH QUALITY	QUALITY INDICATORS
Other research output	Personal and collaboration grants PhD candidates Contract projects, consultancies
Research output	Scientific publications PhD Theses Open-source software and databases
Academic reputation and recognition	Organisation of international events Awards and keynote speeches Editorial roles Visiting positions (from and to AE+T)
RELEVANCE TO SOCIETY	QUALITY INDICATORS
Industrial recognition, collaboration and guidance	Prototypes and realised buildings Articles in professional magazines Professional fairs and exhibitions Awards and recognitions from professional / societal bodies
Synergies with education	Research-driven educational material MOOCs and other open educational platforms Research-based MSc projects
Public policies and public engagement	Policy making documents Media appearances Public exhibitions and outreach events Societal awards

Accomplishments during the past four years – research quality and societal relevance

Here we present our accomplishments in the 2022-2025 period, by considering their academic aspects in the Research Quality section and their impact beyond academia in the Societal Relevance section. This is a convenient but artificial split that fails to capture the symbiosis between the two. We therefore use the Case Studies in [Paragraph B.2] to illustrate how societal impact drives our academic research and how our academic research makes societal impact towards a resource-efficient, resilient and regenerative built environment.

TABLE 2.3

RESEARCH FUNDING AE+T								
	2022		2023		2024		2025	
	k€	%	k€	%	k€	%	k€	%
Direct funding (1)	7.976	71%	8.627	70%	9.990	79%	10.593	78%
Research grants (2)	831	7%	926	8%	465	4%	766	6%
Contract research (3)	2.305	21%	2.644	21%	2.103	17%	2.274	17%
Other (4)	88	1%	135	1%	72	1%	29	0%
Total funding	11.200	100%	12.332	100%	12.630	100%	13.662	100%
Personnel costs	10.052	94%	11.770	92%	12.810	94%	13.070	95%
Material costs	301	3%	416	3%	234	2%	242	2%
Other costs	385	4%	564	4%	543	4%	445	3%
Total expenditure	10.738	100%	12.750	100%	13.587	100%	13.757	100%
	462		-418		-957		-95	

TABLE 2.4

RESEARCH OUTPUT AE+T				
	2022	2023	2024	2025
Refereed article	97	103	88	93
Non-refereed article	1	4	2	0
Professional publications	11	8	2	6
Books	0	2	1	3
Book chapter	9	11	15	7
Publications aimed at the general public	0	1	0	3
Conference papers	48	48	59	43
PhD theses	18	11	13	9
Other research output	7	21	15	16
Total	191	209	195	180

TABLE 2.5

RESEARCH STAFF AE+T								
SEP categories	2022		2023		2024		2025	
	#	FTE	#	FTE	#	FTE	#	FTE
Assistant professor	17,3	6,5	14,8	5,5	17,2	6,3	19,9	7,6
Associate professor	10,5	3,7	11,6	4,1	11,0	4,0	10,2	3,6
Full professor	14,0	4,3	13,6	4,0	13,2	3,5	12,9	3,4
Postdocs	10,6	7,9	11,9	8,2	11,4	8,2	9,8	6,8
Researchers (other)	10,8	6,3	7,0	4,3	7,3	5,4	5,9	4,0
PhD candidate (HR)	14,1	13,6	16,3	15,8	17,6	17,5	20,6	20,5
Total	77,3	42,2	75,1	41,8	77,7	44,8	79,3	46,0
Support staff	2,0	1,8	2,7	2,1	3,3	2,2	2,7	1,9
Grand Total	79,3	44,0	77,8	43,9	80,9	47,1	82,0	47,9

TABLE 2.6

PHD CANDIDATES AE+T									
	Enrollment			Success rates cumulative					
	Male & other	Female	Total	Graduated totals		Not yet finished		Discontinued	
Start	#	#	#	#	%	#	%	#	%
2022	2	0	2	0	-	2	100%	0	-
2023	6	5	11	0	-	10	91%	1	9%
2024	5	7	12	0	-	12	100%	0	-
2025	5	5	10	0	-	10	100%	0	-
Total	18	17	35	0	-	34	-	1	-

TABLE 2.7

PHD CANDIDATES AE+T PROGRESS																	
	Enrollment			Success rates cumulative													
	Male & other	Female	Total	Graduated ≤ 4 years		Graduated ≤ 5 years		Graduated ≤ 6 years		Graduated ≤ 7 years		Graduated totals		Not yet finished		Discontinued	
Start	#	#	#	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
2016	5	4	9	2	22%	3	33%	4	44%	4	44%	6	67%	0	-	3	33%
2017	6	5	11	2	18%	6	55%	10	91%	10	91%	10	91%	1	9%	0	-
2018	7	2	9	2	20%	3	30%	5	50%	6	60%	7	70%	3	30%	0	-
2019	2	13	15	0	-	6	38%	7	44%	7	44%	7	44%	6	38%	3	19%
2020	4	7	11	1	9%	6	55%	7	64%	7	64%	7	64%	2	18%	2	18%
2021	6	2	8	1	13%	1	13%	1	13%	1	13%	1	13%	7	88%	0	-
Total	30	33	63	8	-	25	-	34	-	35	-	38	-	19	-	8	-

FIG. 2.5 Proportion male (blue) / female (orange) in research staff 2022-2025 (excl. guests).

FIG. 2.6 Proportion of nationality (NL/EU/non-EU) (excl. guests). Dark green = NL, medium green = EU, light green = non-EU.

Research quality

Project acquisition

We successfully obtained research funding from national (e.g., NWO, RVO, Click NL, TKI), EU (e.g., HE, Interreg, Erasmus+) and other international (e.g., Research Council of Norway) funding bodies, for both fundamental scientific and applied research. Many of our acquired projects are the results of strong collaborations within **inter-sectoral, interdisciplinary consortia** with active participation of industrial parties. We took the role of coordinators in a few projects, such as MULTICARE (HE-CL5), UPCAST GLASS and POINT-TWINS (NWO OTP), HeatFace (RVO TKI) and ReACT (NWO Open Science), while we participated as partners in many others.

In 2024, the Department received its **first personal grant** ever with the RECLIMATE project (NWO Veni to Simona Bianchi), the first project from the engineering panel of the NWO Talent scheme awarded to the ABE Faculty (besides those received from the social sciences and humanities panel). This is a prestigious achievement and an important recognition that our Department can also compete and lead in top-level engineering fields. It is also a positive sign for any staff member with the ambition to apply to these competitive funding schemes in the future. In the past four years, we saw roughly three unsuccessful applications per year (to Veni, Vidi and ERC Advanced schemes), and the strategic positioning of our expertise within the broader engineering field remains a challenge.

Our research was also supported by **consultancy** fees from public and private parties, which went into solving innovative, cutting-edge engineering challenges. For example, previous findings on glass recycling (Bristogianni & Oikonomopoulou, 2023) led to funding acquisition for both fundamental (NWO OTP UPCAST Glass) and applied research via the R&D of the Mirage Sculpture (Zingoni, 2025), commissioned by Apple for the Apple Park in CA, USA. Other industry-funded contract research across AE+T includes investigations on haze in high-performance glazing, a consultancy that resulted in publications and further collaborations (Luna-Navarro et al., 2024), and testing of novel glass materials for a large project in Saudi Arabia (MAI Project).

Research output

The variety of funding sources that fuel our research inevitably results in a variety of dissemination outputs and channels. We aim to reach audiences beyond our academic field and academia in general, thus we target them with the most appropriate dissemination strategy, from professional magazines and reports to books for the larger public, from databases to software for industrial applications. About 40% of our research output in the 2022-2025 period was co-authored with researchers from more than one section or from outside the department, demonstrating the importance of interdisciplinarity and collaboration in all our academic activities.

FIG. 2.7 Selection of books authored and curated by AE+T staff, aimed at both public and scientific audiences

Scientific publishing remains at the core of our activities and is our largest output, with stable numbers year by year. The journals where we published the most were: *Glass Structures and Engineering* (24), *Building and Environment* (22), *Sustainability*, *DOCOMOMO Journal*, *Buildings*, *Journal of Building Engineering*, *Energy and Buildings*, and *Land* (10), but we also published our position and recommendations on COVID-19 in *Nature* (Lazarus et al., 2022) and the performance analysis of innovative photochromic film technologies in *Advanced Materials* (Meng et al., 2024), for example. The paper (Bluyssen, 2025) led to an invitation to present in a webinar in the series «Bringing Building and Environment into the AI Era». Next to scientific papers, we authored **professional articles** in *DETAIL*, *TVVL Magazine*, *Bouwfysica Blad*, *Pioneering Tech*, *KNAW* and other magazines aimed at an industrial readership. We authored **books** aimed at scientific and public audiences on the topics of timber buildings («*Anatomy of Timber*»), indoor air quality («*Wat je moet weten over binnenlucht*»), building services («*Wat je moet weten over klimaatinstallaties*»), circularity («*Circular Communities*»), additive manufacturing («*AM Perspective*»), architectural education («*Architectural Education in Times of Uncertainty*»), climate-conscious design strategies («*Archi-tectuur als Klimaat-machine*») and historic concrete conservation («*CONCRETO Code Book*»), as well as editing and authoring a larger number of books and book chapters related to our broader expertise.

Our research in computational methods for large-scale spatial data management, digital twins, and performance-based design has resulted in **software** prototypes, workflows, and **databases** released as open-access resources. Within the EU Horizon GISCAD-OV project, validation workflows for high-precision satellite positioning produced operational digital instruments for cadastral applications. Similarly, the NLeSC-funded nD-PointCloud project resulted in a scalable software stack for large-scale point-cloud storage, querying, and visualisation.

In parallel, **digital tools and datasets** produced through MSc and PhD projects are systematically published in open-access repositories (<https://www.gdmc.nl/projects/open-source/> and Digipedia, our flagship platform for digital skills dissemination), allowing subsequent research projects to directly build upon educational outputs. Furthermore, by contributing to the development of standards (including LADM and OGC-related implementations) and the structuring and integration of national datasets such as AHN, BRK/KKN, and BRO GeoTOP, these digital outputs extend beyond academia into policymaking, spatial governance, and industry practice.

Research performed by our PhD candidates is the lifeblood of most of our research activities. In the last four years, we saw the completion and publication of 39 PhD theses from the AE+T cohort, and 12 more theses to which our staff were affiliated. PhD candidates have the choice to complete their dissertation as a compilation of scientific papers or as a monograph, with no requirement on the minimum number of publications during their programme, as officially stated by the Faculty Graduate School. This option is designed to reduce unnecessary pressure on PhD candidates and to move away from the publish-or-perish culture by educating early career researchers on the value of quality over quantity for scientific publishing.

Academic reputation and recognition

We consolidated our academic reputation and visibility through the **organisation of conferences and other academic events**. Well-established international organisations invited us to organise and host flagship conferences that attracted experts in our core disciplines to our 'home turf'. In 2022, we co-hosted with TU/e and TVVL the 14th REHVA World Congress CLIMA in the field of heating, ventilation and air-conditioning, and we organised the 7th WTA Colloquium on the maintenance of concrete buildings. In 2023, we hosted the AGILE and the 20th CAAD Futures conferences, focused on Geographical Information Science (GIS) and on Computer Aided Architectural Design, respectively. In 2024, we co-hosted together with the Faculty of Civil Engineering and Geosciences (CiTG) the 9th Challenging Glass Conference on building glass technology and innovation. In 2025, we co-hosted with TU Darmstadt the 10th edition of BE-AM, the symposium on additive manufacturing for the built environment. In addition, we maintained our tradition of organising well-known events aimed at our established networks in academia and industry, such as the Future Envelope conference (2024). We initiated further events to attract critical mass and form new networks in up-and-coming research topics, such as the Façade and Products Forum (2023), the Glass Forum (2022, 2023, 2025), the Sustainable Structural Design Forum (2023) and the Material Movement Symposium (2025).

Our role in **editorial boards** is both a sign of outstanding reputation and a way for us to give back to the academic community by supporting the peer review process,

a cornerstone of all scientific endeavours. Besides the journals that are managed directly by our Department (*Journal of Façade Design and Engineering* and the *Koninklijke Nederlandse Oudheidkundige Bond*, both entirely Open Access), in the period 2022-2025 we started new editorial roles in *Energy & Buildings* and *Build Up portal* (Thaleia Konstantinou), *Building and Environment* (Philo Bluysen), *Studies in Conservation* (Barbara Lubelli), *Intelligent Buildings International* (Mauro Overend), *Architecture, Structures and Construction* (Faidra Oikonomopoulou), and we guest-edited special issues on «Sustainable Structural Design: Resource, Reuse, Resilience», «Glass Circularity», «Early Career Researchers in Lighting», and «Challenges, Solutions, and Methods for the Energy Transition in the Existing Housing Stock».

Our research and dissemination work was well received in the scientific community and was recognised with **awards** and invitations as **keynote speakers**, and with increased trust from our partners and stakeholders, which led to continued and new collaborations. Among our most notable recognitions in the 2022-2025 period, we saw the awards to the ENSNARE Project (Best Innovation Project 2025 at the A3E Energy Efficiency and Sustainability Awards and recognition by the *EC Innovation Radar*) and to our research on glass recycling (UPCAST Glass awarded the *CircuClarity Award 2024*, Category Recycling), and several invitations as keynote speakers at international scientific events on the topics of: indoor environmental quality; cast glass and glass recycling; algorithmic decision-making for structural systems; façade circularity, human-centred facades and building technology, renovation and sustainability; AI-empowered architectural design and urban resilience; and preservation challenges of modern heritage. Many of these talks were given by assistant professors, who are already recognised as international leaders in their field. Two of our assistant professors were also recognised with a Best Young Researcher 2024 Award (by the International Association of Building Physics to Alessandra Luna-Navarro) and with a Rising Star of Computational Social Science 2025 Award (by the CAAI-BDSC to Nan Bai). At the same time, our professor of Climate Design & Sustainability, Andy van den Dobbelen, became national CSR Manager of the Year in 2023 and won the prestigious ABN AMRO Duurzame 50 2024 Award «for his innovative approach to policymaking and design that paves the way for a sustainable future». Our staff's excellence in research is also recognised by numerous awards for best paper, among others: Best Paper 2022 in the *Building & Environment* journal (Chinazzo et al., 2022), Outstanding Paper 2022 Award in the *Materials and Structures* journal (Lubelli et al., 2022), and Best Paper at the International Building Physics Conference 2024 (Kim et al., 2025).

Another valuable mark of recognition is the establishment of **visiting research positions**, for external people who contribute to our research and academic discussion, and for our staff who spend time at international institutions and come back with new energy and ideas. This cross-pollination is essential for a dynamic environment that does not solely rely on new hires to bring in fresh perspectives. Such mobility programmes are typically funded by external sources, yet another testament to our outstanding reputation. Our assistant and associate professors visited prestigious institutions such as MIT, ETH, the Getty Conservation Institute, TU Munich, Sapienza University of Rome, Politecnico di Milano and University of California Berkeley. Besides hosting numerous PhD candidates from all over the world, we hosted Carlo Ratti and Gert-Jan Rozemeijer within the *Jaap Oosterhoff Visiting Professorship Programme*, a programme supported by the company Oosterhoff and still ongoing, with more internationally leading experts coming to our Department in the future.

FIG. 2.8 Mirage Sculpture realised in the Apple Park, CA, USA

FIG. 2.9 ENSNARE demonstrator building in Tartu, EE

2.6.2

Societal relevance

Industrial recognition, collaboration and guidance

Our close relationship with industrial partners gives us a strategic advantage for application and dissemination activities beyond the academic world. Our **prototypes** are often showcased at industrial fairs and exhibitions, such as GlassTec (Concepts for the Circular Economy, Interactive Glass, Free Form Façade). We develop research lines that are cutting edge and beneficial to the industry, and we test our innovations in real settings (e.g., the building control systems within the SmartEEstory and Acapulco projects), with working prototypes (e.g., the bio-based cladding in the FoWaBa-Bio project) and even as **fully constructed buildings** (Mirage Sculpture and ENSNARE demonstrator building shown in Fig. 2.8 and 2.9). In addition, we are often invited to provide expert advice and opinion to private and public entities, for example on the conservation of several monuments (e.g., Westertoren and De Waag) commissioned by the Municipality of Amsterdam and in international cases of forensic engineering in construction materials and façade technologies.

We shape **professional policies and guidelines** through our roles in committees and our expert scientific advice. Many of our staff members are active in national (NEN) and international (IEA, CEN, ISO, IStructE, REHVA, CIBSE) committees working on the implementation of engineering innovation and best practice design for industry. As part of our involvement in international committees and project consortia, we regularly publish reports and white papers that summarise joint research efforts towards a specific, tangible goal with practical implications, such as the IEA Task 75 Final Report «Business Models for cost-effective building renovation at district level combining energy efficiency & renewables» or the SHIFFT Project (Interreg) final report «How to accelerate the heat transition: a guide for local government and actors: Module 4 – Technology choices, data, and mapping for sustainable heating». These documents provide an essential link between research, industry and society, as they are typically open access documents with easier, more accessible language than scientific papers.

FIG. 2.10 VR setup in action for the HANDZONe project (photo by Serdar Aşut)

FIG. 2.11 Poster of the Immeasurably Important exhibition

Two examples of how our educational activities creates opportunities for research in digital technologies

Our peer-reviewed scientific publications are cited within these reports, guaranteeing the rigour and quality of the underlying research. We also guide entire building sectors and governmental policies by setting roadmaps and ambitious targets for a better industry and society, such as the [CIBSE TM68](#) on Monitoring Indoor Environmental Quality, the roadmap towards [circular building installations \(Initiatieven Overzicht Circulaire Klimaatinstallaties\)](#), or the [ISO 19152-1:2024](#) standard on standardisation in the land administration/georegulation domain.

Synergies with education

Our research is closely aligned with our education, fuelled by a constant dialogue and exchange between the two. We are largely associated with the Building Technology master track within the AUBS MSc programme, but most of our permanent research staff is also active in the BSc programme, in graduation studios and in elective courses open to other master tracks.

FIG. 2.12 Design prototypes exhibited at De Gevel tradeshow (photo by Marcel Bilow)

FIG. 2.13 Pavilion for young refugees realised together with COA & ONE (photo by ONE)

MSc-related activities gave us plenty of opportunity to test, inform and develop our research in collaboration with our most capable and motivated students. For example, the HANDZONE project created a digital twin of our robotic lab for educational activities (see Fig. 2.10), supported by the SURF Open and Online Education Incentive Scheme, while informing our research on robotics for additive manufacturing and resulting in a conference publication (Aşut, 2024). In 2025, the launch of a new series of additional elective courses (so-called Q5 courses) available to students from the entire University gave us additional opportunities to plan cross-pollination between research and education; the *Creative Robotics in Spatial Design* course brought a step further the achievements from the HANDZONE project, the *Future Materials* course accompanied the development of the Material Movement, and the *Architectural Lighting Design* course facilitated applications and network creation for our research on lighting. Research outcomes are further embedded in and supported by our education through relevant MSc graduation topics, as evident by the joint scientific publications with MSc graduate students. A recent MSc graduation work resulted in both a journal publication (Alsaggaf et al., 2025) and a public exhibition on dementia-inclusive building design tools, titled Immeasurably Important: Artificial intelligence and the soft values of Architecture, in collaboration with architecture firm TANGRAM (see Fig. 2.11). The research topic subsequently evolved into a PhD position within AE+T, while the same professional network contributed to securing the ClickNL-funded PLAIA project. BuckyLab and Circularity Technoledge student work was featured in Future Facades International expo and De Gevel international tradeshow 2022 (see Fig. 2.12), and a real-scale prototype, inspired by a student team's design in Technoledge Glass Structures, was exhibited at the GlassTec 2024 fair. In addition, in 2024, our students were part of a project that brought together COA (the Dutch Central Agency for the Reception of Asylum Seekers), ONE (Office for the New Earth), and TU Delft and that resulted in an inspiring pavilion for young refugees (see Fig. 2.13).

A special synergy between research, education and collaboration with market parties concerns the participation of a student team in the 2022 **Solar Decathlon Europe** competition, which built upon our experience with two other very successful Solar Decathlon participations. These teams predominantly consisted of students from AE+T master programmes and were supervised and guided by AE+T and MBE (research) staff. They had to collaborate closely with market companies. Many new concepts and techniques came forth from these prize-winning projects, and they yielded a lot of public attention.

Feeding our research into educational platforms gives us additional access to diverse audiences and increased visibility. Besides the multiplier effect already enabled by our local teaching activities, we reach intersectoral and international audiences through our **online platforms**, such as [Digipedia](#) for our digital expertise, the [Circular Design Atlas](#) for our expertise on circular materials, the [Open GLASSroom](#) portal for our expertise on glass design and engineering, and the [ShakeUp](#) knowledge exchange platform on building resilience to earthquake and climate change. Our MOOCs serve the same purpose and continue to be a strong asset of our department; among the most recent ones, we launched the OpenFace micro-master (funded by Erasmus+), the [Circular Economy for a Sustainable Built Environment](#) MOOC, and the [Buildings as Sustainable Energy Systems](#) MOOC. Of note, our existing façade-related MOOCs received the TU Delft Open Education Ambassador Award. Last but not least, courses within our BSc curriculum (Archineering minor) resulted in prototypes and public exhibitions at the Week of Circular Economy 2024 ([Capable Bridge](#)) and at the Dutch Design Week 2025 ([Touching Cellulose](#)), showcasing the results of our research directly to public events and audiences.

Public policies and public engagement

The impact of our work becomes tangible when it reaches **public policies** that improve citizens' lives. To cite one example above all, much of the research that was done in reaction to the COVID-19 pandemic continued in the following years and strove to improve policies on prevention and preparedness for future pandemics. Additionally, through the MIST project, dedicated online resources were developed to sensitise the public to the need for adequate indoor ventilation.

Our commitment to sustainable buildings had a tangible impact on the policies of our own University campus with the appointment of Andy van den Dobbelen as Sustainability Coordinator (2021-2025), which resulted in the roadmap and the first fundamental steps towards a [carbon-neutral, circular, climate-adaptive and regenerative campus by 2030](#).

Our research and our prototypes were often featured in **public exhibitions** that bring science closer to the public. In addition to students' projects already mentioned in the previous section, our research on human-façade interaction featured in the Delft Highlight Festival and several Delft Science Days. We were present at the Venice Biennale 2025 with the Circular Souvenirs piece, in collaboration with La-Di-Da Architects, and as contributors to the Water-Filled-Glass installation. On top of these participations, we took an active role in organising outreach events with the rest of the Faculty, for example by opening the Faculty building and organising activities for the Science Day 2025, by co-organising the CBE Hub Public Debates and the Resilient Neighbourhoods BK Festival in 2025. In addition, the Department hosts blogs (e.g., [Facadeworld](#), [AE+T Blog](#)) to disseminate innovation in the field to a general audience.

FIG. 2.14 Stills from the Clean Air Matters video

FIG. 2.15 Group photo during the shooting of the Klaas Kan Alles TV episode

FIG. 2.16 Students involved in the construction of the Capable Bridge, exhibited at the Week of Circular Economy 2024

National **media channels** showcased our research by featuring cast glass research in an episode of the TV programme *Klaas Kan Alles*, dedicated to popularising science and technology with families and children, by featuring our expertise in sustainable buildings and constructions in an episode of *Wat Houdt Ons Tegen*, a programme about the obstacles towards a sustainable and fair society, and by featuring our research on circular construction and bio-based façade cladding in *Het Klokhuis*, an educational children's programme. Our research is also appearing in podcasts (e.g., on heritage and citizen engagement *Future Making in the Anthropocene*, on summer overheating in *The Daily Move*) and news outlets (e.g., on the disadvantages and unintended consequences of using air conditioning in *AD*, on summer overheating in *NOS* and *Volkskrant*).

2.7

Strategy for the Next Assessment Period and Beyond

AE+T conducted a thorough internal review to prepare for the next assessment cycle. Its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats were identified and its mission was revised. The principal strengths identified include a strong international reputation, interdisciplinary expertise, close integration of research and education, and an extensive collaboration network; the achievements outlined above provide further evidence of these strengths. However, a number of weaknesses and external pressures persist and must be addressed, namely: structural funding constraints, heavy workloads, limited seed funding, restrictions on PhD recruitment, and the national hiring freeze. Consequently, our future strategy will focus on strengthening collaborative culture, improving governance and transparency, enhancing support for funding acquisition, advancing open science practices, and increasing visibility and impact across the full research lifecycle.

SWOT Analysis

The SWOT analysis was informed through a series of department-wide sessions to gather opinions under three main pillars: research quality; societal relevance; and viability of the AE+T Department. The sessions were well attended and enabled us to collect views from most of our academic staff. These activities also coincided with additional sessions organised by the new head of Department to align the department's vision and strategy across all sections and roles. The principal findings are as follows:

STRENGTHS

- High reputation of TU Delft and AE+T, attracts top international talents;
- Extensive external collaboration network including strong ties with industry;
- Strong links between research and education that guarantee impact of our core research topics;
- Large bandwidth of expertise spanning across design, technology/engineering and science;
- Increased diversity and broadened academic and scientific expertise via the Sector Plan positions;
- Staff's interdisciplinary backgrounds enable deep expertise across multiple high-impact fields;
- Ability to attract both fundamental and applied funding from national, international, and industry sources;
- Improved interactions of academic staff via weekly department-wide lectures (AE+T Bites).

WEAKNESSES

- Predominance of project-funded PhD hiring and pressure to frame research in fundable narratives restricts academic freedom, research diversity, and innovation;
- Concerns about social safety and persistent internal hierarchies limit ownership of achievements (e.g., right of *ius promovendi* not granted to assistant professors);
- Insufficient transparency in the decision-making process for research resource allocation and workload distribution;
- High teaching workload, complex research administration and limited acquisition support reduce research capacity;
- Limited coordinated external visibility of departmental research, and little support for visibility of early career researchers;
- Limited tailored support and training for diverse career paths;
- Limited budget for structural, long-term investments (e.g., subscriptions for advanced software licences, technicians for laboratories).

OPPORTUNITIES

- Strong alignment of departmental research with current funding calls (fundamental research), industry needs (applied research) and societal priorities (impact);

- Potential to tap into new national and international funding streams dedicated to strategic autonomy and resilience – risk of creating unequal opportunities for diverse staff positions, nationalities and ethical stands;
- Significant support of open science policy at University level, still largely untapped.

THREATS

- Hiring freeze (until 2030) reduces capacity and risks loss of critical expertise;
- Unclear role boundaries across academic ranks, combined with inconsistent promotion criteria across TU Delft;
- Budget cuts lead to heavy workload, prioritise teaching and erode research capacity;
- Weak academic culture (at international level) of recognising collective contributions results in strong individuals in a fragmented research community;
- Concerns between open-science expectations and expanding use of AI tools;
- Increased scrutiny on knowledge security and limitations to international collaborations and mobility, partially due to current geopolitical situation;
- Insufficient structural support and maintenance funding threaten viability of labs;
- Rising competition in funding acquisition (e.g., Horizon Europe) strains success rates.

2.7.2

Mission

At AE+T, we focus on the design and technologies that make buildings function: structure, envelope and environmental systems. Traditionally, this has required large quantities of materials and energy, with significant impacts on human well-being and the environment. The built environment contributes substantially to major socio-environmental challenges, including the climate crisis, resource scarcity and the vulnerability of buildings. AE+T is positioned at the interface of engineering sciences and architecture, enabling us to develop and advance strategies and technologies that address pressing societal needs by building on recent developments in the fundamental sciences. In doing so, we make notable contributions to both the fundamental sciences and real-world applications.

The department's mission during 2022–2025 focused on advancing architectural engineering technologies that enable a better-performing built environment within planetary boundaries. Research activities were organised into four themes: sustainable built environment, circular built environment, healthy and comfortable built environment, and digitally enhanced built environment. [Building on internal reflection and external feedback, AE+T has begun consolidating its profile around three overarching ambitions: **resource efficient**, **resilient**, and **regenerative** built environments. AE+T works towards these ambitious goals by developing and integrating innovations in engineering and technology through the lenses of **materials**, **energy** and **people**.] These ambitions are tested for the first time in this document and within this research assessment to frame our past achievements as coherent case studies (in Paragraph B.2). We are open to feedback on their effectiveness as the conceptual basis for our future strategic orientation.

FIG. 2.17 AE+T Vision

The AE+T vision for a **resource-efficient, circular built environment** aims to establish robust design approaches and manufacturing technologies that support the closing, slowing, and narrowing of material loops. It promotes systems thinking within planetary boundaries, addressing material use, energy consumption, and life-cycle impacts.

The AE+T vision for a **resilient built environment** aims to enhance its capacity to withstand, adapt to, and recover from shocks while safeguarding the health, safety, and wellbeing of their occupants. It considers equally *green infrastructures* that support ecological performance, climate adaptation, and healthy living environments; *adaptable infrastructures* that enable spatial, functional, and technological flexibility over time; and *equitable and inclusive infrastructures* that ensure fair access, social cohesion, and protection for vulnerable communities.

The AE+T vision for a **regenerative built environment** aims to deliver a net-positive impact on people and planet by restoring and enhancing the social-ecological systems in which buildings are embedded. It builds on the historical, cultural, and ecological context of existing structures to enhance biodiversity and improve human health and well-being.

2.7.3

AE+T Research objectives

Our future strategy tackles the research process at each of its 'lifecycle' steps, starting from acquisition to the management of research projects, to the dissemination of their

results and to the stimulation of real impact on society. The Department collectively identified areas of improvement and has recently launched dedicated working groups (so-called **Futures Teams**) to tackle them. These teams are cross-sectional through sections and career stages and will advise the Department management on issues related to: visibility and outreach; research vision and strategy; future-fit education; attracting and developing talent; laboratories; and governance, roles and communication. The advice generated within these teams and related discussion platforms will inform several aspects related to our research activities at various steps of our projects' lifecycle. Here we list the objectives we set for ourselves in the coming years, which are operational objectives meant to enable our research mission.

Concept development and positioning

We will dedicate more time and attention to academic discussions on our positioning and on our strategy for funding acquisition. This will require the organisation and planning of more **opportunities for brainstorming and coordination** between sections and staff members. Going forward, we want to be more conscious of our strengths and their deployment.

For each of our six research units, we will identify cutting-edge research areas that we can successfully lead, we will define the resources necessary to accomplish either incremental or disruptive innovation, and we will draft a plan to obtain such resources from internal or external routes. This will require a strategic use of all our existing internal assets and a collaborative mindset that prioritises the success of the Department as a whole.

Partnership building and funding acquisition

The rising competition for national and international research funding is a huge threat, which risks seeing even more time invested collectively in unsuccessful applications. We aim to **diversify our target funding sources**, including a mix of public and private resources, and strategically combine networks and skills already present in the Department to bring these various resources together. This will require a collective and cohesive effort from sections to share ideas and contacts. Of note, one experienced member of the Department is seconding part-time to the TU Delft central Impact and Innovation team to enhance the funding linkages between department, Faculty and TU Delft. His role will be to help colleagues develop materials and circular EU funding opportunities.

Our academic profile will largely remain the same as the hiring freeze will not allow the opening of new permanent positions. However, our portfolio has significantly expanded in the 2022-2025 period, and we can tap into new networks and expertise that new hires brought with them. At the same time, the **wealth of expertise** — both topical and strategic — that our professors have will also be invaluable to guide new staff towards the most promising funding routes. Strategic guidance is key at this time of high workloads, to make sure that efforts lead to sustained improvement and eventual rewards. Similarly, strategy and guidance will be at the core of our future applications for personal grants, limiting the mismatch between personal portfolios and expectations on personal excellence by reviewing panels.

We will continue seeking to fund new **PhD positions**, which are the lifeblood of our research, as we still have sufficient capacity to host and guide them. The limit on self-funded and scholarship positions is a challenge that we will face in the coming years. Potential co-financing strategies will be explored for situations in which existing funding covers most but not all of the required amount for a four-year PhD position. This includes the application to EU schemes that cover only 3-year programmes (e.g., MSCA DN schemes). We will continue to foster our close relationship with industry and create opportunities for co-creation and co-funding of research ideas.

Project set-up, research execution and project management

We will strive to **streamline managing and financial processes** behind running research projects by clarifying responsibilities and offering appropriate training to the key people involved in each project. Training on financial and knowledge security is of particular importance given the related challenges at national level. Taking up roles as project coordinators should be carefully evaluated in each situation, making a well-informed choice between using internal or external resources to fill such positions.

We invest in coordinating more effectively the resources that can be shared across the Faculty or even across the University, such as the BK Labs and the Faculty's overall Digital Strategy. By **leveraging each department's strengths** and by sharing skills and knowledge, we can optimise and magnify our individual contributions.

At these times of financial and social difficulties, it is essential that we promote a **collaborative and respectful academic culture**, where people listen to others and feel heard. We will continue to create opportunities to exchange ideas and come together as a department.

Communication, dissemination, impact and exploitation

The **dissemination** of our research findings is key to positioning us at the forefront of our field. We will continue to target traditional scientific output (journal and conference papers, books) and outlets aimed at the industrial sector (professional magazines, industry fairs). In parallel, we want to sharpen our digital presence and our contribution to broader open science platforms, such as open repositories and public databases. We will also continue to use MOOCs and other forms of open education (e.g., open platforms such as DigiPedia) as a strategy to disseminate our research for educational and training purposes.

Besides focusing on research content, we want to make our research more visible and accessible to non-specialists (i.e., broader stakeholders, the general public, the next generation, etc.) in a catchy and attractive way. We have talented and creative individuals in the Department who can help increase the visibility of flagship projects and department-wide initiatives on our website and other digital channels. This will contribute to the wider **communication** of research with which we identify and that we can use to promote our academic profile even further. We also plan to increase our involvement in **outreach** activities that bring us closer to the broader society and showcase our research in an accessible and engaging way. A committee dedicated to research dissemination to general audiences has been recently formed at Faculty level, and we have a leading role in it.

The strong engagement and the time pressure that **educational activities** impose on staff members can be used synergistically for research activities too. We will continue to implement our research findings into our teaching, and at the same time we can use our teaching to inform or enable research activities. This two-way stream is especially effective when combined with our laboratories and experimental facilities, which provide students with hands-on, experiential learning and provide us with a chance to test innovation. The high quality of our graduation students from the Building Technology MSc track is already resulting in scientific publications and public exhibitions. We plan to showcase graduation works to even more stakeholders, especially from industry, to increase our network and inspire future collaborations.

We will continue to **engage with industrial stakeholders** in existing and new networks. Our proven experience with applied research is appreciated at national and international levels, and places us in an excellent position to inspire and guide industry towards new trends and innovations.

2.7.4

Summary of objectives

Concept Development and Positioning

- Create regular cross section discussions and structured brainstorming sessions to sharpen AE+T's strategic positioning, funding focus, and shared understanding of departmental strengths;
- For each research unit, identify leading research areas and develop resource plans—linking internal assets and external funding routes—to support both incremental and disruptive innovation;
- Strengthen collaborative strategic planning by coordinating efforts across units and aligning resource deployment with the department's long term mission.

Partnership Building and Funding Acquisition

- Diversify and strategically target funding sources—public, private, and industry—by leveraging shared networks, collective acquisition efforts, and coordinated section level input;
- Provide structured strategic guidance to staff (especially early career researchers) to improve the relevance, competitiveness, and alignment of both collaborative and personal grant applications;
- Secure new PhD positions by exploring co financing models, EU three year schemes, and industry co funding, ensuring continued capacity for high quality doctoral research.

Project Set Up, Research Execution and Management

- Improve project management by clarifying responsibilities, simplifying administrative processes, and providing targeted training in finance, coordination, and knowledge security;
- Make informed decisions about assuming project coordinator roles, balancing internal capacity with the option of external coordination support;
- Enhance cross-Faculty and cross-University coordination by pooling shared resources (e.g. BK Labs, digital platforms) and reinforcing a respectful, collaborative academic culture.

Communication, dissemination, impact and exploitation

- Maintain strong academic and industry-facing dissemination while expanding contributions to open-science platforms, repositories, MOOCs, and other accessible knowledge channels;
- Increase visibility of flagship projects and departmental strengths through coordinated digital communication, improved online presence, and attractive content for non-specialist audiences;
- Strengthen the research–education–industry triangle by embedding research in teaching, using student work as an innovation driver, and showcasing graduation output to broaden networks and spark collaborations.

Case Studies AE+T

Each accomplishment presented in Paragraph [2.6] is part of a larger narrative in which scientific research, industry collaboration, education, and societal impact interweave in a strong and mutually reinforcing synergy. Our case studies are formed by exemplary projects that show how all these components were pursued to answer three overarching goals: a resource-efficient built environment, a resilient built environment and a regenerative built environment. These goals map our new research mission and vision as presented in [Paragraph 2.7]. We are using these case studies to cluster our work and to reshape our mission around them, knowing that in reality there is no such clear cut, and some projects respond to multiple goals at the same time.

B.2.1

Resource-efficient built environment

AE+T's work towards a **resource efficient** built environment is grounded in the belief that the construction sector must urgently reduce its material, energy and environmental footprint. Over the past assessment period, the Department has advanced this agenda through a combination of **material innovation, systems thinking, applied experimentation and cross-sector collaboration**. We forged new networks, such as the Material Movement, and leveraged existing networks, such as the CBE Hub, the Urban Energy Institute and the European Façade Network, to engage multi-disciplinary and intersectoral actors in our planning. Together, these efforts demonstrate how AE+T research both reshapes foundational knowledge and delivers realworld impact. A core component of this agenda is the development of **novel materials and building products derived from waste streams and renewable resources**. Our research groups have delivered internationally recognised breakthroughs in glass recycling (UPCAST Glass), enabling the upcycling of waste glass into structurally sound castglass components; biobased façade systems (FoWaBaBio), which transform organic residues into functional cladding; and innovative timber alternatives rooted in regenerative forestry concepts (WoodStock). Using novel or waste materials brings additional **challenges in their manufacturing and assembly strategies**, which we addressed with research on reversible joining technologies (ReSolved), additive manufacturing (Wood Without Trees) and façade design (AEGIR). These projects not only advance scientific understanding but also showcase the feasibility of circular manufacturing pathways when tested through fullscale prototypes, demonstrators and industrial partnerships.

FIG. 2.18 The FoWaBa-Bio prototypes use food-waste streams combined with biopolymer resin to contribute to circular and regenerative design(image by Marcel Bilow)

FIG. 2.19 The WaterWarmth project aims to provide building heating from water bodies

FIG. 2.20 ... while ensuring the preservation of ecosystems (photos by Robèrt Kroonen)

At building and district scale, AE+T researchers address **operational resource efficiency** through integrated system strategies. Projects such as IEBB, WaterWarmth and Acapulco explore how heating, cooling and ventilation systems can operate synergistically, reducing energy demand and improving thermal performance in both new and existing buildings. Complementary research on heritage buildings investigates how historic masonry facades can be upgraded while safeguarding cultural value. These studies are supported by the **development of decision support tools** (e.g. ENSNARE, ReClaimed, DECIST, IEBB tools) that translate complex performance data into actionable insights for designers, policymakers and building owners.

To ensure wide societal uptake of resource efficient solutions, AE+T invests heavily in **open knowledge platforms and dissemination**. The Circular Design Atlas, Open GLASSroom, OpenFace, and the FaçadeWorld blog serve as accessible repositories of design precedents, engineering guidance and technical data, supporting practitioners and educators worldwide. These efforts are reinforced by national and international **teaching collaborations**, including the Zuyd 3C programme and the Eurodelta alliance, which extend AE+T's circularity expertise to broader professional and academic communities, a much-needed development to ensure broader societal uptake of systemic shifts.

The department's influence also extends to **industry practice and public policy**. AE+T researchers contribute to national roadmaps such as the Circular Building Installations agenda and shape architectural discourse through the work of thoughtleading professors. High visibility outputs — including the Mirage Sculpture, Future Facades exhibitions and contributions to the Venice Biennale — bring resource efficient innovation into the public realm, **building societal awareness and acceptance**.

AE+T embeds its resource efficiency agenda deeply into **education**, ensuring continuity through future generations of architects and engineers. Research directly informs BSc and MSc courses, minors and graduation studios, while student projects often mature into prototypes showcased at international fairs such as GlassTec and Future Facade.

B.2.2

Resilient built environment

The concept of **resilience** – the capacity of buildings and urban systems to withstand, adapt to and recover from environmental, climatic and operational disruptions – has become central to AE+T's strategic development. Recognising the increasing severity of climate-related shocks, energy system stresses and environmental health risks, the Department has built a diverse portfolio of research that addresses resilience from material to district scale.

AE+T's resilience research begins with **collaboration across faculties and disciplines**. Through partnerships with the Climate Action Programme, ThermoNED and the Resilient Neighbourhoods initiative, AE+T contributes technological and design expertise to integrated resilience strategies. These collaborations ensure that architectural engineering insights – ranging from façade behaviour to microclimatic design – inform wider policy debates and interdisciplinary scientific work.

AE+T develops of **new evidence and technologies for climate-adaptive operation**. The RECLIMATE project investigates how buildings can maintain comfort under rising temperatures, providing data that supports other projects on physiological acclimation and adaptive thermal thresholds (ReAct). Complementary systems-oriented research in Sunrise IR and HeatFace explores alternatives to centralised heating systems, shifting towards decentralised, lowcarbon and comfortenhancing approaches.

As buildings become increasingly dependent on allelectric systems, AE+T researchers evaluate critical risks related to **grid congestion and system failure**. Projects such as DATALess and Brains4Buildings provide digital solutions for flexible energy demand, predictive control and earlyfault detection. These innovations strengthen building resilience by reducing vulnerability to overloads, outages and operational inefficiencies.

Climate-related hazards also require **advanced modelling and decision support tools**. Through POINTTWINs and MULTICARE, AE+T has developed digital analysis methods that simulate wind conditions, energy flows and multicriteria resilience metrics at building and neighbourhood scale. These tools support policymakers, engineers and designers in making informed decisions about adaptation strategies.

AE+T's resilience agenda also extends to **heritage and cultural infrastructure**. The ReVerDi project ('Real Versus Digital: Sustainability optimization for cultural heritage preservation in national libraries'), for example, addresses the future of libraries as both cultural anchors and resilient community spaces, ensuring their continued relevance under shifting climatic and societal conditions.

FIG. 2.21 Design Studio exhibition organised in collaboration with the ReVerDi project

Knowledge dissemination is amplified through international networks such as ShakeUp, reinforcing **global exchange on resilience related design and engineering**. Education plays an essential role as well: resilience research directly informs courses such as MEGA, CORE and EXTREME, equipping students with hands-on methodologies for climate-adaptive design.

Together, these efforts demonstrate AE+T's comprehensive and multiscale approach to resilience — one that integrates empirical evidence, technological innovation, digital decision-making and societal engagement.

B. 2. 3

Regenerative built environment

AE+T's ambition for a **regenerative built environment** extends beyond reducing harm: it seeks to create buildings and urban systems that actively restore ecological and social conditions. This case study illustrates how the department's research contributes to positive environmental impact, cultural stewardship and human wellbeing.

A central theme in this work is the transformation of crises into opportunities for progress. Building on research initiated during the COVID-19 pandemic, AE+T continues to develop **health-centred approaches** to indoor environments. Projects such as MIST translate scientific evidence on airborne transmission and ventilation into accessible resources for schools and public institutions, empowering citizens and facility managers to maintain healthier indoor environments.

FIG. 2.22 A respiring manikin setup to simulate face-to-face conversations in an indoor setting (photo by Arghyanir Giri)

AE+T also investigates **living and bio-fabricated materials** that create regenerative ecological cycles. The MASS project explores mycelium-based and other organic materials as structural or insulating elements, contributing to carbonnegative construction strategies.

Heritagelated research provides another pathway to regeneration. Through initiatives such as Sticking Stones, AE+T studies traditional construction methods not only to preserve monument quality but also to inspire more **respectful and adaptive approaches to contemporary retrofitting**. SmartEEstory complements this approach by exploring how historic buildings can be upgraded to **improve comfort and user experience** without eroding cultural value. AE+T researchers also engage with civic partners on the **regeneration of critical infrastructures**, including efforts to stabilise and revitalise Delft's historic quay walls through multidisciplinary investigation.

Regeneration is pursued at urban scale as well, for example in Sky High, which examines ways of **embedding food production within buildings** and city systems. Digital design tools such as PLAIA and dementiasensitive spatial simulations demonstrate how buildings can **support psychological wellbeing and social inclusion**, linking technological development to humancentred outcomes.

FIG. 2.23 Investigation of traditional wood tar as stone adhesive in the Sticking Stones project

Much of this work connects directly to **policy and institutional transformation**. As Sustainability Coordinator of TU Delft, an AE+T full professor authored the roadmap towards a carbonneutral, circular, climateadaptive and regenerative campus by 2030, ensuring that AE+T's regenerative principles influence decisions at institutional level.

Public engagement is a further driver of regenerative impact. AE+T's work has been showcased at the Venice Biennale, Delft Science Days, architecture festivals and citizen-science partnerships. Such activities build awareness of regenerative design and invite communities to participate in shaping their built environment.

Through these diverse contributions – spanning health, ecology, heritage, digital tools and public policy – AE+T demonstrates how architectural engineering can move beyond sustainability towards truly regenerative design.

References

- Alsaggaf, F., Eijkelenboom, A., Lugten, M., & Turrin, M. (2025). A machine learning framework for early-stage dementia-friendly architectural design evaluation using visual access metrics. *Architectural Intelligence*, 4(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44223-025-00087-2>
- Aşut, S. (2024). Developing a Hybrid Learning Environment for Architectural Robotics. 695–704. <https://doi.org/10.52842/conf.ecaade.2024.2.695>
- Bluyssen, P. M. (2025). The need to go beyond the comfort-based dose-related indicators in our IEQ-guidelines. *Building and Environment*, 283, 113349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2025.113349>
- Bristogianni, T., & Oikonomopoulou, F. (2023). Glass up-casting: A review on the current challenges in glass recycling and a novel approach for recycling “as-is” glass waste into volumetric glass components. *Glass Structures & Engineering*, 8(2), 255–302. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40940-022-00206-9>
- Chinazzo, G., Andersen, R. K., Azar, E., Barthelmes, V. M., Becchio, C., Belussi, L., Berger, C., Carlucci, S., Corgnati, S. P., Crosby, S., Danza, L., De Castro, L., Favero, M., Gauthier, S., Hellwig, R. T., Jin, Q., Kim, J., Sarey Khanie, M., Khovalyg, D., ... Wei, S. (2022). Quality criteria for multi-domain studies in the indoor environment: Critical review towards research guidelines and recommendations. *Building and Environment*, 226, 109719. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.109719>
- Kim, K., Bianchi, S., Konstantinou, T., Overend, M., Ciurlanti, J., & Luna-Navarro, A. (2025). Thermal Resilience to Extreme Heat: Preliminary Study on Thermal Fragility Curves. In U. Berardi (Ed.), *Multiphysics and Multiscale Building Physics* (Vol. 553, pp. 350–357). Springer Nature Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-8309-0_47
- Lazarus, J. V., Romero, D., Kopka, C. J., Karim, S. A., Abu-Raddad, L. J., Almeida, G., Baptista-Leite, R., Barocas, J. A., Barreto, M. L., Bar-Yam, Y., Bassat, Q., Batista, C., Bazilian, M., Chiou, S.-T., Del Rio, C., Dore, G. J., Gao, G. F., Gostin, L. O., Hellard, M., ... Øvrehus, A. (2022). A multinational Delphi consensus to end the COVID-19 public health threat. *Nature*, 611(7935), 332–345. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05398-2>
- Lubelli, B., Aguilar, A. M., Beck, K., De Kock, T., Desarnaud, J., Franzoni, E., Gulotta, D., Ioannou, I., Kamat, A., Menendez, B., Rørig-Dalgaard, I., & Sassoni, E. (2022). A new accelerated salt weathering test by RILEM TC 271-ASC: Preliminary round robin validation. *Materials and Structures*, 55(9), 238. <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-022-02067-8>
- Luna-Navarro, A., Brembilla, E., De La Barra, P., Moreau, L., & Overend, M. (2024). Luminance-based methodology for assessment of low level haze in glazing. *Glass Structures & Engineering*, 9(3–4), 671–683. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40940-024-00281-0>
- Meng, W., Kragt, A. J. J., Gao, Y., Brembilla, E., Hu, X., van der Burgt, J. S., Schenning, A. P. H. J., Klein, T., Zhou, G., van den Ham, E. R., Tan, L., Li, L., Wang, J., & Jiang, L. (2024). Scalable Photochromic Film for Solar Heat and Daylight Management. *Advanced Materials*, 36(5), 2304910. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202304910>
- Zingoni, A. (2025). *Engineering Materials, Structures, Systems and Methods for a More Sustainable Future* (1st edn). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003677895>

MBE redefines coherence in the built environment

Management in the Built Environment

Climate change, the energy transition, housing shortages and an ageing population require new perspectives on, and approaches to, the design, construction and management of the built environment. These intertwined developments cannot be addressed solely within existing systems. They require unconventional approaches, including reconsidering our interactions with existing systems and structures of the built environment.

MBE plays its part in this, motivated by societal values, through new collaborative models, and by drawing insights from the past. We know the built environment inside and out, recognising both its interconnectedness and unique features. We understand its constraints and know that solutions can only be achieved through collective efforts. Thus, we collaborate with governments, market stakeholders, residents, and users to explore what is required for this. Now, tomorrow and for the future. We develop new knowledge and educate students who will be capable of orchestrating this complex collaborative effort. This is how we bring ideas about the future built environment into reality. In navigating this challenging and intricate world, we are contributing to a safe, healthy space for everyone.

Summary

Over the past four years, Management in the Built Environment (MBE) has moved from a collection of strong individual research profiles towards a more coherent, recognisable, and strategically aligned research department. This midterm self-evaluation shows that MBE has largely addressed the key concerns raised in the 2022 assessment and has established a solid foundation for the next phase of development.

The most significant accomplishment has been the establishment of a shared research identity. Through a department-wide process, MBE articulated a mission that emphasises coherence in the built environment and positions management as a critical lens for understanding and shaping societal transitions. This mission now provides a stable reference point, which the department is already using to shape our research strategy, collaboration, and personnel decisions.

Research performance during this period demonstrates both depth and breadth. Among many highlights, MBE has consolidated international leadership in housing and urban development, produced influential work on health-supportive environments, and advanced innovative approaches to future value, climate adaptation, digitalisation, AI, and circularity. Across these domains, MBE's work is characterised by strong methodological rigour, integration across scales, and engaged scholarship with societal partners. This has resulted in policy influence, widely used tools, and long-term collaborations that extend beyond individual projects.

Internally, MBE has invested in the conditions that enable high-quality research. Improved PhD onboarding, research forums, and explicit attention to academic culture and social safety have strengthened the research environment. At the same time, the department has experimented with mission-aligned indicators that better capture research quality and societal impact than traditional metrics alone.

Looking ahead, MBE's strategy for the next six years is focused and realistic. The department aims to strengthen its theoretical core, institutionalise key collaborations, and find ways to take on further leadership within the faculty's strategic themes. External communication and visibility will become a higher priority, supported by a coherent narrative and alignment with open science principles. We will use our recently completed strategic personnel planning to ensure we safeguard our disciplinary expertise and supervision capacity under budgetary constraints, while keeping a perspective on new and emerging research frontiers.

In summary, MBE has used the past four years to build a cohesive foundation for long-term excellence. The emphasis now shifts from internal alignment to external leadership. In the years to come, we expect to see MBE further positioned and recognised as a trusted, visible, and intellectually grounded partner for addressing the most pressing challenges in the built environment.

FIG. 3.1 MBE as illustrated during the graffiti workshop of the 2025 departmental outing

3.2

Introduction

Management in the Built Environment focuses on how the built environment is initiated, designed, realised, used, and redeveloped across multiple scales. We study how governing, organising, and managing shape buildings, portfolios, and urban areas, and how these practices enable adaptation, transformation, and long-term transitions. Our work addresses major societal challenges, aligned with the themes of the faculty, including sustainable urbanisation, healthy cities, future values including equity and justice, digitalisation, and circularity.

Our research programme develops theoretical perspectives and translates them into actionable methods, strategies, and policies. We design and test interventions that support future value creation in the built environment by linking technical, organisational, and institutional change. Central to our approach is designing for people, which means we embed values, interactions, and institutions into management practices. Our research can then inform and guide decision-making over the full lifecycle of the built environment.

Our research activities span across phases (e.g., from design and construction to use and redevelopment) and across interconnected scales (e.g., from building to portfolio to area). We work in close engagement with societal stakeholders and users, because we recognise that meaningful change requires coordination across disciplines, organisations, and governance levels. This integrated approach is structured across three sections: Design and Construction Management, Real Estate Management, and Urban Development Management.

FIG. 3.2 Thematic Overview of MBE

3.2.1

The Three Sections of MBE

The section **Design and Construction Management (DCM)** focuses on new ways of reconfiguring work processes in designing, constructing and renovating the built environment to meet the goals of creating a climate-neutral circular economy that emphasises greater responsiveness, reliability, quality and resource efficiency in the through-life delivery of built environment projects. These new ways of working also call for business model innovation that can facilitate more integrative methods of connecting people and technologies to reduce transaction costs and drive better built environment and societal outcomes. DCM covers six domains: Design and Construction Management, Construction Management and Entrepreneurship, Building Law, Housing Quality and Process Innovation, Public Commissioning, and Construction Cultures. The DCM section's ambition to address social, environmental and technological change in producing future built environments is realised by engaging with four challenging aspects; these include examining questions of (1) technological change and its impacts on ways of designing, constructing and managing built assets; (2) institutions, policies, regulations and tools and their impact on institutional change; (3) how people and organisations learn in/when navigating through change, and (4) configurations of data and (digital) systems in producing the built environment.

FIG. 3.3 Organization of the Professorships at MBE

The section **Real Estate Management** (REM) focuses on the performance of the built environment. The performance is considered in terms of values delivered to the users of real estate. The values include spatial, functional and technical quality, cost effectiveness and sustainability. To assess the performance, it is necessary to incorporate the interests, requirements and constraints of the various users, uses and stakeholders in all phases of the lifecycle (from initiation to use, re-use and disposal) and at different scale levels (buildings, real estate portfolios and markets). Real Estate Management is interdisciplinary in its scope, and combines scientific fields of policy, geography and planning sciences, organisational studies, economics, law, mathematics and sociology with design and engineering – mainly architecture, urbanism and building technology. The REM section covers four domains: Real Estate Management, Public Real Estate, Housing Management and Housing Systems. Each domain focuses on aspects of Real Estate Management. The section regularly cooperates with practitioners such as the Dutch Police, the Transitieteam Circulaire Bouweconomie, and Statistics Netherlands (CBS), amongst others.

The section **Urban Development Management** (UDM) focuses on managing the decisions that help create urban places. The development and creation of urban places involve many stakeholders who operate in partly overlapping institutional settings. Understanding, redesigning and intervening in the interactions of the stakeholders and decisions taken in development processes is what drives the section. This includes attention to strategies developed, the instruments used, actions performed, policies shaped, spatial plans drawn, designs approved, stakeholders involved, governance arranged, contracts signed, networks forged, and all other elements of urban development that shape the quality of future urban areas. The UDM section covers four domains: Urban Development Management, Area Development, Governance of Land Development and Housing Institutions and Governance. The section cooperates with practitioners and has cooperations and partnerships with, amongst others, Stichting Kennis Gebiedsontwikkeling, Leiden-Delft-Erasmus centres, Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Studies and the Resilient Delta Initiative with Erasmus University and Erasmus Medical Centre.

FIG. 3.4 Departmental Governance of MBE, with roles current as of May 2026

3.2.2

Department Governance

The department chair represents MBE in the management team of A+BE faculty. Each of the three sections is led by a section leader. They are additionally supported by a section coordinator and section research coordinator.

MBE is governed by the Daily Board (DB). The DB is composed of the MBE department head (chair), the section leader and section coordinator for each of the three sections, the education manager, the master coordinator, the research leader and the department manager. The DB of MBE meets every three weeks.

The DB is responsible for the department's strategy and coordination. The DB focuses on decision-making that reflects our strategic aims and priorities. The DB considers questions such as: Who are we? What is our purpose? Where do we want to go next? How do we integrate our research into education and valorisation? To help guide this process, one of the main developments in the past years has been the creation

of the MBE mission statement (see next section). The DB also discusses the department's staffing needs and manages the departmental budget. Specific investments are also considered, most of which are related to HR, such as travel, conferences, and the appointment of guest researchers. Additionally, the DB is responsible for implementing TUD and faculty policies. Input and feedback on faculty-level decisions are discussed in the DB and conveyed to the faculty management team by our chair, Ellen van Bueren.

3.2.3

Research Support and Development

At MBE, research is fundamentally driven by PhD candidates and research staff, and research support is strategically organised around a clearly defined journey from onboarding to independent scholarship. PhD candidates enter the department through a structured onboarding process that clarifies expectations, supervision arrangements, training requirements, and available support. Early stages focus on building strong foundations in theory, research design, and methods, supported by the Graduate School and department-level initiatives such as research forums and cohort-based activities. As PhD researchers progress, supervision increasingly shifts towards intellectual independence, publication strategy, and positioning within international research debates. Postdoctoral researchers are supported as emerging research leaders, with explicit attention to developing independent research lines, proposal writing, supervision experience, and academic leadership. Across both groups, research training at MBE is understood not as a checklist of courses, but as a staged process of becoming a researcher capable of designing rigorous, societally relevant, and reflective research.

3.3

Mission and Strategic Aims of the Past Four Years

3.3.1

Mission of MBE

One of the key recommendations of the 2022 research assessment is that the department must articulate added value and research identity. In 2023 and 2024, MBE underwent a process to create a new mission statement (see case study #1). Since 2024, MBE has been operating under our new mission statement.

MBE redefines coherence in the built environment.

The built environment is the space where we find our sense of home, engage in work, and connect with each other. This space faces big challenges. Climate change, the energy transition, housing shortages and an ageing population require new perspectives on, and approaches to, the design, construction and management of the built environment.

These intertwined developments cannot be addressed solely within existing systems. They require a profound understanding of the built environment across various levels and scales, and insights into how they interact. They demand creative and innovative thinking and action. While the exact forms and functions of the future built environment are not yet certain, we must take the initial steps now to reimagine what they could entail.

This may require unconventional approaches, including reconsidering our interactions with existing systems and structures of the built environment. We play our part in this, motivated by societal values, through new collaborative models, and by drawing insights from the past. We know the built environment inside and out, recognising both its interconnectedness and unique features. We understand its constraints and know that solutions can only be achieved through collective efforts. Thus, we collaborate with governments, market stakeholders, residents, and users to explore what is required for this. Now, tomorrow and for the future. We develop new knowledge and educate students who will be capable of orchestrating this complex collaborative effort. This is how we bring ideas about the future built environment into reality. In navigating this challenging and intricate world, we are contributing to a safe, healthy space for everyone.

3.3.2

Strategic Aims and Indicators

In the 2022 assessment, MBE identified several strategic aims. However, with the creation of the new mission statement and the new research coordination team, we felt it was the right time to reformulate these aims. Therefore, in 2024 we developed eight categories to help us operationalise our mission statement and to act as categories to assess our research performance as a department. These are described below. They represent both our strategic priorities in research and what success looks like. The first three categories identify “what” we do. The fourth through eighth categories represent “how” we do it, looking outward and looking inward.

First, we see the context. We recognise the (often changing) context of the built environment, far deeper than what is observed at the surface level. When we see this context, we then assess with a critical lens/perspective, including inputs from the current state of theory and of practice. To see this context, we emphasise participation in strategic international research networks (e.g., European Network for Housing Research, Association of Researchers in Construction Management) and university partnerships (e.g., collaboration with University College London). We take up roles on editorial

What we do at MBE

1. See the context
2. Develop new knowledge
3. Make a difference in practice

How we do it – looking outward

4. Integrate across scales and disciplines
5. Engaged Scholarship
6. Uphold key values

How we do it – looking inward

7. Contribute to a positive academic culture
8. Create synergies between Research & Education

boards or as Editor-in-Chief of relevant journals in our field, or we lead the organisation of international research conferences. We act as lead editors of book publications, where we can provide a broad and holistic mapping of the field. Because we understand the present context and hold insights from the past, we can identify and articulate emerging transformations in the built environment before they become mainstream. This positions us at the forefront of the field, allows us to secure highly competitive personal (e.g., ERC, VIDI) research grants, and prepares our trained researchers to obtain competitive academic or industry career track positions.

Second, we **develop new knowledge**. This begins with the generation of new and relevant theory, often resulting in high-quality peer-reviewed journal publications. We encourage unconventional approaches, creative thinking and innovative actions that challenge existing paradigms found in research and practice. We do all of this with methodological rigour and with a focus on topics relevant to the strategic aims of the BK faculty: sustainable urbanisation, healthy cities, heritage with future value, climate adaptation and energy transition, digitalisation and AI, and circularity in the built environment. We do not measure success by the quantity of knowledge produced (e.g., by the number of publications) but by its quality and impact. While evidence of this can (carefully) come from citation frequency or best paper awards, we also look to tell the narratives of breakthrough research.

Third, we strive to **make a difference in practice**. This means that, drawing from our new knowledge, we design and implement change in today's practice in the built environment. We also reconsider our interactions with existing structures of the industry when required. Because our work is often situated in modes of societal change such as adaptation, transformation and transition, we translate our research findings into actionable policy insights. We put ourselves in the overall societal discourse through media appearances and publications in professional journals. We look for narratives that illustrate the uptake of our work in practice.

Fourth, we **integrate across scales and disciplines** as part of our fundamental approach. This means that we must understand the interplay and integration of people, information, and processes across multiple scales (e.g., buildings, portfolios and areas) in the built environment (see Fig. 3.2 for an example of the scales). We therefore conduct research that embraces the complexity found in the built environment, recognising its intertwined and interconnected nature. We seek to work across MBE sections, across BK departments, and across faculties at TU Delft, learning from novel theoretical and practice points of view found outside of MBE. We see evidence of this through our multi-stakeholder collaborations and coalition-building efforts that enable widespread integration among actors that do not normally work together. Overall, we build a strategic network of strong, long-lasting relationships across sectors, including industry, government, and civil society.

Fifth, we do the above through **engaged scholarship**. Engaged scholarship is an approach to research and education in which academic work is co-produced with societal actors and directed towards real-world challenges, while maintaining scientific rigour. We actively pursue transdisciplinary research that bridges academia and society, integrating knowledge from practice, policy, and diverse stakeholder communities throughout the research process. Our goal is mutual value creation rather than extractive knowledge production. This work is often time-intensive, requiring long-term

relationships and iterative feedback, and results in “slow science” as opposed to a high quantity of publications. In the MBE context, engaged scholarship includes co-designed research with public and private partners, co-creation workshops, living labs and pilot projects. We do not stop at the journal publication but seek to take the extra step to translate our research into policy advice, design frameworks, and governance models specific to the communities that helped us create the research. This engaged scholarship prepares our researchers to operate effectively at the interface of science, policy, and practice when they leave MBE.

Sixth, we strive to **define and uphold key values**. As stated in our mission statement, we contribute to a safe, healthy built environment for everyone. Our research is motivated by societal values, such as sustainability, aesthetics, and inclusion. We work towards best practices for research ethics, guided by principles of open data and open science.

Seventh, we contribute to a **positive academic culture**. We develop and encourage teamwork, work-life balance, service, career advancement/development, and leadership and mentorship. We seek to balance international relevance with our local embeddedness in the Dutch context. Through these aims, we seek to bring a reflexive, critical perspective on our own position as researchers. Case Study #2 explains how MBE refocused on social safety and PhD Researcher Development in the past years. Our ambition is to prioritise and build a culture of social safety for all team members.

Eighth, we create **synergies between research and education**. This means that we take intentional steps to develop connections between research and teaching, such as translating our research into teaching plans for students. We invest in the research process of our Master’s track, resulting in high-quality graduation theses sometimes worthy of wider publication. We also study and analyse our own teaching practices, then communicate these evidence-based best practices to others, such as through research publications about teaching and design. Overall, we seek to develop students strong in both theory and practice, who are themselves capable of integrating across scales, conducting engaged scholarship, and upholding values.

3.3.3

Summary of the 2022 Research Assessment

Reflecting on the 2022 assessment, the committee acknowledged the strong reputation and international visibility of individual scholars but concluded that the department’s collective research identity required clearer positioning. It stated that “the department needs to better articulate the added value of management research in its research mission statement” and urged MBE to “reflect and communicate more explicitly on its unique selling proposition”. The Executive Board reinforced this emphasis, noting that for MBE the focus lies in the articulation of its distinguishing profile. The central message was that quality and relevance are evident, but better collective framing and communication are necessary.

Beyond profile articulation, the committee called for stronger strategic steering. It recommended translating the department’s strategic goals into measurable indicators and encouraged a conversation about meaningful and relevant data to inform decisions and monitor progress. This reflected a broader concern with ensuring transparency, coherence, and accountability in research governance over the 2022–2027 period.

Finally, the committee addressed structural and cultural conditions for sustainable performance. It explicitly noted that “the workload of staff at all levels, from PhD to full professor, is a point of concern” and encouraged systematic monitoring and action. A summary of the 2022 MBE evaluation report can be found in Table 3.1 below, and the full report is available in the appendix.

TABLE 3.1

PROGRESS FROM THE 2022 MBE EVALUATION REPORT		
Year	Title	Theme
Mission & Unique Selling Point (#1)	Department must articulate added value and research identity	Research Coordination Team established (2022); MBE Mission statement developed (2023); Strategic Personnel Planning completed (2024).
Communication (#2)	Improve internal/external visibility	New MBE visual communication and branding complete (2025); Rollout of new external communication, including website and social media, planned for 2026 and 2027.
PhD Support (#3)	Improve supervision structure, onboarding, and methods training	New onboarding strategy for MBE PhDs developed (2023); Monthly MBE Research Forum initiated (2023); Specific MBE PhD coaching funded and initiated (2025).
Language & Dutch Context (#4)	Balance international staff with Dutch societal embedding	Recent examples of Dutch-speaking hires for permanent staff 10 staff (3 permanent, 7 postdoc/PhD) currently participating in Dutch courses; Main principles understood but extension to clear policy planned (2026-2027).
Knowledge Transfer (#5)	Need a coherent strategy and aftercare model	Priority was mission statement and identity, so less efforts were made in this area; Now groundwork is ready and this is a priority to create a formal strategy for 2026 and 2027.
Strategic Hiring (#6)	Use turnover to strengthen research profile	The use of the Strategic Personal Plan now central to hiring decisions; Today’s context is hiring freeze, but MBE is prepared for future should this change.
Indicators (#7)	Translate strategy into meaningful self-defined KPIs	Mission-aligned qualitative indicators have been developed (2024) and piloted in this midterm evaluation (2025). See Paragraph 3.5.
Workload (#8)	Monitor pressure and develop mitigation strategies	For proposals, establishment of MBE “one-pager” (2025); MBE Research Coordination Team meetings and BK faculty grant coordination tools act as coordination within MBE; For careers, R&D used to reduce the (felt) expectancy for writing grant applications or publishing more; Clarification that PhD does not require publications; Renewed point of emphasis in R&D on single, highly impactful outputs in the place of quantitative /summative evaluation metrics such as impact factor.

Strategy

Since 2022, MBE has concentrated on strengthening our core identity and building the structures that support a coherent research programme. During this time, we completed a department-wide mission process, established a more active research coordination team, created a visual identity, held strategic personnel planning sessions, considered how to support links to the Dutch context, and created structure to better support PhD researchers. These steps were our priority in the past four years, and now that they are established, they serve as the foundation for us to build upon for developing our knowledge transfer strategy in 2026 and 2027, as we transition from internal coherence to external visibility.

Case Study #1

How MBE worked to develop its mission statement and strategic future priorities.

The most significant step forward for MBE from 2022 until 2026 is the establishment and internal alignment of a **single, coherent identity** for the department (*Committee Critique #1*). To do this, we have identified a new MBE mission statement as described in section 3 above. Strategically, this was also a process for MBE to better understand how we fit together as a department, including our unique selling point for the research we do. In addition, we established the MBE research coordination team, by adding one coordinator responsible for each section.

Together with the departmental research coordinator, this team took the initiative to develop measurable indicators to operationalise this new mission statement (*Committee Critique #7*). These formed the basis for this midterm evaluation, which we feel provides our own self-developed criteria upon which we can evaluate ourselves.

We designed a new visual identity for MBE (*Committee Critique #2*). The visual identity was led by an external agency, and done in collaboration across the department, for example by sharing potential visual designs in the MBE hallway and allowing our community to vote on preferred designs.

From 2023 to 2025, we developed a Strategic Personnel Plan (SPP) to inform future hiring decisions (*Committee Critique #6*). The SPP has two parts: strategic and people. The strategic part focuses on mission, goals, and trends (internal and external); the people part addresses the current team, dream team, and (future) gaps. The results of this SPP are described in the final section under future strategy.

Case Study #2

How MBE Refocused on Social Safety and PhD Researcher Development

In addition, we took meaningful steps forward on PhD support (*Committee Critique #3*). We piloted improved onboarding, expanded our collaboration with Graduate School partners, and started a monthly Research Forum series that allows us to have domain-specific conversations within our community. Case Study #2 explains in greater detail these steps. Many of our permanent staff are enrolled in courses provided in Dutch and have strengthened our connections to Dutch societal partners through recent hirings of Dutch speakers, while remaining an attractive employment destination for scholars coming from abroad (*Committee Critique #4*).

FIG. 3.5 MBE's new visual identity: female persona

FIG. 3.6 MBE's new visual identity: female persona

Two areas identified by the committee are still developing. First, the knowledge-transfer strategy has not yet been formalised (*Committee Critique #5*). We decided to focus on the mission statement and identity, and now we have a more stable basis for shaping a department-wide approach in the coming period, including the development of the department website and social media strategy, which will be later described in the strategic aims of the next period.

Second, we have tried to address workload issues (*Committee Critique #8*). For example, along with the faculty, we recently introduced a new “one-pager” for proposals to increase transparency and integrate research planning. However, we find that cultural change around both taking on heavy workloads (e.g., choosing to take on more proposal writing than necessary) and proposal coordination (e.g., informing colleagues about intended grant submissions ahead of time) is challenging. Furthermore, there are important and ongoing conversations about academic autonomy and the level to which the department should coordinate for popular funding topics versus risking competition with each other internally.

3.5

Evidence

In the following sections, we present an overview of our progress over the past four years. Quantitative indicators are reported in section 3.5, while the narrative explanation of how the strategic objectives were achieved is provided in section 3.6.

3.5.1

Evidence of Seeing the Context

Hosting of Major Academic and Societal Conferences

TABLE 3.2

HOSTING OF MAJOR ACADEMIC AND SOCIETAL CONFERENCES BY MBE		
Year	Title	Theme
2022	ARCH22	Enabling health, care and well-being through design research
2022	SBE22 (Sustainable Built Environment)	Innovations for the Urban Energy Transition - Preparing for the European Renovation Wave
2024	European Network of Housing Research (ENHR)	Making housing systems work
2025	BK Festival of Resilient Neighbourhoods	"Community Engagement", "Housing and Place", "Climate Adaptation", and "Governance".

Field-Shaping Books

TABLE 3.3

MAJOR PEER-REVIEWED SCIENTIFIC BOOKS EDITED BY MBE SCHOLARS			
Year	Title	Publisher	Reference
2022	An instrumental approach to planning and development law in the Netherlands	Instituut voor Bouwrecht	Hobma & Jong (2022)
2023	Together: Towards collaborative living	Nai010 and TU Delft OPEN Publishing	Czischke et al. (2023)
2024	A Circular Built Environment in the Digital Age	Springer	De Wolf et al. (2024)
2024	Pandemic Recovery?: Reframing and Rescaling Societal Challenges	Edward Elgar Publishing	Andres et al. (2024)
2025	Adaptive Reuse for Housing	TU Delft / BookRxiv	Remøy et al. (2025)
2025	Going circular: unlocking the potential of regions and cities to drive the circular economy transition	Taylor & Francis	Dąbrowski et al. (2025)
2025	Blockchain, Smart Contracts and Distributed Ledger Technologies in the Built Environment: Key concepts, technologies, and applications	Institution of Engineering and Technology	Kassem et al. (2025)
2025	Advances in Construction and Demolition Waste Recycling: Digital Technologies, Management, Processing and Environmental Assessment	Elsevier	Pacheco-Torgal et al. (2025)

Develop New Knowledge

Peer-Reviewed Journal Publications

TABLE 3.4

MOST FREQUENT JOURNALS FOR MBE PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS 2022-2025

#	Journal	Publisher	Keywords
15	Buildings	MDPI	Building science; Building engineering; Architecture; Sustainability
13	Sustainability	MDPI	Sustainable development; Environmental systems; Policy and governance; Socio-technical transitions
12	Energy and Buildings	Elsevier	Building energy; Energy efficiency; Indoor environment; Building systems
11	Cities	Elsevier	Urban studies; Urban policy; City development; Governance
9	Land	MDPI	Land use; Spatial planning; Land systems; Environmental management
9	Urban Planning	Cogitatio Press	Urban governance; Spatial planning; Urban policy; Urban development
9	Journal of Cleaner Production	Elsevier	Cleaner production; Circular economy; Sustainability transitions; Industrial ecology
8	Journal of Housing and the Built Environment	Springer	Housing systems; Urban development; Real estate; Policy
8	Construction Management and Economics	Taylor & Francis	Construction management; Project delivery; Economics; Organization
6	Automation in Construction	Elsevier	Construction automation; Robotics; Digital construction; BIM
6	Land Use Policy	Elsevier	Land policy; Spatial planning; Governance; Sustainability
6	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	MDPI	Public health; Environmental health; Policy; Epidemiology
5	Sustainable Cities and Society	Elsevier	Sustainable cities; Urban systems; Energy; Environment
5	Bestuurskunde	Boom Uitgevers	Public administration; Governance; Policy; Institutions
5	Journal of Building Engineering	Elsevier	Building engineering; Materials; Structural systems; Performance
5	International Journal of Project Management	Elsevier	Project management; Governance; Strategy; Organizations
5	Energy Research and Social Science	Elsevier	Energy transitions; Social science; Policy; Behaviour
5	Frontiers in Psychology	Frontiers	Psychology; Behaviour; Cognition; Human factors
5	Journal of Construction Engineering and Management	ASCE	Construction engineering; Project management; Methods; Systems
5	Sustainable Production and Consumption	Elsevier	Sustainable production; Consumption; Circular economy; Systems

Best Paper Awards

TABLE 3.5

MBE BEST PAPER AWARDS (2022 - 2025)		
Paper	Award / Conference	Reference
Digitalization for a circular economy in the building industry: Multiple-case study of Dutch social housing organizations	Best Paper Award 2022, Journal of Resources, Conservation & Recycling Advances	(Çetin et al., 2022)
Learning for Value Creation in a Project Alliance	Best Paper on an International Topic, ARCOM Conference	(Kamphuis et al., 2022)
Evaluating the procurement documents of Dutch water boards portfolio: A step towards more reliable public clients	Best paper ICE infrastructure/civil engineering, ARCOM Conference	(Molaei, et al., 2022)
Changing constellations of hybridity through the phases of sustainable business model innovation	Best Paper Award, Academy of Management Annual Meeting 2024	(Greco, 2024)
Circular Building Adaptability and its Determinants – A Literature Review	Emerald Literati Awards 2024 (Award for Outstanding Paper in the 2024)	(Hamida et al., 2024)
Revisiting action research: Leveraging paradox for responsible theoretical and practical impacts	Rupert F. Chisholm Best Theory-to-Practice Paper Award, Academy of Management (2025 cycle)	(Greco & Berti, 2025)
The added value of environmental certification in the Dutch office market	Best Paper Award 2024, Journal of European Real Estate Research	(van Overbeek et al., 2024)
The pilot trap: Interactions between sustainable startups and clients in the built environment	Paul Townsend Commemorative Award for Research in Practice, ARCOM Conference	(Leendertse et al., 2024)
Circular renovation of urban infrastructures: A multi-project perspective	Best Paper Award, CIB World Building Congress 2025	(Ashrafi et al., 2025)
Impactful projects: forward co-creation of academics and practitioners in circular construction transition	Best Paper Award, Track Project and Society, European Academy of Management (EURAM) 2025	(van Uden et al., 2025)

3.5.3

Make a Difference in Practice

Professional Publications

In addition to scientific publications, MBE develops many professional and societal publications. These, along with societal consortiums, are described in further detail in Section 3.6.

Accomplishments During the Past Four Years – Research Quality and Societal Relevance

The following chapter is structured around the six faculty themes at BK, which we use as a narrative lens to explain both what MBE is doing and how this work is being developed. The themes do not function as rigid silos or organisational units; rather, they provide a shared storyline through which research questions, methods, and societal engagement can be understood across the department.

TABLE 3.6

RESEARCH FUNDING MBE								
	2022		2023		2024		2025	
	k€	%	k€	%	k€	%	k€	%
Direct funding (1)	5.863	61%	6.642	57%	7.382	56%	7.246	54%
Research grants (2)	880	9%	1.487	13%	2.111	16%	2.025	15%
Contract research (3)	2.789	29%	3.355	29%	3.546	27%	3.925	29%
Other (4)	76	1%	85	1%	137	1%	113	1%
Total funding	9.608	100%	11.569	100%	13.176	100%	13.309	100%
Personnel costs	8.926	95%	10.869	97%	12.656	95%	12.837	96%
Material costs	243	3%	138	1%	152	1%	52	0%
Other costs	232	2%	198	2%	532	4%	460	3%
Total expenditure	9.401	100%	11.205	100%	13.340	100%	13.349	100%
	207		364		-164		-40	

TABLE 3.7

RESEARCH OUTPUT MBE				
	2022	2023	2024	2025
Refereed article	100	107	102	108
Non-refereed article	2	1	4	2
Professional publications	39	46	27	31
Books	1	2	2	3
Book chapter	11	15	41	25
Publications aimed at the general public	1	0	3	0
Conference papers	19	28	30	26
PhD theses	7	9	8	14
Other research output	46	50	52	29
Total	227	259	270	241

TABLE 3.8

RESEARCH STAFF MBE								
SEP categories	2022		2023		2024		2025	
	#	FTE	#	FTE	#	FTE	#	FTE
Assistant professor	18,7	6,8	19,7	7,1	18,3	6,8	16,5	6,2
Associate professor	10,8	4,1	11,3	4,4	11,0	4,3	11,7	4,5
Full professor	12,3	4,0	13,0	4,0	13,0	4,0	13,8	4,2
Postdocs	7,1	5,2	8,8	6,7	12,8	8,9	15,5	11,3
Researchers (other)	11,4	7,3	15,3	9,9	13,9	9,0	10,3	6,1
PhD candidate (HR)	21,2	20,6	29,3	28,4	33,8	31,9	36,8	35,8
Total	81,4	48,0	97,2	60,5	102,7	64,8	104,5	68,1
Support staff	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Grand Total	81,4	48,0	97,2	60,5	102,7	64,8	104,5	68,1

TABLE 3.9

PHD CANDIDATES MBE									
	Enrollment			Success rates cumulative					
	Male & other	Female	Total	Graduated totals		Not yet finished		Discontinued	
Start	#	#	#	#	%	#	%	#	%
2022	9	5	14	0	-	14	100%	0	-
2023	4	8	12	0	-	11	92%	1	8%
2024	6	5	11	0	-	11	100%	0	-
2025	6	7	13	0	-	13	100%	0	-
Total	25	25	50	0	-	49	-	1	-

TABLE 3.10

PHD CANDIDATES MBE PROGRESS																	
	Enrollment			Success rates cumulative													
	Male & other	Female	Total	Graduated ≤ 4 years		Graduated ≤ 5 years		Graduated ≤ 6 years		Graduated ≤ 7 years		Graduated totals		Not yet finished		Discontinued	
Start	#	#	#	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
2016	1	6	7	0	-	2	29%	4	57%	4	57%	4	57%	3	43%	-	-
2017	4	4	8	1	13%	3	38%	4	50%	4	50%	4	50%	1	13%	3	38%
2018	7	4	11	2	18%	4	36%	7	64%	9	82%	9	82%	0	-	2	18%
2019	2	7	9	0	-	3	33%	6	67%	7	78%	7	78%	1	11%	1	11%
2020	10	6	16	1	6%	7	44%	7	44%	7	44%	7	44%	8	50%	1	6%
2021	5	5	10	0	-	1	10%	1	10%	1	10%	1	10%	5	50%	4	40%
Total	29	32	61	4	-	20	-	29	-	32	-	32	-	18	-	11	-

FIG. 3.7 Proportion male (blue) / female (orange) in research staff 2022-2025 (excl. guests).

FIG. 3.8 Proportion of nationality (NL/EU/non-EU) (excl. guests). Dark green = NL, medium green = EU, light green = non-EU.

Sustainable Urbanisation

At MBE, a sustainable built environment is understood as an environment that fosters social and environmental sustainability while contributing to the reduction of social inequalities. Achieving this goal requires a thoughtful provision and governance of housing and places to work, learn and innovate, including green space, infrastructure, and amenities. Our approach is value-driven, prioritising bottom-up and inclusive processes, evidence-based decision-making, and measurable social outcomes.

Housing is a cornerstone of a sustainable built environment. Access to secure and affordable homes is a fundamental precondition for living a healthy and fulfilling life. Unfortunately, the current housing crisis in Europe places severe pressure on this foundation. At MBE, the housing crisis forms a central focus of housing research. Our researchers investigate its roots and drivers, as well as the socially and spatially unequal outcomes it produces. Above all, they work on developing new and innovative housing solutions that can help alleviate the impacts of the crisis and contribute to a more equitable and resilient housing system.

Collaborative living is an example of such an innovative housing solution, addressing social sustainability, collective action, and alternatives to dominant models. The book *Together: Towards Collaborative Living* (Czischke et al., 2023), based on eight years of research, has significantly expanded awareness of this emerging approach among academics, practitioners, and citizens. The VIDI In-Common project (2025–2029) will further advance MBE's research into upscaling collaborative housing.

MBE is internationally recognised for its scientific and societal impact on housing research. For example, in 2025, MBE staff joined as a member of the EU Housing Advisory Board that advised on the European Affordable Housing Plan. This board called for a paradigm shift to treat housing as essential infrastructure alongside transport, energy, and water. The department also plays a central role in the European Network of Housing Research (ENHR), with MBE staff serving as Chair and Vice-Chair. In 2024, MBE organised the ENHR Annual Conference in Delft, bringing together about 500 academics, policymakers, and practitioners.

MBE's research in the field of sustainable urbanisation encompasses more than housing. It centres on bringing diverse actors together to address urban challenges at various scales. In doing so, it often challenges established paradigms. For example, a comparative study of public transport financing in major Western cities (Van Zoest & Daamen, 2024) has opened new conceptual ground by shedding light on the persistent inertia in infrastructure planning and funding. New knowledge has also emerged from a study on the dependence of Antwerp's chemical industry on Dutch base industry (Van den Berghe et al., 2025). This study challenges frameworks based on administrative boundaries and stresses the importance of global supply and value chains. It informed Dutch parliamentary debates, led to keynote invitations, and reshapes industrial strategy and spatial planning towards more sustainability-driven approaches, demonstrating how research can directly influence national policy and industry collaboration.

FIG. 3.9 The 2024 ENHR was hosted by MBE at TU Delft

MBE maintains a long-standing cooperation with *Stichting Kennis Gebiedsontwikkeling* (SKG), a foundation supported by around 60 public and private partners involved in urban area development. The collaboration focuses on developing knowledge and practical instruments, connecting key actors and disciplines, improving quality and sustainability in projects, and contributing to education and research, including funding PhD candidates and a professorship in urban area development. SKG and MBE also jointly run *gebiedsontwikkeling.nu*, a platform with 35,000 monthly visitors, publishing 500 annual contributions from 200 authors, supported by a dedicated editorial team and advisory board to ensure quality and continuity.

MBE places a strong emphasis on the social sustainability of the built environment. In two PhD theses (Janssen, 2024; Kimhur, 2022) as well as in the H2020 UPLIFT project (Gentili and Hoekstra, 2025), the Capability Approach was used to gain insight into how (vulnerable) residents navigate and experience the built and institutional environment they live in. In the latter project *Uplift Youth*, boards of young people and policy-makers in four big European cities also collaboratively developed policies to expand young people's capabilities. This process generated significant local policy impact and produced valuable methodological insights that are shared through an online course, a guidebook, and training modules for professionals and students.

The booklet ‘Where We Stand’ (Esteban et al., 2024) reports on participatory workshops with residents of vulnerable neighbourhoods based on the method of collective introspection, as part of a larger NWA-supported transdisciplinary research programme on climate risks in the built environment (Red&Blue Project). The publication demonstrates how innovative methodologies can bridge academic research and grassroots perspectives in integrated urban re/development strategies. Innovation in participation practices is also visible in a workshop format that MBE developed for designing area developments based on pluriform place values (Ruijsink & Neefs, 2025). This workshop format integrates unheard voices, including nonhuman actors, into decision-making processes in the built environment. It has informed municipal strategies, with spin-offs in professional education and other projects.

3.6.2

Healthy Cities

MBE approaches Healthy Cities through evidence-based design across building and urban scales. We combine post-occupancy evaluation, environmental psychology, housing market analysis, action research, and digital simulations to test how different housing concepts, building layouts, daylight, acoustics, air quality, and green/active mobility shape health and well-being. In our research projects, we co-create with hospitals, housing providers, municipalities, and end-users to translate findings into practice and policy solutions, standards, and procurement. Equity and diversity are integral values: we design with special attention to the needs of vulnerable groups and measure outcomes, not just intentions, in real settings.

Case Study #5

How MBE is helping to solve the housing crisis.

The “Resilient Neighbourhoods” Flagship was a faculty-wide initiative in 2025 addressing urgent housing challenges by leveraging interdisciplinary expertise. Led by MBE, a team of eight academics from all four BK faculty departments collaborated to identify key knowledge developed by our faculty that addresses neighbourhood challenges and proposes innovative solutions. Their work produced two major outcomes: the BK Festival “Resilient Neighbourhoods” (27–30 October 2025), which showcased research and student projects through events open to the public and exhibitions, and the White Paper “Resilient Neighbourhoods in the Netherlands: An Evidence-Based Blueprint for Action”, a strategic document offering practical tools for policymakers, professionals, and citizens. Both outputs were structured around four resilience dimensions: *Climate Adaptation, Housing and Place, Communities and Citizen Engagement*, and *Governance*. The White Paper outlined ten recommendations spanning different spatial scales. Results have been presented at national events, including the Dag van Volkshuisvesting, and will inform debates leading up to the 2026 local elections. A short film was produced during the festival as a key science communication output.

Resilient Neighbourhoods in the Netherlands

An evidence-based blueprint for action

FIG. 3.10 New White Paper developed from the Resilient Neighborhoods Festival

FIG. 3.11 The ARCH22 conference co-hosted by MBE and Erasmus University Rotterdam

In response to the housing crisis and demographic shifts, particularly ageing, new research has focused on the intersection of housing, ageing, and care. In 2025, the faculty announced the creation of a Centre for Housing, Ageing and Care, funded by the Dutch government and market partners. The centre will consolidate faculty-wide research, including the study of innovative community-living housing concepts for older adults. An example of the latter is the recently published book chapter “The clustered living approach in the Netherlands” (Czischke & Moons, 2025) in the edited volume *Collaborative Housing, Ageing and Social Care* (Policy Press), which applies the concept of «Positive Health» developed by Machteld in collaborative housing.

MBE researchers have contributed to environmental psychology through initiatives such as the *ARCH22 Enabling Health, Care, and Well-Being through Design Research conference* (TU Delft, 2022), which focused on evidence-based design in healthcare environments. Research on post-occupancy evaluation (POE) in hospitals shows how built environments can support patient safety, well-being, and quality of care (Van Heel et al. 2024). Additional studies examine how design influences privacy, staff workflows, and the use of virtual reality for evaluating future healthcare settings (Koolwijk et al., 2025). This work has also been conducted with students in the course Research Methods 2. Overall, POE insights are integrated into both research and education, strengthening the link between design research and professional practice in healthcare environments.

FIG. 3.12 The book *Adaptive Reuse for Housing* (Remøy et al., 2025)

3.6.3

(Heritage with) Future Value

MBE believes future value extends beyond traditional financial metrics to encompass social, ecological, cultural, and long-term benefits that emerge from adaptive, circular, and participatory practices. We see buildings, infrastructure, and neighbourhoods as dynamic assets whose worth evolves over time. MBE scholars work towards this theme with examples such as adaptive reuse of housing, non-monetary values, finance, and public real estate. Overall, MBE is working towards a broader view of value to help guide decision-making, policy, and practice.

The topic of *adaptive reuse* is one example of how MBE connects the concepts of heritage and future value. For example, the recent book *Adaptive Reuse for Housing* touches on themes of use value, user appreciation, societal value, and the contribution to circular real estate (Remøy et al., 2025). The book helps inform Dutch governmental strategies, fosters international knowledge exchange, and can be used by students globally. Another example is the NOMAD project, led by a Marie Skłodowska-Curie postdoctoral fellow hosted at MBE, which explored the values of experimental temporary uses in vacant buildings, focusing on mapping and understanding these values, and how they can be incorporated into real estate decision-making. The project included the presentation of the short film “Haven” (Mazzarella, 2024) at the Rotterdam Architecture Film Festival (AFFR) and organised the symposium “Temporary Use and Commons in Real Estate Management”, bringing together international experts on the topic.

In 2023, MBE initiated a new cluster hire with money from the National Growth Funds. Three new permanent staff were selected to work towards the theme “values beyond monetary value”. These scholars challenge how we conceptualise “Future Value” in the built environment. Although still at an early stage, the appointments already show strong promise through complementary research trajectories. For example, this has resulted in the article *A Historical Narrative of Value Theory in Economics and Appraisal* (Zhang et al., 2025), which examines the theoretical conception of value in real estate, linking it to socioeconomic developments and challenging current valuation paradigms.

This cluster hire has also resulted in a line of research on how sustainable finance can inform investment decision-making by integrating diverse value perspectives that move beyond conventional monetary metrics. This research focuses on developing new approaches to quantify non-financial value (drawing on semantic geometrical models, quantum finance, and real options theory) to capture the complex interrelations between sustainability, regulation, and market dynamics. By combining the Financial, Environmental, Social, and Technology (FEST) framework dimensions, MBE researchers can build valuation models that capture how investment choices generate value across dimensions such as circularity, energy efficiency, and social impact. The ReValue platform convened four sessions in 2025 with an average attendance of 75 valuers, investors, and financial institutions, in close collaboration with RICS and the DuPa 3.0 working group. This enables MBE scholars to bring these new value perspectives into professional and policy frameworks within the built environment. This also directly translated into the new interdisciplinary MSc course *Sustainable Finance: Valuation Techniques Going Beyond Monetary Value*.

Additional work on circular economy and new economics advances systemic, human-centred approaches to value creation in construction, renovation, and infrastructure, offering actionable frameworks for cities and industry. For example, MBE researchers can map waste journeys in renovation projects, highlighting the importance of human-centric approaches alongside technical solutions (Schraven et al., 2025). Together, MBE sees Future Value research as a distinctive and emerging approach that integrates economics, management, sustainability, and societal impact.

Although we look beyond monetary terms, finance still plays a key role in future value and sustainability transitions. Within the NWA-funded Red and Blue project, MBE examines the intersection of real estate financialisation and climate risk governance. This research shows how financial institutions shape uneven trajectories of urban climate action and how public–private collaboration can redirect these towards more equitable and effective outcomes. In 2025, MBE convened a national expert meeting and delivered a keynote synthesising a decade of research, contributing to the launch of a national adaptation finance think tank and the Zuid-Holland knowledge programme supporting transdisciplinary research at TU Delft.

Further, MBE works to preserve values in public real estate. For example, project Campus NL (2023–2027), commissioned by Universities of the Netherlands, takes a transdisciplinary approach between academics and practitioners to address organisational, social, financial, and technical challenges in transforming 4.5 million m² of university buildings. There is additionally formalised collaboration with the Netherlands Police, focusing on performance measurement, value assessment, and decision-support tools for their 1.8 million m² building portfolio. Within the broader context, MBE plays a central role internationally through its long-standing contribution to the European Real Estate Society (ERES), dedicated to promoting and advancing the field of real estate research, with MBE staff serving as board members.

3.6.4

Climate Adaptation and Energy Transition

Across MBE, scholars examine how financial, digital, and collaborative approaches enable equitable climate action, sustainable renovation, and resilient urban infrastructure. Here we see the strength of MBE in dealing with adaptation, transformation, and transitions.

The energy transition places enormous pressure on Europe’s existing housing stock, demanding effective renovation strategies and digital tools to accelerate decarbonisation. Within this challenge, MBE leads research on housing quality and process innovation, focusing on policies and tools supporting the energy transition in existing housing. Recent work, including work on advancing energy renovations through digitalisation (Hwang et al., 2025), is a key output of the Horizon Europe project DemoBLog. The paper critically reviews EU policies on Digital Building Logbooks (DBLs), essential for achieving Europe’s decarbonisation goals. This research directly influences policy

Case Study #6
MBE’s multi-scalar approach to built environment transitions

and industry, contributing to the approval of a new NWO-KIC project titled *RenoDat*, which explores implementation of the Renovation Passport under the revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive.

Several other projects focus on the behaviour of homeowners and occupants to support the energy transition and renovation of the existing housing stock, and use transaction costs theory to reduce barriers and exploit opportunities in renovation processes. In the NWO-KIC project JustPrepare, MBE focuses on justice-based decision-making processes in vulnerable neighbourhoods (Ricci et al., 2025).

Experiences in the various projects on behavioural aspects in renovation projects led to MBE becoming one of the main partners in the [SHAPE-EU project](#) to develop a Social Innovation Blueprint. A series of dissemination activities followed, such as a network event at the [World Urban Forum 12](#) in Cairo in 2024 organised by UN-Habitat with about 30,000 participants.

Research on energy efficiency and renovation at MBE often combines innovation, valuation, and strategic niche development. The EU LIFE project CondoReno has developed four Integrated Home Renovation Services for condominium associations. This project produced tested business models and publicly available services, embedded in local contexts and adopted across multiple European countries. Its societal and scientific impact includes systemic innovation in renovation, energy and carbon savings, policy uptake, stakeholder training, and advances in innovation theory and business model viability. The work exemplifies sustainability, collaboration, co-creation, accessibility, and clean energy transition.

The energy transition – from fossil to renewable sources – requires major upgrades to an already crowded underground infrastructure. MBE scholars study how megaprojects and interorganisational collaborations can manage the complexity of such transformative work. For example, longitudinal research reveals how power relations, daily practices, and organisational tensions shape multi-level project outcomes (van Marrewijk & van den Ende, 2022). Working with the Dutch Centre for Underground Construction (Centrum van Ondergronds Bouwen), MBE scholars examined nine organisations responsible for building subsurface utilities and telecom networks. Beyond advancing academic understanding, the research delivered operational improvements, including cost reductions and efficiency gains, demonstrating the value of rigorous project research for infrastructure transitions.

Digital transformation and urban planning intersect closely with adaptation and infrastructure challenges. MBE explores the intersections of digital transformation, climate adaptation, and urban planning. In 2022, MBE began collaborating with contacts in Brazil, with an MBE researcher delivering a keynote on cities, infrastructure and climate adaptation at an international conference organised by Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie in São Paulo. This presentation initiated an ongoing collaboration and exchange, leading to a funded comparative research project on micro-mobility services in disadvantaged neighbourhoods in São Paulo and Rotterdam. Similarly, MBE has developed collaborations with various Asian research institutes on issues around urban development, energy transitions, megaprojects and financialisation.

FIG. 3.13 AI supported interface framework for the Information Provision in Energy-Efficient Renovations (Bingöl et al., 2025)

3.6.5

Digitalisation and Artificial Intelligence

At MBE, digitalisation is not approached as a purely technical challenge, but as a fundamentally sociotechnical transformation. Technologies shape professional practices, organisational arrangements, and decision-making just as much as these social contexts shape how technologies are designed and used. MBE's research therefore focuses on understanding what digital transformation means for the multiple actors involved in designing, constructing, managing, and transforming the built environment, and how policies, institutions, and everyday practices evolve alongside emerging digital tools.

This perspective is strongly reflected in MBE's leadership in responsible and human-centred AI. In 2022, MBE joined the wider TU Delft initiative on AI labs by founding the AiBLE Lab (AI for the Built Living Environment). The lab advances a just and responsible use of AI by foregrounding multi-stakeholder deliberation, ethical reflection, and human-AI collaboration. This research integrates information management, organisational theory, and human-computer interaction to study how AI can support equitable decision-making from building components to urban-scale systems. Through human-AI experiments, public debates, and policy-oriented engagement – including contributions to AI for urban planning and infrastructure life-extension – this work demonstrates how AI can be embedded in governance and practice rather than imposed as a technical fix. The lab's strong collaboration with Computer Science, industry partners, and national initiatives such as the Dutch Growth Fund and NWO-KIC programmes further reinforces MBE's role as a connector between technical innovation and societal needs.

For example, ongoing research within AiBLE exemplifies this sociotechnical approach in the context of the energy transition (Bingöl et al., 2025). MBE studies the role of intermediary actors in energy renovations for Homeowners Associations (VvEs), highlighting how communication, trust-building, and coordination are central to successful renovation processes. By identifying where existing information flows and decision-support mechanisms break down, this research explores how AI can enhance (and not replace) human mediation. The resulting tools and insights offer practical value for governments, municipalities, and industry actors seeking to accelerate energy renovations, while contributing to academic debates on AI-enabled governance. The project also strengthens MBE's educational mission through open-access datasets, AI-focused capstone projects, and integration into the newly redeveloped Information Management in the Built Environment course.

Across MBE's work on digitalisation, a shared emphasis on human-centred technology development is clearly visible. This is reflected in research that critically reorients digital innovation towards cognition, decision-making, and practice. The paper "Enhancing Situation Awareness of Construction Managers using Human-Centred Digital Twins" exemplifies this approach by challenging technology-driven assumptions that more data automatically lead to better management. Instead, the work formalises construction managers' goals and decision processes using Goal-Directed Task Analysis, generating theory-informed design principles for digital twins that support decision-making under uncertainty (Čustović et al., 2025a). Building on this work, the Agents in Construction Ontology provides an open-source ontological resource that structures how human and artificial agents interact in construction settings (Čustović et al., 2025b). This contribution not only informs future AI-assisted tools but also embodies MBE's commitment to Open Science and practice-oriented research.

MBE also has several projects at the intersection of digitalisation and the circular economy. This perspective is articulated in the multiple-case study on digitalisation for circular economy implementation in Dutch social housing organisations (Çetin et al., 2022). The study shows that technologies such as AI, digital twins, scanning, and digital marketplaces can support circular strategies across building lifecycles – particularly maintenance, reuse, and urban mining – but only when aligned with actor needs, data governance, and institutional capacity. Rather than treating digital tools as universal enablers, the research highlights cultural, organisational, market, and regulatory barriers that shape their effectiveness in practice.

MBE's digitalisation agenda also extends beyond professional actors to residents and users of the built environment. MBE has developed an impactful line of research using virtual reality (VR) to empower residents in housing renovation processes. This work shows how VR simulations, co-design workshops, and charrettes enable residents to actively shape renovation decisions, increasing engagement, ownership, and understanding of technical constraints (Kowaltowski et al., 2024). This approach has been successfully applied in NWO-funded projects such as UVital and VR Renovate, where residents collaboratively designed renovation outcomes, including realised garden spaces in social housing complexes (van Oel et al., 2023). Contractors and housing associations have since adopted VR as a communication tool in complex retrofit projects, demonstrating direct uptake in practice. Ongoing work under VR Retrofit 4U explores how VR can be embedded earlier in design processes, strengthening collaboration across residents, professionals, housing portfolios, and municipal policy agendas.

FIG. 3.14 An MBE PhD researcher guides a tenant through a VR narrative that empowers them take control of the retrofit process.

Finally, MBE contributes to digitalisation at the governance and infrastructure level through research on data spaces and data governance. Recent work examines how regulatory frameworks, legal structures, and multi-level governance arrangements enable or constrain the development of data spaces as part of Europe's digital and sustainability strategies, including collaboration with the Municipality of Rotterdam and its Citiverse programme within the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium to explore how urban data infrastructures can support advanced AI applications while aligning with public values and policy objectives. Complementing this, MBE also addresses data as a subject, focusing on what building data are required for specific functions across the lifecycle, and how such data can be effectively collected, structured, stored, and shared to improve efficiency and effectiveness in building and renovation projects. This includes work on concepts such as Digital Building Logbooks and Renovation Passports (e.g., DemoBlog and Renodat; see Section 3.6.4), which aim to systematise data flows across actors and phases. At the international level, MBE contributes to the development of global building data infrastructures as a member of the GlobalABC Data Hub, supporting collaboration on standardisation and knowledge exchange for building data systems worldwide.

FIG. 3.15 Ad Straub discusses his work with the Queen of the Netherlands at the 2023 Climate Tech Forum in Brussels

3.6.6

Circularity in the Built Environment

MBE works to accelerate the transition towards a circular, equitable, and low-carbon built environment, while maintaining a strong capacity for critical reflection. MBE's work on circularity is characterised by a dual approach: developing actionable tools and frameworks that directly support practice and policy, while also questioning dominant assumptions about value, governance, and decision-making in circular transitions. This combination enables MBE not only to support implementation, but also to shape how circularity is understood, evaluated, and governed in the built environment.

MBE has established a strong position in advancing circular building practices through conceptual frameworks that translate abstract principles into practical guidance. One example is the MBE work that adapted Brand's six shearing layers model to better support material reuse in construction projects. By refining broad categories such as "Site" and "Services" into more operational subcomponents, including outdoor spaces and HVAC systems, this work provides a concrete structure for identifying reuse opportunities across building layers. The framework has gained international visibility, including recognition at the Climate Tech Forum in Brussels in 2023, and has informed discussions at the European policy level. Its relevance lies in enabling clients, designers, and contractors to make more informed decisions about reuse, while supporting alignment with emerging EU and national circular economy policies.

Complementing these conceptual contributions, MBE has developed widely adopted tools that support the operationalisation of circular ambitions in real projects. A key example is Het Nieuwe Normaal (HNN), which is now broadly used in the Dutch building sector (Wamelink & Peeters, 2025). HNN enables clients and project teams to define, compare, and communicate circularity ambitions in tenders and project planning. It translates abstract sustainability goals into concrete performance indicators. Examples like HNN show how MBE can bridge circular aspirations to actionable steps.

MBE's circular economy research also addresses the behavioural and organisational dimensions of transition. The TranCiBo project examines how collaboration during the design phase can support the shift from linear to circular construction practices. By studying how roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes evolve in low-carbon and circular projects, TranCiBo highlights the importance of governance and team dynamics in achieving systemic change. Importantly, the project's datasets are made openly available, reinforcing MBE's commitment to Open Science and enabling further research on behavioural change in circular transitions (Eikelenboom and Van Marrewijk, 2023).

At the urban and infrastructural scale, MBE advances circularity through systems-oriented and logistics-focused research. MBE leads a series of large, practice-based projects that address circular and zero-emission construction in dense urban environments. Projects such as NWO Logiquay and SEB Zero Emission Highrise focus on the renovation of bridges, quay walls, and high-rise buildings, particularly in historical city centres. By developing closed-loop logistics, multi-project planning methods, and

meso-scale coordination frameworks, these projects demonstrate how circularity can be embedded across portfolios. A key output from Logiquay is a three-step framework – Planning, Assessing, and Routing – that supports material reuse across multiple projects, enabling municipalities to scale circular strategies while reducing emissions and disruption. This work also explicitly addresses governance and value distribution, emphasising that successful circular transitions require equitable allocation of costs, benefits, and decision-making power (Ashrafi et al., 2025).

MBE is also scholarly engaged with the sectoral needs for the circular economy transition. In this regard, a group of academics from MBE are involved in a large consortium (100+ industrial and societal partners) called ‘Toekomstbestendige Leefomgeving’ (TBL), funded through the National Growth Fund. Within the overall goal of the programme to scale up climate, low-carbon and circular construction practices, MBE’s contributions are embedded in two sub-consortia, on (a) buildings and (b) infrastructures. In the infrastructure consortium, the academics focus on two areas. First, a set of projects aim to cultivate more circular experimentation in cities. Here, circular solutions for public space are explored and developed using living lab and business modelling approaches in collaboration with AMS and Amsterdam. The second area studies whether more transparency of costs and values would offer a better case for circular construction. By comparing traditional and circular strategies to replace bridges, tools are developed to study (a) the level of transaction costs, (b) proof for value claims, and (c) the value of more information. As is required of the TBL programme overall, these tools are deployed directly with sectoral partners.

MBE is also strongly engaged with industry and policy networks in advancing the circular economy transition, moving beyond observation to actively shaping change in practice. This is reflected in a series of collaborative research projects developed in close partnership with industry, including Circol (NWO), The Circular Kitchen (Climate-KIC), Developing Circular Building Components, and CHARM (Interreg NWE), which collectively demonstrate how circular innovations can be tested, implemented, and scaled in real-world contexts. In parallel, MBE plays a leading role in national coordination and agenda-setting, including chairing the National Transition Team for a Circular Construction Economy, contributing to the Building Material Agreement, and participating in the program advisory board of the TKI Bouw en Techniek multi-annual innovation programme on Circular Building and Infrastructure. These roles position MBE not only as a knowledge producer, but also as a key actor in shaping the direction of circular construction at the national level.

Circular economy research at MBE is increasingly connected to questions of value, valuation, and decision-making under uncertainty. The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Doctoral Network QuiVal (2024–2028) brings together eight universities, fourteen practice partners, and thirteen PhD candidates to develop new valuation approaches for circular real estate. QuiVal (Quantum-inspired valuation of circular real estate) explicitly challenges conventional monetary valuation by integrating complex value drivers – environmental, social, and temporal – using methodologies inspired by quantum mechanics. Similarly, other MBE research on circular adaptive reuse strategies has significantly contributed to understanding how buildings can be transformed over time, and this line of work continues through postdoctoral research. This work positions MBE at the forefront of international debates on how circularity reshapes value creation in the built environment.

Finally, MBE's work on circular economy is strongly future-oriented through large collaborative projects focused on adaptive reuse and housing. The Interreg NWE projects Circular Building Convert (2024–2028) and Circular Transformation (2025–2026) develop business models and decision-support tools for extending building lifespans and enabling affordable, circular housing solutions. In parallel, the Reincarnate project (2022–2026) aims to dramatically reduce construction and demolition waste while lowering sector emissions by developing scenarios and decision models that support uptake of circular practices across Europe. An important output of the Reincarnate project is the innovation “Strategic circular decision-making for real estate assets” (van Laar, B., 2024). MBE also takes a leading role in the DAT 4TU Circularity and Sustainability, fostering cooperation between the four Dutch universities of technology.

Connecting Research and Teaching

At MBE, research and teaching are connected through a bidirectional model. On the one hand, our research directly informs teaching content, methods, and course design. On the other hand, teaching – most notably the master's graduation thesis – is used to advance and extend departmental research agendas. This alignment ensures that education remains research-led, while research benefits from sustained engagement with student inquiry, empirical work, and emerging topics.

Case Study #3

How MBE reorganized the graduation thesis to better connect research and teaching

A central mechanism, recently introduced, is the strategic alignment of master's graduation theses with ongoing staff research projects. Graduating master's students are encouraged to position their thesis work within active research lines, empirical case studies, or funded projects led by MBE staff. You can read about our recent efforts to organise our graduation theses with ongoing research projects in *Case Study 3*.

Over the past four years, we have seen successful examples of graduation theses resulting in high-quality publications. For example, the article “When ‘port out – city in’ becomes a strategy” was co-authored by MBE staff alongside a master's graduate (van den Berghe et al., 2023). The thesis research was embedded in a broader research agenda on port–city interface conflicts and governance, allowing student work to contribute directly to international academic debate while deepening staff-led empirical research. Another example is a thesis on price indexes of commercial real estate, which contributed to the theory of pricing and valuation in commercial real estate. Its practical impact has already been significant, as the research led to the development of a new statistical method for constructing indexes that is now used by the Central Bureau of Statistics (Ishaak et al., 2025).

Staff research also shapes course content and learning formats. Research conducted within the NWO-funded *Stepping Out* project directly informed educational programmes through the development of the *Systeem Innovatie Leergang* and the *Transitions Makers* tool. These outputs are used in teaching to expose students to sustainability transitions, urban living labs, and inter-organisational collaboration, while simultaneously serving as research instruments to study learning, experimentation, and governance in real-world urban contexts such as Havenstad (Amsterdam) and M4H (Rotterdam). In this way, research outcomes are translated into teaching materials, while teaching environments function as testing grounds for research concepts.

FIG. 3.16 The Participants of the 2025 Summer School "Sustainable Housing from a European Perspective"

In addition to degree programmes, MBE connects research and teaching through targeted international education initiatives that disseminate the state of the art of departmental research. A key example is the Summer School “Sustainable Housing from a European Perspective”, which presents cutting-edge research on housing systems, policy, finance, and governance to an international audience of master’s students, PhD candidates, and early-career professionals. The summer school draws directly on ongoing research within MBE on housing affordability, tenure systems, regulation, and socioeconomic dimensions of housing, translating recent academic insights into an intensive educational format. By attracting participants from around the world, the summer school functions both as a research dissemination platform and as a space for scholarly exchange, allowing staff to test emerging ideas, engage with diverse perspectives, and integrate the latest research developments into teaching. In this way, MBE uses advanced teaching formats not only to educate, but also to actively position and circulate its housing research internationally.

MBE has also seen cross-sectional collaboration resulting in publications that explicitly integrate educational innovation with research agendas. For example, a recent book chapter brought together MBE staff across construction management, real estate, and urban development to translate research on sustainability transitions into educational frameworks (Mlecnik et al., 2024).

MBE research on entrepreneurship in the built environment also directly informs our education programmes at both department and faculty level. An example is the award-winning paper “The Pilot Trap: Interactions Between Sustainable Start-Ups and Clients in the Built Environment” (Leendertse et al., 2025), which analyses why many sustainability-driven start-ups struggle to move beyond pilot projects despite technical success. The insights from this paper are actively integrated into our entrepreneurship education courses, helping students understand real-world dynamics of innovation, scaling, and client engagement in construction and real estate contexts. This helps align our research with education initiatives such as BK Launch, where students develop start-ups and venture ideas rooted in the built environment.

Longer-term research trajectories similarly support teaching across the department. Foundational research in planning and development law has been consolidated into the book *An Instrumental Approach to Planning and Development Law in the Netherlands* (Hobma and Jong, 2022), which is now used in teaching at TU Delft and other universities. The book draws on extensive contract research for public-sector clients and directly informs courses dealing with governance, legal instruments, and spatial development, thereby connecting research, education, and societal practice.

Finally, research-led teaching is embedded in methodological and design-oriented courses. In the Research Methods 2 course, students conducted empirical research in collaboration with healthcare institutions, generating interview-based insights that informed the redesign of psychiatric wards. These course-based research activities contribute data and reflections to ongoing research on evidence-based design and health-supportive environments, while simultaneously training students in rigorous, applied research methods.

3.7

Strategy for the Next Six Years

3.7.1

SWOT Analysis

Our SWOT analysis shows that MBE builds on strong foundations, including a well-established tradition of industry collaboration, leadership in inter-university research networks, and a recognised position as a Centre of Expertise on key societal challenges such as housing and circularity. MBE’s ability to bridge disciplinary depth with transdisciplinary, engaged scholarship enables effective translation between policy, practice, and research. At the same time, the analysis highlights structural weaknesses, including dependence on individuals rather than institutionalised collaborations, limited embedded support for large consortia, high education and service workloads, and an underdeveloped theoretical core and talent pipeline.

Strengths

- Strong tradition of institutionalized collaboration with professionals and practitioners (joint research, living labs, co-funded projects), providing access to practice-driven and societally relevant research questions;
- Active leadership in inter-university research collaborations (e.g., Convergence, 4TU, AMS, LDE) ;
- Recognized Centre of Expertise for several key societal topics (e.g., housing, circularity, urban development, Artificial Intelligence) ;
- Making a Difference: ability to translate from policy to practice and vice versa;
- Focus on Engaged Scholarship and Team Science (and not “extractive scholarship.”);
- Transdisciplinary research is in our nature, and we can connect disciplines and institutions;
- Strong on both fundamental disciplinary knowledge and topical research themes, allowing us to be bridge-builders in inter/trans disciplinary research settings;
- Proactive approach to PhD development, social safety, and transparent organizational procedures.

Weaknesses

- Dependence on specific individuals in collaborations rather than structural embedding of the department in networks;
- Managing large consortiums with industry partners is time consuming; current options for support staff (e.g., project management capacity) have been underutilized;
- Fragile structural support for transdisciplinary research; support staff are not embedded;
- High education and service demands;
- Lack of clear definition/theoretical basis for the field of MBE (or the field that MBE research covers);
- Limited evidence of talent pipeline from MBE masters track to PhD researcher;
- Online web presence and social media presence lacking compared to peer institutions.

Opportunities

- Build upon transdisciplinary research strength to increase relevance and funding competitiveness;
- Use societal themes as drivers to sharpen MBE’s research profile and uniqueness;
- Increased inter-university research collaboration and access to shared infrastructure;
- Growth of industry co-funded PhD trajectories and research projects;
- Lifelong learning–related research and alternative research career pathways;
- Strong and engaged Alumni network which can be activated more structurally than it already is;
- Extend to show the impact of our research outside of academia;
- Increase the external visibility of MBE, especially to our academic peers.

Threats

- Higher competition for research funding plus less overall funding from Dutch Research Council (NWO). Additionally, increased requirements for cash contributions from societal partners that can often exceed the capacities of our partners;

- Reduced research capacity due to structural budget limitations; non-replacement of retiring staff and increase in students will result in increased educational and service workload for permanent staff;
- These same financial constraints are also limiting strategic research investments
- Reduced research flexibility due to the 100% rule, due to partial dependence of tenured research capacity on project funding. This extra funding above 100% is for education, freeing capacity for research;
- Misguided focus on quantity over quality: high workload pressure and perceptions of career development expectations can limit research quality, especially for academic career track staff and PhDs;
- High competition for (international) research talent;
- Overemphasis on transdisciplinary research might disrupt balance with strength of disciplinary knowledge;
- Decline of societal value for science may pose future threats to funding and relevance;
- Value for engaged scholarship takes time, and can result in less publications, which might be perceived as a negative by peer institutions who do not hold the same values.

3.7.2

Strategic Priorities for MBE

MBE Strategic Priorities (2025 – 2030)

1. Strengthen the MBE “core concepts”
2. Structural Embedding of Collaboration
3. Make the Next Step in the Six Faculty Themes
4. Invest in External Strategic Communication and Visibility.
5. Keep Balance in our Transdisciplinary Position
6. Continue to Strengthen PhD Support and Talent Identification
7. Reward and Recognize Engaged Scholarship
8. Execute our Strategic Personnel Plan

Over the past four years, MBE has moved beyond a collection of strong individual researchers and now functions as a Centre of Expertise recognised by peers and societal partners across the key faculty themes. Our next strategic step is to evolve from a Centre of Expertise to a Centre of Excellence by strengthening a shared intellectual core, structurally embedding collaborations, and aligning people, partnerships, and platforms around a coherent MBE research paradigm.

Through these strategies, our overall goal is to position MBE as the institute stakeholders turn to when facing complex management questions in the built environment.

1) Strengthen the MBE “core concepts”

One weakness is the lack of a clearly articulated theoretical basis for «Management in the Built Environment.» We therefore prioritise the synthesis of what MBE is and does, by articulating a coherent conceptual framework that positions MBE as a bridge discipline connecting governance, organisation, design, and societal transitions across scales. Our strategy is to make explicit the shared paradigms, core concepts, and methodological commitments of MBE. We will clarify how disciplinary depth and transdisciplinary integration reinforce each other. A tangible outcome of this effort could be a collective synthesis product such as a foundational book or framework publication.

Doing this will help reinforce how MBE research operates in a shared paradigm, how sections complement one another, and what is required to work together effectively. By both strengthening the “home base” and the “core concepts,” we reduce dependence on individuals, something critical given the challenges we face with loss of staff capacity and expertise due to pending retirements.

2) Structural embedding of collaboration

MBE's strong tradition of industry collaboration and societal partnerships is a core strength, but the SWOT analysis shows that these collaborations still depend too heavily on individuals rather than durable structures. Our strategy is therefore to further institutionalise long-standing collaborations through formal framework agreements, shared laboratories, and/or recurring research partnerships with both societal and academic partners. The success of SKG demonstrates the value of structurally embedded collaboration in providing continuity, shared ownership, and visibility beyond individual projects; we aim to replicate and adapt this model in other thematic areas where MBE already has critical mass. This also includes strengthening and expanding academic collaborations across TU Delft faculties (e.g., civil engineering, technology policy and management, industrial design, and computer science), and with external partners such as UCL Bartlett, the IDEA League, and other strategic university networks. Institutionalisation is not viewed as a one-off effort but as an ongoing strategy of network building, maintenance, and renewal, ensuring that collaborations remain relevant as societal challenges evolve.

To do this may require rethinking capacity. Networks and coalitions require active management, something which takes time and capacity. Permanent or temporary staff with project management skill sets are in high demand. There might be a need to rethink how best to support such structural positions.

3) Make the next step forward in the six Faculty Themes

MBE has deliberately aligned its research activities with the six Faculty Themes, using them as a shared framing for societal relevance and interdisciplinary collaboration. Building on this alignment, our next strategic step is to move from thematic participation to thematic leadership by identifying a clear, MBE-specific development trajectory. For example, we already see the following opportunities:

Sustainable Urbanisation: positioning housing more explicitly as a core disciplinary domain, integrating governance, finance, design, construction, and management perspectives to address housing affordability, quality, and long-term urban resilience.

Heritage with Future Values: MBE sees alignment in this theme with our ongoing work on values, including non-monetary valuation, sustainable finance, and ethical values (e.g., reducing inequality, ethics of AI, etc.). In the future years, MBE seeks to position «Values» as a core analytical and design dimension of the built environment. We would like MBE to be the home for research on how societal, ethical, and economic values are articulated, negotiated, and embedded.

Digitalisation + AI: Building on its strong sociotechnical foundation, MBE can further develop research lines on data interaction (e.g., human–machine interaction and human–data interaction), data governance (e.g., data spaces, digital autonomy) and the ethical embedding of values in digital systems for the built environment.

Circularity: Moving from learning about circularity to research focusing on embedding circularity as a normal practice in the built environment and construction industry.

4) Invest in external strategic communication and visibility

The SWOT analysis identifies MBE's limited online and social media presence as a weakness, while highlighting a clear opportunity to increase external visibility and demonstrate societal impact. Now that internal alignment in the department is stronger, we can therefore turn to our external communication strategy. We will invest in a coherent and proactive communication strategy that clearly conveys MBE's research identity, societal relevance, and integration of research and education. This includes refreshing the MBE website and strengthening our social media presence in line with a shared visual and narrative identity.

In parallel, we will adopt a more proactive approach to science communication as part of our Open Science strategy. Initiatives such as BK Resilient Neighbourhoods show how focused communication can successfully connect research to public debate and practice. This can include engaging more visibly in societal debates through public-facing outputs, open-access publications, open datasets, and more accessible dissemination formats than traditional journal publications.

To do this, we will align with BK Communications to ensure consistency in faculty-level strategic messaging. We will also activate our large alumni network, who can be actively engaged as ambassadors for MBE research and education.

5) Keep balance in our transdisciplinary position

MBE feels that transdisciplinary research is «in our nature». While advancing transdisciplinary research, MBE also needs to explicitly safeguard our disciplinary depth in topics of the built environment. We can therefore ensure methodological rigour and a strong theoretical foundation alongside societal engagement. This balance will be reflected in hiring and development strategies by recruiting scholars who combine disciplinary excellence with the capacity to operate across science, policy, and practice.

At the same time, MBE can contribute from a place of strength to the ongoing conversation about transdisciplinary research across higher education in the Netherlands and internationally. For example, by connecting further with emerging groups such as the Nationaal Expertise Centrum Transdisciplinair werken (NECTR), or by setting forth definitional and methodological positions on the “MBE way” of doing transdisciplinary research.

6) Continue to strengthen PhD support and talent identification

At the PhD level, MBE will continue to invest in structured mentoring, leadership development, and career planning, preparing candidates not only as academic researchers but as knowledge brokers capable of operating across science, policy, and practice. By explicitly training researchers in the «MBE way», we hope to strengthen research quality and produce PhD graduates committed to societal relevance and long-term success both within and beyond academia.

MBE finds limited connection in the talent pipeline from MBE MSc track to PhD research, which is a missed opportunity for talent identification. MBE will actively strengthen connections between MSc programmes, summer school, and PhD recruitment. One key lever will be the renewed graduation studios, which can be used more

strategically as talent-identification and thematic alignment mechanisms, while also exposing MSc students to ongoing, state-of-the-art research and current PhD students who can act as mentors.

7) Reward and recognise engaged scholarship

MBE has a tradition of engaged scholarship. In the coming years, MBE will strengthen recognition of this approach by explicitly valuing time-intensive transdisciplinary and societal research activities in performance assessments, promotion criteria, and career development (e.g., for academic career track (ACT) staff). We intend to specifically discourage approaches that could be considered «extractive» from partners. To reduce pressure on traditional academic trajectories, MBE will continue to develop and legitimise diversified research career paths, with little to no emphasis on metrics such as H-Index and citation counts. By aligning recruitment, evaluation, and reward structures with this balanced approach, we can remain true to our own values and produce high-quality research while sustaining long-term societal impact and avoiding unnecessarily high work pressure for research staff.

8) Execute our Strategic Personnel Plan

One pressing and critical risk (as identified in the SWOT analysis) is losing key disciplinary knowledge due to upcoming retirements. This is further complicated by structural budget constraints that limit staff replacement. This poses a direct threat to research continuity and to MBE's ability to balance strong disciplinary foundations with transdisciplinary engagement. Our succession planning therefore requires deliberate and strategic choices about which core competencies must be safeguarded and renewed; difficult choices will need to be made. Through a series of workshops, we have already engaged in a structured process of strategic personnel planning (see Case Study 1). Priority will be given to positions that anchor MBE's theoretical core, support long-term collaboration structures, and sustain PhD supervision capacity. This proactive approach is our main strategy to maintain research quality under increasing workload and funding pressures.

Case Studies MBE

B.3.1

How MBE Developed a New Mission Statement and Strategic Personnel Plan

During the 2022 Research Assessment, MBE formulated its mission as follows: *“To theoretically understand governing, organising and managing in the built environment to design interventions for societal challenges and transitions.”*

In its report, the evaluation committee questioned the clarity and coherence of this mission. While acknowledging the presence of many strong individual researchers within MBE, the committee noted that the department lacked a clear and unified profile. As they stated, “from an outsider perspective, it is difficult to identify the unique selling proposition of the department.”

In response to this feedback, MBE initiated a process to revise and strengthen its mission statement. Beginning in 2022, the department undertook a two-year trajectory that concluded in 2024 with the adoption of the mission statement. Throughout this period, all MBE staff were actively involved through ten dedicated meetings and regular email updates, ensuring broad engagement and shared ownership.

The revision process was supported by two consultancy firms. BeeImprove facilitated the initial phase, organising six sessions focused on assessing the existing mission statement and identifying areas for improvement. Building on the outcomes of these sessions, HollandSpoor led the subsequent phase, incorporating insights from MBE’s stakeholders and working towards the formulation of a renewed and more externally resonant mission.

The resulting mission statement not only addresses the committee’s critique but also plays a central role in the department’s strategic personnel plan, providing a shared guiding framework for future research, collaboration, and development within MBE.

FIG. 3.17 Advertisement for the MBE PhD day

FIG. 3.18 Researchers discussing together with their supervisors struggles during the PhD process

B.3.2

How MBE Refocused on Social Safety and PhD Researcher Development

Beginning in 2023, MBE began to engage in structured discussions with a representative group of PhD students to foster a supportive and transparent research culture for our PhD candidates. Together with the department manager, this group developed the MBE PhD Manual, an extensive guide designed to clarify procedures, expectations, and available support throughout the PhD trajectory.

In parallel, the MBE Daily Board approved the MBE PhD Guideline, which consolidates all essential information concerning workplace arrangements, travel, courses, and the PhD defence procedure. This guideline applies equally to all PhD categories: employed PhD candidates, scholarship PhDs, and industry-based PhDs.

In 2024, a major concern across the TU Delft community was the topic of social safety for researchers and students. These developments prompted a series of staff meetings and informal hallway conversations within MBE, during which it became clear that PhD candidates needed stronger empowerment – particularly in understanding what it means to be a PhD researcher within the MBE, Faculty of Architecture, and TU Delft context.

In June 2025, we organised the first MBE PhD Day, bringing together PhDs and their supervision teams in an event that aims to strengthen their bonds and improve the experiences and workflow for both PhDs and their supervisors. Using the Game of Unspoken Things (developed by DownSideUp), topics that are not often brought up in casual conversation or supervision meetings were put in the spotlight.

Following recommendations from the PhD representatives, the department further contracted with DownSideUp, a well-known agency that supports academic researchers and contributes to Graduate School training. In early 2025, the first PhD Learning Programme was launched, enrolling ten first-year PhD candidates.

MBE also began intentional dialogue about research culture for all researchers and staff through the initiation of the MBE research forums. The MBE research forums are not for the presentation of information, but instead to facilitate the MBE community in debate, discussion and sharing of tacit knowledge. So far, we have organised eight MBE research forums on key topics such as career progression, publishing ethics, connecting research and education, and AI in research. The MBE research forums serve as an important connecting point between researchers both new and experienced, where we can determine the values and approaches that guide MBE as a cohesive unit together.

In addition to formal initiatives, MBE has continued to place importance on informal community-building activities. Events such as the annual MBE Christmas Lunch, the New Year's Dinner, the Ramadan Iftar gathering, and the department outing help colleagues connect, relax, and support one another. Each section also organises yearly activities for its own staff, contributing to a strong sense of belonging throughout the department.

B.3.3

How MBE Reshaped the Graduation Process to Better Connect Research and Education

Since the study year 2025/2026, the preparation time for the graduation research (until the kick-off meeting A1) has been reduced from one semester to one quarter, therefore reducing 5 credits from the overall thesis. This means that students do not have much time to think about a topic for their research. Therefore, MBE chose to offer the students two approaches for their graduation: the research project-based process on the one hand and the exploration-driven process on the other hand. For the research project-based process, MBE prepares a series of topics per graduation theme. These topics are proposed by researchers who work on projects related to the themes. The topics give a brief description of a problem, present a main research question, some sub-questions and some key publications, the responsible supervisor and possibly a second supervisor. About 80% of the students have chosen this option. In the exploration-driven process, students with a clear idea have the possibility to propose a topic themselves. These students need to come well-prepared to the start of the graduation studio and hand in a small proposal beforehand. About 20% of the students choose this option.

A main advantage of this new way of working is that we create an excellent relation between research and education. Most of the topics are related to ongoing research projects in the department, like NWO, NWA, EU or other (externally) funded projects.

This connection has many benefits for the students as well as for the projects. The students experience the advantage of an existing infrastructure for a topic, such as background information, a network of related organisations and specialists, and possibly already generated data. The research projects benefit by having extra research capacity to go deeper into some issues or work on another case.

All graduation topics (both research project-based and exploration-driven) are structured at MBE Graduation according to the following eight themes that represent most of the research domains of the department:

- Circular transformations: strategies, tools, and processes;
- Human-centred sustainable transitions;
- Inclusive communities – “Civic transformation, innovation, vision for inclusive communities”;
- Gamechangers: Changing the regime in the architecture, engineering and construction (AEC) industry in sustainability transitions;
- Tackling the housing crises;
- Value and Valuation;
- Area development: Advancing sustainable area development – balancing values, actors and interests through urban or rural development;
- Building the Future: Entrepreneurial Responses to Societal Challenges.

The graduation theses are generally guided by two researchers and offer the students three joint meetings during the preparation period with a focus on (1) research problem, (2) literature review and (3) research methods. We chose this approach so that students not only learn from their supervisors but also learn from each other. They stimulate each other at the start by exchanging practicalities and also provide social support in the process. In the past, this approach has proven its success both in the success rates of graduation projects and the throughput time of students.

Altogether, this new approach to the graduation process has resulted in stronger connections, in line with our approach to connect research and education. For example, the PhD students and postdocs in the department that are part of these research projects are increasingly involved as second supervisor or additional reader in the graduation projects. This generates more supervision capacity in the department, and the PhD students develop supervision expertise. The Graduate School offers doctoral education that is required for the PhDs to take up the supervision role. An example are two graduation projects that recently started on ‘renovation passports’ related to the Horizon Europe project DemoBLog and the NWO project Renodat. The PhD of DemoBLog and PostDoc of Renodat are involved with the supervision and will benefit from the data collection of the students. One of the students will do an internship at the Ministry of VRO, which is part of the network. The other student is doing a dual graduation project in Geomatics and the supervisors there are also part of the Renodat consortium.

FIG. 3.19 The transdisciplinary research environment of the RE-DWELL project

B.3.4

How MBE Takes a Transdisciplinary and Regional Perspective

One of the distinctive strengths of research at MBE is its transdisciplinary character. MBE researchers integrate insights from multiple governance levels and spatial scales, working closely with a wide range of stakeholders, including fellow academics, policy-makers, industry representatives, and residents. As a result, much of MBE’s work is not confined to a single spatial entity but adopts an integrative perspective.

For example, between 2020 and 2024, MBE collaborated with two early-stage researchers (Alex Fernandez and Tijn Croon) in the MSCA-ITN RE-DWELL network, which examines housing affordability and sustainability across various European countries. The network adopts a multi-scalar perspective, ranging from the housing unit to the regional level, and brings together physical and social structures as well as diverse scientific viewpoints (architectural, urban, social, economic, political, environmental, and governance) in a genuine transdisciplinary research environment.

Another clear example of an integrative and transdisciplinary approach is the H2020 Ruralization project (2019–2023). This project explored emerging rural trends, mapped young people’s “dream futures,” and examined practices that support rural newcomers, new farming entrants, and farm successors. It analysed rules, policies, and on-the-ground practices, while also launching pilot actions to improve land access. The project has had substantial impact on policymaking and has inspired follow-up initiatives, including the EU-funded FLIARA project (Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas), in which MBE is also a partner.

A third example is the Resilient Delta initiative, in which Zac Taylor from MBE collaborates with researchers from Erasmus University Rotterdam and Erasmus MC. This initiative focuses on delta regions, which are home to more than two-thirds of the world’s largest cities and among the areas most acutely affected by climate change and socioeconomic pressures. Using the Dutch delta as a living lab, the initiative’s transdisciplinary research supports delta regions worldwide in becoming more resilient to challenges such as rising water levels, extreme weather, pollution, poverty, inequality, and technological change. Through partnerships with companies, governments, and civil society, the initiative develops actionable and scalable solutions, policies, innovations, and practical tools to address critical issues in urban delta regions.

B.3.5

How MBE is Helping to Solve the Housing Crisis

TU Delft has a long-standing tradition of excellence in housing research and its application to societal needs, both nationally and internationally. The MBE Department has continued this decades-long tradition through its expertise in housing systems, institutions, governance, development, and management. In a global and national context marked by acute and increasingly complex housing challenges, robust housing research has become ever more critical. Building on its strong foundations, MBE has steadily developed new conceptual and methodological frameworks to address this complexity.

The department is widely recognised for its leadership in housing systems research, with several MBE scholars regularly providing policy advice at national and international levels. Professor Peter Boelhouwer, for example, is a leading authority on housing market developments in the Netherlands and Europe. Since 2012, he has directed the Expertise Center for Property Value, a collaboration with Statistics Netherlands (CBS) that produces quarterly indicators such as the VEH Market Indicator and the Homeownership Market Monitor. These datasets form a vital empirical foundation for research conducted by PhD candidates and master’s students.

MBE researchers have also been at the forefront of emerging fields within housing studies. The Co-Lab Research Group, founded in 2018 by Dr Darinka Czischke, provides a platform for scholars working on collective and self-organised housing models.

Among its key outputs is the Co-Lab Mapping Project, an interactive data-visualisation platform documenting collaborative housing initiatives across Europe. In addition, the Centre for Comparative Housing Research, led by Professor Marja Elsinga, brings together MBE researchers engaged in housing research across diverse thematic and international perspectives.

Researchers involved in these initiatives have successfully secured competitive national and European funding to address pressing contemporary housing issues. Examples include Horizon Europe projects such as Re-Dwell (affordable and sustainable housing) and UPLIFT (housing young people in Europe), as well as an NWO Vidi grant awarded to Dr Darinka Czischke for the project «InCommon: Reconceptualizing Individual and Collective Housing Preferences,» which investigates latent demand for collaborative housing. MBE has also hosted several self-funded PhD candidates from outside Europe, whose work addresses housing challenges in diverse global contexts (e.g., capabilities approach in South Korea; collaborative housing in Chile; co-residence strategies in Latin America; incremental housing in South Africa).

MBE has made significant contributions to scholarship through peer-reviewed publications. Notable among these is a book chapter about long-term developments in housing policy and research, co-authored by Dr Marietta Haffner, which offers inspiration for emerging researchers and policymakers. The chapter on housing highlights the increasingly intertwined social and economic dimensions of housing and elucidates its complex role as a human right, a consumption good, and an investment asset (Dewilde & Haffner). In addition, Professor Marja Elsinga serves as Associate Editor-in-Chief of the *Encyclopaedia of Housing and Home*, a leading international reference work.

The societal impact of MBE's research is further reinforced by the active engagement of its members in supervisory boards of Dutch housing associations (e.g., Marja Elsinga, Gerard van Bortel, Vincent Gruis), advisory boards to national and international organisations (e.g., Dutch Ministry of Housing, Dutch Union of Tenants, Cooplink, European Commission, European Parliament), and industry partners (e.g., Inbo).

This rich and diverse research expertise is also transmitted to new generations of students through the recently established MBE Graduation Lab "Solving the Housing Crisis." This initiative enables master's students to connect their graduation projects to ongoing departmental research or to pursue independent topics aligned with contemporary housing challenges.

How MBE uses a Multi-scalar Approach to Managing Transitions in the Built Environment

The Department of Management in the Built Environment (MBE) is uniquely positioned to adopt a multi-scalar approach to addressing societal transitions that shape and are shaped by the built environment. Challenges such as affordable housing provision, energy and water transitions, and circularity require integrated governance, organisational, and management responses across projects, property portfolios, and urban areas.

MBE combines extensive expertise in governance arrangements, organisational approaches, and management instruments to translate theory into actionable practices, bridging the policy–practice gap. By operating across multiple scales, the department develops solutions for managing complexity, uncertainty, and interdependence in built environment transitions.

Recent projects exemplify this multi-scalar orientation. In CHARM (Circular Housing Asset Renovation & Management), MBE researchers engaged with the “twin transition” challenge, integrating digitalisation with sustainability in housing renovation and management. This work also led to the establishment of the Digital Circular Economy Lab (DiCE Lab), a cross-institutional knowledge exchange network with ETH Zürich.

In infrastructure, MBE researchers apply multi-scalar approaches to maintenance and replacement challenges while enhancing climate resilience in built structures. Projects such as SUBLIME and URBIQUAY explore governance and management strategies that link asset-level decisions to broader urban and regional resilience objectives.

To extend societal impact, research insights are translated into professional learning forums that upskill practitioners in navigating transition uncertainties. Examples include TransCiBo, which focuses on circularity in the built environment, and Stepping Out, which promotes deep transdisciplinary and interprofessional collaboration.

MBE’s work also informs policy development, combining actionable recommendations with in-depth understanding of real-world practices. Initiatives such as The New Normal illustrate how research contributes to embedding sustainable and circular principles in built environment governance.

This multi-scalar perspective is embedded in MBE’s research-informed education. The Master’s track in Management in the Built Environment equips students with broad knowledge and skills for managing projects, portfolios, and urban development. The Graduation Studio, where students undertake their final thesis projects, aligns with ongoing research and addresses contemporary challenges such as inclusive neighbourhoods, sustainable housing, energy transitions, and the creation of new societal values in the built environment.

References

- Andres, L., Bryson, J. R., Ersoy, A., & Reardon, L. (Eds.). (2024). *Pandemic Recovery?: Reframing and Rescaling Societal Challenges*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Ashrafi S, Vrijhoef R and Wamelink H (2025) Circular renovation in construction at the meso scale: a systematic literature review and framework development. *Front. Built Environ.* 11:1649637. doi: 10.3389/fbuil.2025.1649637
- Ashrafi, S., Wamelink, H., & Vrijhoef, R. (2025). Circular renovation of urban infrastructures: A multi-project perspective. In *CIB Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, p. 213).
- Bingöl, C. K., Wang, T., Ersoy, A., & van Bueren, E. (2025). The Potential of AI in Information Provision in Energy-Efficient Renovations: A Narrative Review of Literature. *Urban Planning*, 10.
- Çetin, S., Gruis, V., & Straub, A. (2022). Digitalization for a circular economy in the building industry: Multiple-case study of Dutch social housing organizations. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling Advances*, 15, 200110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcradv.2022.200110>
- Çetin, S., Gruis, V., & Straub, A. (2022). Digitalization for a circular economy in the building industry: Multiple-case study of Dutch social housing organizations. *Resources, conservation & recycling advances*, 15, 200110.
- Čustović, I., Cao, J., Hall, D. M., & Wamelink, H. (2025a). Enhancing situation awareness of construction managers using human-centered digital twins. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 67, 103557.
- Čustović, I., Cao, J., Soman, R. (2025b). *Agents in Construction (AiC) Ontology - Version 1.0*
- Czischke, D., Peute, M., & Brysch, S. (2023). *Together: Towards collaborative living*. TU Delft OPEN Publishing.
- Czischke, D., & Moons, C. (2025). The clustered living approach in the Netherlands. In *Collaborative Housing, Ageing and Social Care* (pp. 176-195). Policy Press.
- Dąbrowski, M., Van den Berghe, K., Williams, J., & van Bueren, E. (Eds.). (2025). *Going circular: unlocking the potential of regions and cities to drive the circular economy transition*. Taylor & Francis.
- Dewilde, C. and M. Haffner (2022) Long-term developments in housing policy and research, In: Nelson, K., Nieuwenhuis, R. and M.A. Yerkes (eds.) (2022) *Social Policies in Changing European Societies. Research Agendas for the 21st century*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- De Wolf, C., Çetin, S., & Bocken, N. (Eds.). (2024). *A circular built environment in the digital age* (Vol. 10, pp. 978-3). Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- Eikelenboom, M., & van Marrewijk, A. (2023). Creating points of opportunity in sustainability transitions: Reflective interventions in inter-organizational collaboration. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 48, 100748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2023.100748>
- Esteban, T. A. O. E., Heijmeskamp, T., & Sadjad, M. S. (2024). Where We Stand: Risk Perceptions on Changing Neighborhoods in South Rotterdam. *Atlantis*, 35(1), 45.
- Gentili, M., & Hoekstra, J. (2025). The Position of Young Adults on the Amsterdam Housing Market. Combining the Housing Pathway and the Capability Approach. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 1-24.
- Greco, A. (2024). Changing constellations of hybridity through the phases of sustainable business model innovation. *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 2024(1), 54BP. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMPROC.2024.54bp>
- Greco, A., & Berti, M. (2025). Revisiting action research: Leveraging paradox for responsible theoretical and practical impacts. *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 2025(1), 7BP. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMPROC.2025.7bp>
- Hamida, M. B., Jylhä, T., Remøy, H., & Gruis, V. (2023). Circular building adaptability and its determinants—A literature review. *International Journal of Building Pathology and Adaptation*, 41(6), 47-69.
- van Heel, L., Herweijer, M., & van Oel, C. (2024). Trade-offs in Evidence Based Design: 'the Patient Door Debate'. In I. V. L. A. (Ed.), *Effects of Design on Health and Wellbeing* (Vol. 319, pp. 266-279). IOS Press BV. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SHTI240949>
- Hobma, F. A., & Jong, P. (2022). An instrumental approach to planning and development law in the Netherlands. *Instituut voor Bouwrecht*.
- Hwang, S. A., Çetin, S., Visscher, H., & Straub, A. (2025). Advancing energy renovations through digitalisation: A critical review of EU policies and instruments. *Energy and Buildings*, 336, 115627.
- Ishaak, F., Ouweland, P., & Remoy, H. (2024). Constructing Limited-Revisable and Stable CPPIs for Small Domains. *Journal of Official Statistics*, 40(3), 380-408.
- Janssen, C. (2024). Developing places for human capabilities: Understanding how social sustainability goals are governed into urban development projects. *A+ BE| Architecture and the Built Environment*, (01), 1-260.
- Kamphuis, S., Soltani, P., Koops, L., & Hermans, M. (2022). Learning for value creation in project alliance. In *ARCOM Working Papers Compendium* (pp. 132–139). Association of Researchers in Construction Management. Available from <https://www.arcom.ac.uk>.
- Kassem, M., Maciel, A., & Hall, D. M. (Eds.). (2025). *Blockchain, Smart Contracts and Distributed Ledger Technologies in the Built Environment: Key concepts, technologies, and applications*. The Institution of Engineering and Technology.
- Kimhur, B. (2022). Housing justice as expansion of people's capabilities for housing: Proposal for principles of housing policy and evaluation of housing inequality. *A+ BE| Architecture and the Built Environment*, (23), 1-214.
- Koolwijk, J. S. J., Kevdzija, M., van Oel, C. J., Vujovic, M., van Heel, M. E., & Van Goor, H. (2025, June 9–11). Towards user-centered architecture: Teaching post-occupancy evaluation in design education in Delft and Vienna [Conference poster]. *European Healthcare and Design Conference (EHD2025)*, Royal College of Physicians, London, United Kingdom. <https://www.europeanhealthcaredesign.eu/>
- Kowaltowski, D. C., da Silva, V. G., Van Oel, C., Granja, A. D., Muianga, E. A. D., Kabisch, S., ... & Freeke, A. (2024). Living labs for user empowerment and value delivery in social housing upgrading processes. *Habitat International*, 145, 103019.
- van Laar, B., Greco, A., Remøy, H., & Gruis, V. (2024). What matters when?—An integrative literature review on decision criteria in different stages of the adaptive reuse process. *Developments in the Built Environment*, 18, 100439.
- Leendertse, J., Smit, H., Wamelink, H., & Hermans, M. (2025). The pilot trap: Interactions between sustainable startups and clients in the built environment. In *Proceedings of the 40th Annual ARCOM Conference*.
- van Marrewijk, A., & van den Ende, L. (2022). Shaping interorganizational strategic projects through power relations and strategic practices. *International Journal of Project Management*, 40(4), 426-438.
- Mazzarella, C. (2024). Haven [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Wd4T4pJS3BBY>

- Mlecnik, E., Qian, Q., Straub, A., Ersoy, A., Remoy, H., Gruis, V., ... & Roeling, M. (2024). Integrating environmental sustainability in construction and real estate management education. In *Sustainability in Business Education, Research and Practices* (pp. 159-175). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Molaei, M., Koops, L., & Hermans, M. (2022). Evaluating the procurement documents of Dutch water boards portfolio: A step towards more reliable public clients. In A. Tutesigensi & C. J. Neilson (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 38th Annual ARCOM Conference* (pp. 114-123). Association of Researchers in Construction Management.
- van Oel, C., Benning, C., Mukhtar, H., Freeke, A., Zuiderveld, D., Eisemann, E., & Koolwijk, J. (2023). Sociale innovatie door communicatie in Virtual Reality (VR) [Social innovation through communication in Virtual Reality (VR)]. *Real Estate Research Quarterly*, 22(4).
- van Overbeek, R., Ishaak, F., Geurts, E., & Remøy, H. (2024). The added value of environmental certification in the Dutch office market. *Journal of European Real Estate Research*.
- Pacheco-Torgal, F., Colangelo, F., Tuladhar, R., Ding, Y., Xin-Yu, Z., & Koutamanis, A. (Eds.). (2025). *Advances in Construction and Demolition Waste Recycling: Digital Technologies, Management, Processing and Environmental Assessment*. Elsevier.
- Remøy, H. T., van Bortel, G. A., Heurkens, E. W. T. M., & van Venrooij, R. G. A. M. (2025). Adaptive Reuse for Housing.
- Ricci, D., Konstantinou, T., & Visscher, H. (2025). Making energy renovations equitable: A literature review of decision-making criteria for a just energy transition in residential buildings. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 122, 104016.
- Ruijsink, S & M. Nefs (2025) 'Unusual suspects' als middel om diversiteit in gebiedsontwikkeling te versterken, gebiedsontwikkeling.nu
- Schraven, D., Zisopoulos, F. K., Dong, L., & de Jong, M. (2025). A Conceptual Framework for Inclusive Circular Urban Waste Management Systems. In *The Inclusive Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities for Urban Innovation* (pp. 69-90). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- van Uden, M., van Marrewijk, A., Eikelenboom, M., Brouwer, C., Wamelink, H., Heurkens, E., & van Bueren, E. (under review). Impactful projects: Forward co-creation of academics and practitioners in circular construction transition.
- Van den Berghe, K. B. J., De Vil, T., Eggermont, K., & Noels, G. (2025). Investerende Antwerpse chemie afhankelijk van Nederlandse basisindustrie. *Economisch Statistische Berichten*, 110(4847), 311-313.
- Van den Berghe, K., Louw, E., Pliakis, F., & Daamen, T. (2023). When "port-out-city-in" becomes a strategy: is the port-city interface conflict in Amsterdam an observation or a self-fulfilling prophecy?. *Maritime Economics & Logistics*, 25(2), 330-350.
- Wamelink, J. W. F., & Peeters, T. (2025). Het Nieuwe Normaal: het meten van circulariteit in de bouw. *Real Estate Research Quarterly*, 2025(1), 3-13.
- Zhang, J. J., Danivska, V., Schraven, D., & Remøy, H. (2025). A historical narrative of value theory in economics and appraisal. *Journal of Property Research*, 1-22.
- van Zoest, S., & Daamen, T. A. (2024). Explaining Value Capture Implementation in New York, London, and Copenhagen: Negotiating Distributional Effects. *Urban Affairs Review*, 60(5), 1349-1381

Urbanism advances knowledge on how to adapt the built environment to societal and environmental changes.

Cronestein, known for being a green child-friendly neighbourhood, is situated near the Leiden Lammenschans train station

(Image: Nanda Sluijsmans, <https://www.flickr.com/photos/handasluijsmans/54687922814/in/album-72177720326066702>)

Urbanism

The mission of Urbanism is to advance, share and apply knowledge on how to adapt the built environment to societal and environmental changes; and to apply contextual design, planning and engineering strategies and interventions with impact for a better society.

Summary

Sustainable urbanisation, climate adaptation, circularity, healthy cities and digitalisation are the core themes our faculty embraced as relevant societal themes for research and education. The Department of Urbanism adopts them as the foundation for excellent scholarship and research. Our **mission**: to advance, share, and apply knowledge on how to adapt the built environment to societal and environmental changes, and to apply contextual design, planning, and engineering strategies with impact for a better society. The Urbanism research programme is shaped by our understanding that the quality of the urban environment is crucial to societies' social, economic, and environmental performance, and to a more resilient and fairer urban environment.

In the research assessments of 2016 and 2022, the research quality of the Department of Urbanism was labelled as 'excellent'. Urbanism has an international reputation for academic research, scholarship, and education, grounded in knowledge-based, design-oriented, and multiscale work, in which landscape architecture, urban design, and planning closely collaborate with engineers, data scientists, sociologists, geographers, and ecologists. Urbanism is committed to socially relevant research, exemplified by our involvement in design projects and policy development, the development and implementation of practical tools and methods, and our leadership and participation in (inter)national networks. A high level of scientific output in the form of journal articles, books, exhibitions and datasets, and their use, as well as the high number of prestigious personal grants and awarded NWO and Horizon 2020 funding, testify to our premium research.

Our research is organised around five cross-cutting themes, involving staff from across Urbanism: **Delta Urbanism, Inclusive Urbanism, Green Urbanism/Bio-Cities, Data-supported Urbanism, and Integrative Transitional Urbanism**. These themes closely align with the faculty's research themes. We are dedicated to open science, disseminating research through publications and datasets in open formats. Strengthening a safe academic culture, in which research integrity and inclusivity are key elements, is part of our ongoing effort to enhance the conditions for a thriving urbanism community and PhD culture. Complementary to faculty HR policy, we are continuously working on talent management of existing staff, developing leadership, increasing cultural diversity, and improving female representation among senior staff.

In the coming years, the department will consolidate the research programme to remain world-leading in design-related scholarship and in socially relevant, impactful research for the understanding, planning, and development of sustainable urban landscapes. We will develop a tailored **research funding strategy** that combines the strengths of individual and section expertise with efforts to diversify funding sources and respond to increasing competition for funds and the threat of fragmentation of staff efforts. We will continue to strengthen the Delft Approach to Urbanism as part of a wider envisioning process on the role of **Urbanism in the 21st century**. To foster disciplinary breadth, depth and innovation, we will nourish a **fair, diverse and inclusive academic culture** where everyone can excel and where talent is rewarded. We will consolidate the strategies we recently implemented to improve the **efficiency of the**

Urbanism PhD programme. We will expand **co-creative, transdisciplinary modes of working** by engaging communities, civil society, governmental and non-traditional partners as active contributors in our research and design process. Further **refining open and collaborative research practices** to make publications, data, software, and other academic outputs available to the world will be the cornerstone of our engagement and impact.

4.2

Introduction

Sustainable urbanisation, climate adaptation, circularity, healthy cities and digitalisation are the core societal themes the faculty has embraced, guiding its research and education. The Department of Urbanism adopts them as the foundation for developing excellent scholarship and societally relevant research. **This is reflected in our mission: to advance, share, and apply knowledge on how to adapt the built environment to societal and environmental changes, and to apply contextual design, planning, and engineering strategies and interventions with impact for a better society.** The Urbanism research programme is shaped by our understanding that the quality of the urban environment is crucial to societies' social, economic, and environmental performance and to achieving a more sustainable and fairer urban environment.

In the research assessments of 2016 and 2022, the research quality of the Department of Urbanism was labelled as 'excellent'. Urbanism boasts a world-class international reputation for its academic research, scholarship, and education on space and society, founded on the Delft Approach to Urbanism. This approach is knowledge-based, design-oriented and multiscale, with disciplines such as landscape architecture, urban design and planning closely collaborating with engineers, data scientists, sociologists, geographers and ecologists. Urbanism is a practice that addresses contemporary challenges by integrating design, technology, and science. We take this integrated approach to the international arena in partnership with some of the world's leading universities.

The core of the Department of Urbanism in Delft comprises six sections (see Fig. 4.1). These sections include Urban Design, Landscape Architecture, Spatial Planning & Strategy, Urban Studies, Urban Data Science, and Environmental Technology & Design. **Urban Design** concerns the analysis, typological understanding, transformation processes and design of the physical form of existing and new urban areas and their future adaptation to global challenges. **Landscape Architecture** focuses on knowledge acquisition, strategy development and design exploration of landscape compositions and systems in the built environment. **Spatial Planning & Strategy** is concerned with formulating, implementing and evaluating policies, visions, strategies, plans and programmes for urban regions. **Urban Studies** examines the relationships between people and places at various spatial scales, ranging from neighbourhoods to cities and regions. The research focuses on a better understanding of how neighbourhoods, cities and regions develop, how different spatial configurations and structures emerge (within and between cities) and how these configurations affect socio-economic outcomes for people across spatial scales.

FIG. 4.1 The Department of Urbanism and its constituent sections

Urban Data Science focuses on the technologies and governance models underpinning geographical information systems (GIS) and spatial data infrastructures. It aims to design, develop, and implement better systems to model cities, buildings, and landscapes in 3D for urban applications, as well as the governance mechanisms employed in concepts such as the 'open city' and 'the city as a service'. **Environmental Technology & Design** focuses its research on the relationship and integration between engineering and spatial design in the sustainable development of neighbourhoods, cities and regions, addressing environmental challenges arising from the interaction of people and natural systems.

The six sections are the basis for **inter- and transdisciplinary¹, context-driven, problem/solution-focused research and education**. Together, they substantiate the Delft approach to Urbanism. Urbanism involves engineering, social science, and environmental science methods as operative instruments for our research, as well as the development and application of advanced social and urban data science and geospatial information technologies to improve urban environments. Besides the development of the disciplines themselves, there is a strong emphasis on the interaction between these fields in terms of theories, methods and techniques, as well as their application via concepts, strategies and spatial interventions exemplified by five research themes: **Delta Urbanism, Inclusive Urbanism, Green Urbanism/Bio-cities, Data-supported Urbanism**, and (more recently) **Integrative Transitional Urbanism** as elaborated through case studies in the Annex. These research themes are closely aligned with the faculty-wide themes of sustainable urbanisation, climate adaptation, circularity, healthy cities, and digitalisation. The breadth of disciplines represented in the Urbanism department and the fruits of their interdisciplinary collaboration become operational through these themes, enabling us to align our ambitions and research initiatives while bolstering innovation and collaboration. The Urbanism sections collaborate across the five themes; each of them is active in at least two overarching research themes.

At the end of 2025, the department had 285 staff members (204 Full-Time Equivalent, FTE), of which 82 had tenure (66.5 FTE), 70 had a temporary appointment (54.7 FTE), and 136 guests (82.8 FTE) were involved in research, education and organisation. The breakdown of positions, staff development, gender balance, and cultural diversity among research staff is discussed in Paragraph 4.6.

Urbanism is led by a **Management Team (MT)** comprising the department chair, department manager, section leaders, research leader, and education leader. The MT meets every two weeks. Next to the MT, the education and research coordinators from all sections meet regularly in the Daily Boards (DB) for Education and Urbanism Research to discuss education and research affairs. The **DB Research** provides advice and input to the MT's decisions. The research leader serves as the liaison between DB Research and the MT and participates in the Faculty **Research Council**, a collective of research leaders representing the departments.

1

Multidisciplinarity draws on knowledge from different disciplines while remaining within their respective disciplinary limits. Interdisciplinarity analyses, synthesises and harmonises links between disciplines to create a coordinated and coherent whole. Transdisciplinarity is a type of interdisciplinary working, but actively engages societal stakeholders (apart from the scientific community) in co-creating knowledge and solutions.

Mission and Strategic Aims Urbanism 2022-2027

Scope

The mission of Urbanism is to advance, share and apply knowledge on how to adapt the built environment to societal and environmental changes; and to apply contextual design, planning and engineering strategies and interventions with impact for a better society.

Regarding research quality, societal relevance, and viability, we have defined the following strategic aims for the development of our department's research over the period 2022-2027.

Research quality and societal relevance

- Remain world-leading in design-related scholarship and socially relevant and impactful research for the understanding, planning and development of sustainable urban landscapes;
- Cultivate the Delft Approach to Urbanism as a socially and ecologically inclusive approach with a strong link between spatial research and design across scales, based on inter- and transdisciplinary working and employing state-of-the-art digital technology;
- Foster disciplinary breadth, depth and innovation;
- Actively participate in and lead academic and societal networks and engage in strategic collaborations with governmental partners, NGOs and other societal partners;
- Cultivate the relationship between the Urbanism research programme and PhD/MSc education.

Open science

- Stimulate more open and collaborative research practices in which publications, data, software and other types of academic output (when possible) are shared and made available for (re)use, e.g., according to the FAIR principles.

PhD policy and training

- Nurture an Urbanism PhD culture and develop a more efficient Urbanism PhD programme;
- Develop a complementary Urbanism PhD policy and Urbanism-oriented PhD courses.

Academic culture

- Bolster a fair and inclusive academic culture where all members of Urbanism can excel.

Human Resources policy

- Elaborate ways to recruit and retain excellent top talent;
- Continuously build a diverse urbanism community as a precondition for excellence and innovation.

4.3.2

Summary of recommendations of the 2022 research review

Following the self-assessment protocol (SEP), in 2022, an external assessment committee scored Urbanism research. Urbanism received an **excellent** score for **'research quality'** and **'societal relevance'**, as well as a **good** score for **'viability'**. The external assessment committee issued 13 recommendations (in summary):

- 1 Develop a clear ethical protocol for collaborations, data management and sharing instructions in order to maintain an independent and uncompromised research position, if not currently existing;
- 2 Develop research quality policy and indicators in the long term to ensure output volume, diversity and quality; monitor early indicators of potential evolutions; and integrate the critical interpretation of those indicators into executive decisions for the research strategies;
- 3 Continue developing the Delft approach as a distinct school of thought, substantiating it with international benchmark evidence;
- 4 Evaluate the procedures and outcomes of curiosity research;
- 5 Reflect on the role of professors of practice and practice-based research in the research portfolio;
- 6 Formalise onboarding of PhDs in the department organisation to ensure a better start and welcoming work environment;
- 7 If not yet existing, formulate and formalise actions to improve PhD supervision and training and to reduce PhD completion times;

- 8 Develop a specific approach towards representation and inclusion of non-institutional partners within urban research projects and potentially integrate this into the 'Delft approach to urbanism';
- 9 Continue to engage with design practice in general and that of the Netherlands in a mutual learning approach to increase societal relevance;
- 10 Expand and formalise the department's research policy in relation to the faculty-wide themes, in line with the disciplines' claims to the research themes and profit from associated funding streams;
- 11 Identify the strategic aims for the next evaluation period and translate these into KPIs to establish and share insights on the performance of the ongoing research, the department's strengths and its impact in the domain;
- 12 Develop and implement a broader strategy to improve diversity of staff (especially for full professors) while finding the right balance between seeking (international) diversity and keeping grounded within the Dutch context;
- 13 Identify and address the financial challenge in order to maintain a viable research context and high-performance levels.

In response to the Research Assessment Report (2023), the **Executive Board of TU Delft** provided further guidance on recommendations from the assessment committee. First, the Executive Board confirmed **recommendation 3**, to substantiate the 'Delft approach to Urbanism' with international benchmark evidence. Second, the Executive Board reiterated the need to find the right balance between seeking (international) staff diversity and keeping grounded within the Dutch context (**recommendation 12**). The next Paragraph describes how we have operationalised and attempted to achieve the strategic aims, as well as how we have responded to the recommendations of the 2022 assessment committee.

4.4

Strategy (including the strategic process)

- Remain world-leading in design-related scholarship and socially relevant and impactful research for the understanding, planning and development of sustainable urban landscapes;
- Cultivate the Delft Approach to Urbanism as a socially and ecologically inclusive approach with a strong link between spatial research and design across scales, based on inter- and transdisciplinary working and employing state-of-the-art digital technology;
- Foster disciplinary breadth, depth and innovation;
- Actively participate in and lead academic and societal networks and engage in strategic collaborations with governmental partners, NGOs and other societal partners;
- Cultivate the relationship between the Urbanism research programme and PhD/MSc education.

Urbanism is a research- and design-led department. Our research programme has focused, whenever possible, on curiosity-driven research relevant to society, extensive engagement with many stakeholders, and a strong connection to urban and regional design. We have maintained high levels of research quality and societal impact through the widespread recognition and use of our research outputs, both within and beyond academia. **National strategic funds** to strengthen research staff (e.g., Sectorplan, Nationale Wetenschapsagenda) and teaching staff (Van Rijn funds), alongside the increase in external research funding, have led to substantial growth in our staff numbers. This has created great opportunities to expand and deepen our research, but it has also raised challenges about the coherence of our research programme.

In response to the recommendations of the Assessment Committee (**no. 3**) and the Executive Board, the Department has taken steps towards further developing the **Delft approach to Urbanism**. With a substantial influx of early-career staff unfamiliar with the historical background of the Delft approach, there is a need to reinforce the approach's resonance. The Department considers the Delft approach to be a living approach, explaining what we do in the context of a university rooted in the Netherlands. It constantly needs development, discussion, and dialogue with staff, societal partners and international peers. In line with the new Faculty's multi-annual plan, our new strategy for substantiating the Delft Approach contains two components. First, we will extend the working group that will coordinate content development (e.g., an edited volume) on the **background, foundations and section-specific elaborations of the approach**, to stimulate conversations on how it moves forward. Second, the Department has started a visioning process on the purpose and meaning of **Urbanism in the 21st century**, specifically engaging new staff members. This process reflects on our lines of thinking, including (but not limited to) the Delft approach to Urbanism.

We have consolidated our current and past success in knowledge utilisation, valorisation and strategic collaborations by continuing to work with a wide range of academic, governmental, NGO, and other societal partners and networks. Strengthening **outreach, capacity-building, stakeholder engagement and curiosity-driven research** have been and remain key elements of our strategy to bolster social impact. We have also leveraged the relationship between our research and education. As part of faculty-wide master's education reforms, we replaced existing, relatively large graduation studios with smaller-scale **graduation clusters** rooted strongly in the research of the graduation mentors.

Stimulate more open and collaborative research practices in which publications, data, software and other types of academic output (when possible) are shared and made available for (re)use.

We have made considerable progress in increasing the proportion of open-access publications (now almost all publications in our Department) and other research outputs, ensuring that our work is accessible to all potential users worldwide. In collaboration with the Programme Manager for Open Science, we have explored approaches to strengthen information exchange throughout the research process, in accordance with Open Science principles. A telling example is **Rbanism**, a dynamic community of practice and research initiated by several early-career Urbanism staff members, aiming to empower students, researchers, and practitioners to utilise open-source software and open science practices to answer urban questions effectively. Furthermore, we

have diversified the nature of our academic outputs, which now more often include attractively designed short **reports, manifestos, white papers for policy and practice, and digital tools** (see examples in Appendix 4). We have also increased our use of open repositories such as **Zenodo** and **GitHub** (e.g., the well-known GitHub repository of the 3D Geo-information group in Urbanism), and storage of datasets and codes, for example, the **4TU Research Data Repository**, a collaboration of four universities of technology in the Netherlands.

Nurture an Urbanism PhD culture and develop a more efficient Urbanism PhD programme,

Develop a complementary Urbanism PhD policy and Urbanism-oriented PhD courses.

The Department has implemented a multi-faceted PhD strategy (complementary to the Graduate School PhD policy) to achieve the associated aims, also in response to **recommendations 6 and 7** from the Assessment Committee. First, to nurture an Urbanism PhD culture, **two new PhD mentors** have been appointed (added to the one already in place). They serve as a point of contact and support self-organised activities by the PhD community for social interaction and knowledge exchange. Second, an **inquiry into the reasons for PhD delays** provided various reference points for PhD supervisors to anticipate causes of delay and to reduce PhD completion times. Third, we have increased **supervisor training and exchange opportunities**, for example, a yearly **PhD Supervisor Day** that enables a deep exchange of supervisor experiences and peer coaching. Fourth, a **Meta Guide to PhD Supervision** in Urbanism was published, bringing together scattered information on funding, the PhD development cycle, regulations, doctoral education, progress meetings, data management, ethics, and doctoral defence preparation into a single, continuously updated, easily accessible document for all supervisors. Fifth, to improve monitoring of PhD onboarding and progress at the Department level, Urbanism and the Graduate School ABE have designed a substantial **revision of the PhD Agreement form** for agreements between supervisors and the PhD candidate (to be signed three months after the start of a PhD). This revision has been adopted by the University Graduate School as the standard for *all* TU Delft departments, as of 2026.

As part of the revision of the doctoral education programme, the Graduate School ABE has begun offering more PhD courses on key research topics and methodologies in Urbanism, including qualitative research methods. One of the key Doctoral Education courses on developing a research proposal (a compulsory course for all PhD candidates) now includes more instructors from the Urbanism department.

Bolster a fair and inclusive academic culture where all members of Urbanism can excel.

Strengthening our academic culture, particularly in areas such as inclusivity and research integrity, requires ongoing dialogue and effective leadership. Together with the university's integrity officer and the faculty's diversity officer, we have organised (training) programmes and workshops at the Department level to raise awareness, showcase good practices, and offer practical guidelines on research integrity, ethics, fairness, and a safe working environment. In response to growing discussions on social

safety, a large majority of our permanent staff members and all staff members in leading positions have now completed compulsory **training on leadership and social safety**. To give structure, continuity and status to the discussion on social safety, a departmental **Social Safety and Care Council (SSCC)** has been established, complementary to faculty initiatives on this theme. The SSCC aims to ensure long-term continuity in addressing issues of social safety and related topics by creating opportunities for participation in decision-making, providing advice on social safety matters, ensuring voices are heard, and organising awareness activities in the Department.

In response to **recommendation 10** from the Assessment Committee, we worked to further develop our research programme in alignment with the faculty themes of **sustainable urbanisation, climate adaptation, circularity, healthy cities and digitalisation**. To this end, we organised intradepartmental **Research Exchanges** associated with each of the departmental research themes (Delta Urbanism, Inclusive Urbanism, Green Urbanism/Bio-Cities, and Data-supported Urbanism; see Paragraph 4.2). During these meetings, always led by early-/mid-career researchers, we deepened the theme narratives and identified potential opportunities for collaboration in research and funding acquisition. The breadth of disciplines in our Department and the fruits of inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration are operationalised through our research themes, enabling us to align our ambitions and research initiatives while bolstering innovation and collaboration.

Elaborate ways to recruit and retain excellent top talent;

Continuously build a diverse urbanism community as a precondition for excellence and innovation.

We continuously attempt to recruit and retain top talent from the Netherlands and around the world and encourage their development. Together with the Faculty HR department, we explored ways to attract (senior) staff who contribute to diversification, including **gender balance** (more female senior staff) and **cultural representation** (e.g., 2nd- and 3rd-generation immigrants reflecting Dutch society). Both the Assessment Committee (**recommendation 12**) and the Executive Board recommended implementing a strategy to improve staff diversity while finding the right balance between seeking international diversity and staying firmly grounded in the Dutch context. While observing an ongoing tension between these aims, the Department has taken various steps. First, we are actively **coaching female senior staff** to grow into a full professor profile and successfully embark on the internal promotion procedure. Our two new **part-time professors of practice**, who actively foster links with (urban) design practice, are female. The same applies to an endowed professor of inclusive public space (starting in 2026). We also attracted a few **associate professors with non-Dutch backgrounds**, contributing to the diversification of staff in cultural representation. With tighter financial resources and fewer options for new hires, we will invest even more in **personal career development** to retain high-performing staff through mentorship, leadership and communication training, as key elements in the Academic Career Track. This includes aligning with the various career paths identified in the new TU Delft Academic Career Guide, published at the end of 2025.

Similar to our approach to PhD candidates, we have encouraged **community building among** postdoctoral **researchers** and facilitated meetings with the department

leaders. This has led to ongoing improvements in the onboarding information, especially for postdoctoral researchers from abroad. We are also developing more hands-on resources for mentors/supervisors of postdoctoral researchers to ensure that the latter can flourish and develop in the relatively short time they are employed in the Department.

Other Responses to the Main Recommendations of the Assessment Committee

Reflect on the role and place of professors of practice in the research portfolio (ad. 5)

The Faculty initiated a discussion on the positioning and roles of professors of practice and part-time design professors. This discussion is ongoing. Elaborating on the role of design experience, design application and practice-oriented research in the academic environment will be vital to this discussion. In Urbanism, the professors of practice currently focus predominantly on teaching, which leaves less room to further strengthen the relationship between design practice and research. We will have an ongoing discussion and focus on improving expectation management for new practice-based staff members and support them in strengthening the relationship between design practice and research.

Develop a specific approach towards the representation and inclusion of non-institutional partners in urban research projects and potentially integrate this into the 'Delft approach to urbanism' (ad. 8)

This inclusion has turned out quite well, with increasing research collaborations with societal partners through bolstering outreach, capacity building and stakeholder engagement (see Appendix 4 for examples). This is inherently part of the Delft approach to Urbanism. By leading and participating in local, regional, national, and international networks of renowned academic partners, governments, NGOs, and other societal stakeholders, we ensure we are at the forefront of emerging research questions, spatial innovation, and societal development. To increase societal impact, the focus is on knowledge utilisation. We aim to improve the levels of understanding, knowledge and attitudes of all relevant stakeholders, including citizens, to empower them.

Identify and address the financial challenge in order to maintain a viable research context and high-performance levels (ad. 13)

For our Department, the financial challenges are significant. We receive less money for permanent staff than we actually spend, leading to shortages. The current budget cuts (a 15% gross reduction in faculty and departmental budgets until 2030) can still be accommodated by limiting the replacement of leaving staff, anticipating staff retirements, and further improving educational efficiency. New budget cuts will probably require more painful interventions. Considering current national political developments, it is highly unlikely that we will receive more first-stream income in the future (which would enable us to use grant revenues more strategically). This implies that we need to become more entrepreneurial in our acquisition and seek, for example, more diversification in (PhD) funding and scholarships from abroad.

Evidence

Table 4.1 provides an overview of indicators to evaluate the quality, impact, and societal relevance of our research, aligned with our strategy and aims. In Paragraph 4.6, the research context is laid out. The five research themes are elaborated in the Annex to exemplify the excellence and impact of our research programme, based on these indicators and their relationships. Next to indicators that refer to academic output, such as the number of refereed journal articles, we also want to showcase that we ‘get things done’ through indicators of knowledge utilisation, such as the use and downloads of publications and datasets, references in public domains (e.g., media) and implementation through design and policy. Major awarded individual and collaborative research grants, as well as financial support from and contract research with societal partners, demonstrate that our Department successfully implements our research strategy.

TABLE 4.1

SELECTED INDICATORS FOR RESEARCH QUALITY AND SOCIETAL RELEVANCE URBANISM		
	RESEARCH QUALITY	RELEVANCE TO SOCIETY
Demonstrable products	Research products for peers (Open access) Journal articles Conference papers PhD-Dissertations Editorships (Open) Data sets, scripts and software (in open repositories) Providing design documentation (e.g., drawings, code, 3D files) Designs, plans and policy advice Exhibitions	Research products for societal target groups (Open access) Books Book chapters Professional publications (e.g. magazine articles) Lectures, masterclasses and conferences for a general audience Invitations for public lectures MOOC's
Demonstrable use of products	Use of research products by peers Use of our data sets Citations of articles, books and other products Downloads/reads of articles, books and other products GitHub stars, forks, and contributions for tools or scripts Downloads or users of software/plugins Engagement metrics on open access platforms (e.g. ResearchGate, Zenodo) Use of research in teaching	Use of research products by societal target groups Projects in cooperation with societal parties (co-creation), leading to the implementation of jointly developed ideas, strategies, interventions, etc. Contract research Use of academic results in contexts of practice Use in and relation to education References in professional and public domains (e.g. national/local media outlets)
Demonstrable marks of recognition	Marks of recognition from peers Research grants awarded to individuals Research grants awarded to individual and major collaborative research projects Prizes awarded to individuals Competitive commissions or residencies Recognition from expert panels in design competitions	Marks of recognition by societal target groups Financial and material support by society Public prizes awarded to individuals Invitations for public lectures Number of visitors to exhibitions

Accomplishments in 2022-2025; research quality & societal relevance

Research context

In 2025, the Department consisted of **86 scientific staff members and researchers** (excl. PhD candidates), representing approximately **41 FTEs of research capacity** (Table 4.4).

The Department has acquired **€50 million in research funding** for the period 2022-2025 (Table 4.2). There was a **52% increase** in funding income between 2022 and 2025. This upward trend continues from the previous period (2016-2021). It is not only the result of increasing staff, but also of strategy, better support structures and growing experience with grant applications. We secured several prestigious individual grants: **one ERC Starting Grant, one ERC Proof of Concept Grant, two NWO VENI grants, and two Marie Curie grants**. Overall, we secured **more than 60 major collaborative research projects** (Horizon 2020, National Science Agenda NWA, etc.) and projects supported by societal partners during the period 2022-2025. A selection of the associated projects will be highlighted in Appendix 4.

The 2022-2025 period has been very productive, with a total output of **1,011 publications, including 426 peer-reviewed journal articles, 149 book chapters, 17 books, and 36 PhD theses** (Table 5). The full list can be found at <https://research.tudelft.nl/en/organisations/urbanism/publications/>. While the numbers per category fluctuate, the amount of peer-reviewed journal articles is on the rise – a result of our strategy to support publishing in peer-reviewed journals. Through repositories such as [Pure](#), [TU Delft repository](#), [ResearchGate](#) and [Zenodo](#), all our publications can be accessed, and (almost) all are open access. This is partly thanks to negotiations by all Dutch universities with publishing companies, which have led to agreements allowing researchers at Dutch universities to publish open access in most journals. The publication ratio per research staff member has remained high over the years, averaging **three peer-reviewed journal papers per FTE** over the past four years, the highest among the faculty. This demonstrates a high level of awareness that knowledge dissemination is important in our research community.

Regarding **PhD policy and training**, we have, on average, **90 PhD candidates**. As in previous years, enrolment fluctuated between 2022 and 2025. Completion rates within four or five years remain low, despite the Faculty Graduate School's efforts to improve the process and its monitoring. While this does not necessarily affect the quality of the research, it is a concern regarding its financial viability in terms of covering hours and other resources. The delays are largely explained by personal circumstances, students working part-time on their PhD, the Covid-19 period, and ineffective expectation management (on both the side of PhD candidates and supervisors). The latter was uncovered by an inquiry and has received special attention (see Paragraph 4.4). In sum, the Department needs to increase PhD 'efficiency'. Training and improvement of PhD supervision will become increasingly important. We have put substantial effort and resources into this, ranging from training and improved information provision to peer support for PhD supervisors (see Paragraph 4.4 for an overview of our strategy).

TABLE 4.2

RESEARCH FUNDING URBANISM									
	2022		2023		2024		2025		
	k€	%	k€	%	k€	%	k€	%	
Direct funding (1)	7.644	77%	8.942	77%	9.657	71%	9.898	66%	
Research grants (2)	507	5%	694	6%	691	5%	927	6%	
Contract research (3)	1.613	16%	1.816	16%	3.084	23%	3.926	26%	
Other (4)	119	1%	147	1%	183	1%	145	1%	
Total funding	9.883	100%	11.599	100%	13.615	100%	14.896	100%	
Personnel costs	9.015	94%	10.999	94%	13.306	95%	14.407	95%	
Material costs	252	3%	238	2%	257	2%	259	2%	
Other costs	369	4%	425	4%	375	3%	534	4%	
Total expenditure	9.636	100%	11.662	100%	13.938	100%	15.200	100%	
	247		-63		-323		-304		

TABLE 4.3

RESEARCH OUTPUT URBANISM				
	2022	2023	2024	2025
Refereed article	86	104	116	120
Non-refereed article	4	9	4	4
Professional publications	24	22	17	4
Books	3	5	3	6
Book chapter	51	30	32	36
Publications aimed at the general public	2	1	1	1
Conference papers	26	24	43	27
PhD theses	6	13	7	10
Other research output	59	40	38	32
Total	262	248	261	240

TABLE 4.4

RESEARCH STAFF URBANISM								
SEP categories	2022		2023		2024		2025	
	#	FTE	#	FTE	#	FTE	#	FTE
Assistant professor	24,9	9,4	28,3	10,8	29,0	11,1	27,5	10,5
Associate professor	17,8	6,0	17,7	6,2	18,2	6,7	18,9	7,0
Full professor	6,0	1,8	7,8	2,1	9,0	2,3	9,5	2,7
Postdocs	3,9	2,3	12,2	8,5	14,2	10,6	16,3	12,2
Researchers (other)	8,4	5,3	14,2	9,7	17,1	11,3	14,2	8,3
PhD candidate (HR)	19,2	18,4	20,4	19,7	26,8	25,9	29,7	28,8
Total	80,3	43,2	100,6	57,0	114,3	67,9	116,1	69,4
Support staff	1,5	1,4	1,0	0,9	1,0	0,9	1,0	0,9
Grand Total	81,8	44,6	101,6	57,9	115,3	68,8	117,1	70,3

TABLE 4.5

PHD CANDIDATES URBANISM									
	Enrollment			Success rates cumulative					
	Male & other	Female	Total	Graduated totals		Not yet finished		Discontinued	
Start	#	#	#	#	%	#	%	#	%
2022	10	10	20	2	10%	16	80%	2	10%
2023	9	5	14	0	-	12	86%	2	14%
2024	7	10	17	0	-	16	94%	1	6%
2025	4	4	8	0	-	8	100%	0	-
Total	30	29	59	2	-	52	-	5	-

TABLE 4.6

PHD CANDIDATES URBANISM																	
	Enrollment			Success rates cumulative													
	Male & other	Female	Total	Graduated ≤ 4 years		Graduated ≤ 5 years		Graduated ≤ 6 years		Graduated ≤ 7 years		Graduated totals		Not yet finished		Discontinued	
Start	#	#	#	1	6%	4	24%	4	24%	8	47%	#	%	#	%	#	%
2016	11	6	17	0	-	0	-	0	-	2	25%	10	59%	3	18%	4	24%
2017	3	5	8	0	-	1	17%	3	50%	3	50%	3	38%	4	50%	1	13%
2018	3	3	6	0	-	0	-	2	50%	2	50%	3	50%	1	17%	2	33%
2019	4		4	1	8%	3	23%	4	31%	4	31%	2	50%	1	25%	1	25%
2020	10	3	13	0	-	2	12%	2	12%	2	12%	4	31%	8	62%	1	8%
2021	11	6	17	2	-	10	-	15	-	21	-	2	12%	15	88%	0	-
Total	42	23	65	3	-	12	-	17	-	21	-	24	-	32	-	9	-

FIG. 4.2 Proportion male (blue) / female (orange) in research staff 2022-2025 (excl. guests).

FIG. 4.3 Proportion of nationality (NL/EU/non-EU) (excl. guests). Dark green = NL, medium green = EU, light green = non-EU.

Complementary to the faculty HR policy, the number of full professors has increased slightly after years of decline due to retirements and unfilled vacancies. This did not have an immediate effect on the quality and impact of our research. However, this growth has positively affected the Department's visibility, with a few more professors serving as figureheads to connect the Department with societal stakeholders and contribute to societal debates. While this role is partly and successfully conducted by leading associate professors, we still need to increase the number of full professors. The currently low number may affect the societal impact and the longer-term viability of our research. To address this threat, we have continued a more proactive talent management approach, stimulating internal growth and promotion of talented, well-performing staff through dedicated coaching trajectories. This will start to pay off from 2026 onwards.

Although the **gender balance and cultural diversity** have slightly improved in recent years (Fig. 4.2 and 4.3), female leadership in the Department remains underrepresented, despite serious efforts to attract female full and associate professors through targeted advertising and personal invitations. Given the global focus of our work, the Department also acknowledges that we need more non-European representation in leadership without neglecting the importance of Dutch-speaking senior staff, which is indispensable for a strong link to Dutch society, practice, and societal partners.

4.7

Strategy for the time until the next assessment and beyond

4.7.1

SWOT analysis

At the end of the full-term research assessment for 2016-2021, a SWOT analysis was conducted to define the Urbanism strategy for 2022-2027. Here, we have revised the SWOT analysis to reflect new realities of the current period until 2028. The analysis is the result of discussions and brainstorming among a wide range of Department members and research staff.

Strengths

- Strong record in inter- and transdisciplinary, context- and design-driven, and solution-focused research and applications;
- High capability to build digital solutions, partly thanks to the establishment of VR and AI labs for experimentation and fundamental research ;

- Strong and growing engagement with Open Science practices, nationally and internationally;
- Strong international, national, and local networks to support policy-relevant, trans-disciplinary research, community engagement, and impact;
- Sustained success rate in research funding acquisition, including prestigious personal grants;
- Strong links between research and education.

Weaknesses

- Required efficiency in research & education, and scarce resources lead to less space for experimentation and curiosity-driven research;
- Limited diversification of funding streams and strategies; broadening the scope of opportunities requires a lot of (scarce) time;
- Gender balance and cultural diversity in senior positions (associate and full professors);
- Low number of full professors;
- Limited staff progression and inability to hire or retain talented early-career researchers;
- Low efficiency of PhD projects (most candidates still need > 4 years to complete).

Opportunities

- Global trends in urbanisation demand knowledge and expertise in sustainable urbanisation, climate adaptation, energy transition, circularity, spatial inequality, digitalisation and urban health;
- Sustained Open Science funding and recognition in the Netherlands and beyond;
- Strong strategic alliances in the Netherlands and internationally;
- Continuing research calls/funding at national, EU and global levels, particularly for transdisciplinary, design- and application-oriented projects, fitting nicely with our research narratives.

Threats

- Increasingly competitive national and inter-national research funds -> lower chances of success;
- Reduced inflow of PhD candidates due to stricter knowledge security rules and the ban on self-funding;
- Weakening of our common identity by losing the balance in what binds us together, and disciplinary deepening;
- Growing (teaching) pressure due to budget cuts leads to less time for research & grant writing;
- High overall work pressure.

Urbanism research strategy 2026-2028

The Urbanism research strategy outlines how we will utilise the opportunities and strengths mentioned above and address the identified weaknesses and threats. We have defined the following strategic aims for the further development of our Department's research in the period 2026-2028. The strategic aims were built upon the previous ones (2022-2028), and we adapted them in light of recent fundamental changes in funding landscapes, national science policies, and particular developments within the university and faculty to meet our specific needs.

Research quality and societal relevance

- Remain world-leading in design-related scholarship and socially relevant and impactful research for the understanding, planning and development of sustainable urban landscapes;
- Develop an elaborate research funding strategy combining the current strengths of individual and section expertise with tailored efforts to diversify funding sources, to respond to increasing competition for funds and threats of fragmentation of staff efforts;
- Cultivate the Delft Approach to Urbanism as a socially and ecologically inclusive approach with a strong link between spatial research and design across scales, based on inter- and transdisciplinary working and employing state-of-the-art digital technology, as part of a wider envisioning process on the role of Urbanism in the 21st century;
- Foster disciplinary breadth, depth and innovation;
- Expand co-creative and transdisciplinary modes of working by engaging communities, civil society, governmental and non-traditional partners as active contributors in our research and design process;
- Cultivate the relationship between the Urbanism research programme and PhD/MSc education, particularly benefiting from recent changes in the MSc graduation and Graduate School courses.

While we succeeded in securing significant research funding in 2022-2025, the SWOT analysis identifies several threats to our capacity to sustain this level of performance. We will therefore take some time to develop a tailor-made research funding acquisition strategy that accounts for streamlined responses to calls for proposals, personal and group motivation and excellence, a proactive approach to influence funding agendas and to propose new stakeholders for diversification of funding sources, more effective department-level coordination of ideas, initiatives and staff efforts, and capitalising on earlier funding acquisition efforts (which were not granted). Another element will be strengthening internal support (e.g., a 'buddy' system) in which senior academics consistently support younger colleagues in developing grant applications.

We will consolidate our current success in knowledge utilisation and valorisation by continuing work with non-academic partners. Strengthening outreach, capacity building, stakeholder engagement and curiosity-driven research remain constituent

elements of our strategy to bolster social impact. Making better use of our BK Labs (experimental laboratories in our faculty) will be conducive to this purpose. We aim to extend stakeholder engagement across diverse global contexts, including underrepresented regions (e.g., the Global South), to strengthen the Department's inclusive positioning and alignment with international research agendas. We will also further grow and leverage our strong relationship between research and education.

Open science

- Stimulate more open and collaborative research practices in which publications, data, software and other types of academic output (when possible) are shared and made available for (re)use.

We strive to maximise and consolidate the high proportion of open-access publications and other research outputs to ensure that our work is available to all potential users worldwide. We also aim to increase competence in and commitment to other open science practices, such as FAIR data publication, reproducibility, open-source research software and open peer review. We recently hired a 1.0 fte research data and software engineer (a permanent position) to support us in this aim. We will ensure that open science practices translate into real-world impact by making data, tools, and knowledge accessible and usable for policymakers, practitioners, and communities, particularly in resource-constrained settings.

In collaboration with the Programme Manager Open Science, we will explore approaches to strengthen the possibility of exchange throughout the research process in the context of Urbanism, in accordance with the principles of open science. We strictly adhere to the Delft University of Technology guidelines for our research software (see <https://zenodo.org/records/4629635>).

PhD policy and training

- Nurture an Urbanism PhD culture and develop a more efficient Urbanism PhD programme;
- Nourish a complementary Urbanism PhD strategy and Urbanism-oriented PhD courses.

We will continue to improve the efficiency of our PhD programme by consolidating measures from our multifaceted PhD strategy, which we recently developed and implemented (see Paragraph 4.4, complementing the Graduate School PhD policy). This will be done particularly by monitoring progress at the Department level, by training supervisors, and encouraging supervisor peer support (complementary to efforts at the faculty level). We will also continue to nourish an Urbanism PhD culture by organising regular meetings at the Department and section levels with PhD candidates, their supervisors, and PhD mentors for social interaction and knowledge exchange. In line with recent changes in the Graduate School Doctoral Education Programme, we will actively promote input from Urbanism staff members in redeveloped or new Graduate School courses.

Academic culture

- Bolster a fair and inclusive academic culture where all members of Urbanism can excel.

Strengthening our academic culture, especially inclusivity and research integrity, requires ongoing dialogue and leadership. Together with the university's integrity officer and the faculty's diversity officer, we will continue to develop and organise (training) programmes and workshops at the Department level to raise awareness, showcase best practices, and provide practical guidelines on research integrity, ethics, fairness, and a safe working environment. We will devote special attention to the ongoing discussions (also faculty- and TU-wide) on social safety and inclusion.

HR policy

- Elaborate ways to recruit and retain excellent top talent, particularly by exemplifying and supporting various career paths in line with the new TU Delft Academic Career Guide;
- Continuously build a diverse Urbanism community as a precondition for excellence and innovation.

We will continue our efforts to recruit and retain top talent from the Netherlands and around the world, and to encourage their development. Together with the Faculty HR department, we will continue to explore ways to attract (senior) staff who contribute to diversification in terms of gender balance (e.g., more female senior staff) and cultural representation. We strive for a diverse team in which the specific strengths of all team members can be combined. To retain well-performing academic staff, we will support career development through personal mentorship and (clearer) career roadmaps, as well as dedicated training programmes in leadership and communication. For less senior staff, this support is embedded in the Academic Career Track Development Programme, which comprises a wide range of training courses and tools across all areas of the academic career (see the Faculty chapter).

The strategy as presented here serves as a compass for the further development of the excellent scholarship and research that characterise the Urbanism department. The process of unfolding our strategy is a continuous undertaking. The strategic aims and working programme outlined here will be translated into concrete actions that will enable us to maintain our outstanding reputation for contributing to the understanding and creation of future-proof, liveable and socio-ecologically inclusive built environments that respond to societal and environmental changes, and are the breeding ground for applying contextual design, planning, and engineering strategies and interventions with impact for a better society.

Case studies Urbanism

The research programme of the Department of Urbanism was initially organised into four themes: **Delta Urbanism, Inclusive Urbanism, Green Urbanism/Bio-Cities, and Data-Supported Urbanism**. In 2025, a fifth theme was added: **Integrative Transitional Urbanism**. This emergence reflects an expansion of highly interrelated yet distinct research projects, all rooted in the faculty's key research themes.

We illustrate the quality and impact of the research themes through examples of the Department's research and projects in each of the five themes. The examples demonstrate the viability of our research, as the research themes reflect how we address societal challenges, including sustainable urbanisation, climate adaptation, circularity, digitalisation and equity. All examples span across sections and are not strictly connected to one section or research group. In each example, we highlight a selection of research outputs, use, and recognition – in other words, impact.

B.4.1

Delta Urbanism

Sustainable urbanisation, biodiversity loss, and climate change are key challenges for deltas worldwide. These highly dynamic geographies are characterised by fragility, criticality and risk: transitional landscapes between land and water, altered by urbanisation, industrialisation and extractivism. The Department's research on Delta Urbanism covers the most important scales of the **relationship between land and water, focusing specifically on the development and application of design-oriented, systemic, and inter- and transdisciplinary approaches, sensitive to on-site socio-cultural and ecological conditions**. Adaptive multiscale design strategies, nature-based solutions for coastal and river flood protection, water-sensitive urban design, and vernacular water practices are some of the themes elaborated in research and teaching.

R

D

REDESIGNING DELTA

16-18.06.2022

International Delta
Conference

*Design for
transformative change:
evidence, agency,
cross-disciplinary knowledge*

Hosted by:

TU Delft
Convergence Alliance—Resilient Delta
Deltares
The City of Rotterdam
The Delta Alliance
Wageningen University & Research
the Delta Commissioner
PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency

L

A prime example of strengthening the design component in land-water relationships is the multi-year research programme **Redesigning Deltas (RDD)**, an initiative by the Delta Urbanism Interdisciplinary Research group. This initiative is partnered by the Convergence Alliance-Resilient Delta, Deltares, Wageningen University & Research, the Delta Commissioner, PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency, IHE Delft and Erasmus University. Its main impact is national integration of spatial design into delta management (solutions and policy), enriching the delta community with spatial designers. This impact has been achieved through a series of **refereed journal articles, practitioner publications, design study reports, and a manifesto for the 'new Dutch Delta'**. Also noteworthy are **five exhibitions** of design studies by the RDD programme, e.g., about 100 years of future ideas at the Nieuwe Instituut, and 'It's About Time' (five projects) at the International Architecture Biennale Rotterdam in 2022. Links with (post-master) education were established through contributions to interdisciplinary design education and master classes in design study.

Several **major international collaborations** exemplify the quality of our research and societal impact, with partners from academia, the private sector, governmental bodies, and local NGOs, jointly building a transdisciplinary framework at the intersection of spatial design and planning, governance, social sciences, water science, and engineering.

One example is **DST-NWO Water4Change (W4C)**, a **collaboration between** the Dutch and Indian governments in which the Department takes the lead. This project started in 2020 with a research grant of **€3.5 million**, enabling **13 PhDs** (4 NL, 9 India) and **3 Postdocs** (1 NL, 2 India). It addresses the complex challenges to urban water systems faced by fast-growing secondary cities in India and the sustainability transitions needed for short- and long-term mitigation of, adaptation to, and coping with urgencies and uncertainties (Fig. 4.7). By co-creating a **cross-sectoral Water Sensitive Design Framework (WSDF), practice-oriented Fit-for-Purpose Guidelines and an open-source Water Sensitive COMPASS decision-support tool**, this project enables water-sensitive development, accounting for site specificities and deep site knowledge, presenting innovative interventions, practices, design, and policy guidelines. Altogether, W4C's impact extends not only to advancing water-sensitive urban development in India but also to shaping future models for transcontinental, co-creative research capable of informing policy, practice, and climate adaptation trajectories well beyond its original pilot cities.

Another example is the **UNDP Archipelago Project**, a major climate-adaptation and territorial-resilience initiative led in partnership with the United Nations Development Programme and the City of Porto Alegre, developed to strengthen long-term flood resilience and socio-ecological mediation across the Jacuí Delta in the aftermath of the catastrophic 2024 floods. The project hosts a **strategic international partnership, a post-disaster transformation agenda, and deeply embedded co-creation processes (workshops, living labs, and participatory diagnostics), as well as governance and institutional strengthening**. These have produced shared vulnerability assessments, spatial visions, and implementation roadmaps that improve coordination across fragmented planning and water-management regimes.

FIG. 4.5 The Water4Change project regards India as a perfect 'testing ground' to reflect on the interplays and co-dependencies between society and nature (image: Water4Change)

The project has become a **platform for international dissemination and deep knowledge exchange**, through its presentation at the São Paulo International Architecture Biennial, public debates within UN-Habitat Circuito Urbano, and two dedicated panels at COP30 in Belém reflecting on regenerative public policy, South–North cooperation, and the translation of design research into long-term governance instruments. Alongside the research, an intensive **Brazil–Netherlands educational programme** mobilised sixty-eight students through TU Delft's EXTREME Architecture Studio in immersive fieldwork and collective construction on the islands.

FIG. 4.6 Janneke van Bergen and her promoters Prof. Steffen Nijhuis and Prof. Eric Luiten (image courtesy of Steffen Nijhuis).

A final example of a publicly rewarded project is **Shorescape: Sustainable co-evolution of the natural and built environment along sandy shores** (completed in 2023), funded by the NWO Top Sector Water Call. The Shorescape research has delivered knowledge, tools, and design principles for dynamic occupation of the land-sea interface and exploiting its potential for the spatial development of multi-functional coastal environments. This project made an impact by finding smart, proactive sediment management through ‘building-with-nature’ approaches, rather than traditional reactive approaches that involve expanding static, hard coastal defence structures. The project resulted in **four refereed journal articles, an edited volume, and a PhD thesis** by Janneke van Bergen, in the section Landscape Architecture. Her PhD thesis received the **2025 Steven Hoogendijk prize**, awarded every two years by the ‘Bataafsch Genootschap der Proefondervinderlijke Wijsbegeerte’ to the best PhD thesis from TU Delft in that period.

Inclusive Urbanism

Growing urban **inequality** is a growing **concern for citizens, urban practitioners, and policymakers worldwide**. Inequality is not only unacceptable from an ethical and normative standpoint; it also imposes high costs on society, hampering cities' performance and impacting their health, social cohesion, and living standards, thereby hindering the conditions for people and the economy to flourish. The Department's research on Inclusive Urbanism addresses those urgent challenges from an **integrated and cross-disciplinary perspective**, emphasising the **spatial dimension of inequality** and how spatial planning and urban design can be mobilised to make cities more just and inclusive. What makes our approach to researching these topics unique is our combination of insights and methods from urban design, spatial planning, urban geography, and urban sociology. At the same time, in our research on and for inclusive urbanism, we aim to engage a diverse range of stakeholders, particularly representatives of vulnerable and marginalised groups, in the co-design and co-decision-making of sustainable urban futures.

A telling example of this engaging approach is the project **Ruimte voor Meiden op Zuid (Make Space for Girls, 2023-2024)**. This project was commissioned by the city of Rotterdam and asked to investigate how public spaces can be more inviting to young women (12-20 years old), as numbers showed that this group often does not go out due to feelings of unsafety and inadequate public spaces. For the interviews, the researchers collaborated with Chicks & The City (CATC), a Rotterdam-based foundation where girls create media productions about topics that concern them. This resulted in a podcast. After publication, the report generated **significant media attention**, particularly from national newspapers (such as Trouw and NRC) and radio broadcasts. In 2025, after a young woman was murdered in Amsterdam during her bike ride home, attention for this project accelerated. The researchers have been invited by many **media outlets, governmental institutions, architectural firms, and other actors** to present the research, host workshops and advise on design proposals and local public space policies.

In 2022, Dr Cottineau (section Urban Studies) was awarded a prestigious **ERC Starting Grant** for the project **SEGUE**: Integrating explanatory mechanisms of economic segregation across geographical scales. While continuing until 2029, the project has already delivered several key outcomes. It has been shown that income inequality and segregation are relatively low and stable, but differ strongly in level and trend between 35 functional areas in the Netherlands since 2011. Moreover, the project shows diverging trends: residential segregation by *income* has decreased in most Dutch cities, while segregation by *wealth* has increased. SEGUE has already generated a substantial list of peer-reviewed journal articles, books and book chapters. Widely recognised as groundbreaking research, it also resulted in **several invited keynote lectures and seminars** at conferences in Brage, Luxembourg, Paris, London and Athens. Also under the Inclusive Urbanism theme, several **major international collaborations** exemplify the quality of our research and societal impact, with partners from academia, the private sector, governmental bodies, and local NGOs, jointly building a transdisciplinary framework at the intersection of spatial design and planning, governance, social sciences, and engineering.

FIG. 4.7 The DUST exhibition displaying hopes and dreams of communities facing sustainability transitions. Photography: SZ REDA. Artwork by Ooze architects, with the support of Malgorzata Rybak, TU Delft.

Between February 2023 and January 2026, the Department of Urbanism led the project **Democratising jUST Sustainability Transitions (DUST)**, funded under the European Union's **Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme**. The DUST project developed and operationalised novel participatory instruments for proactive and strategic citizen engagement in sustainability transitions. It addressed a fundamental societal and democratic challenge for Europe: hearing the voices of the least engaged communities (LECs), especially in economically weak regions dependent on energy-intensive industries. Around **50 researchers from 13 partner organisations** collaborated on the DUST project, focusing on **eight case study regions** across Europe. Their involvement strengthened interdisciplinary research and networks at the intersection of regional spatial design and planning research, public policy, and democracy studies. Living Labs, titled **Regional Futures Literacy Labs (RFLs)**, were conducted in four European case study regions. The participation of approximately 180 least-engaged community members and 20 policymakers and other institutional stakeholders was sustained over nine months and across four workshops per RFL. Around 750 members of the public participated in the RFLs via the e-democracy tool Pol.is. These members cast approximately 26,000 votes on LEC policy statements. Four regional designs, spatially representing the positions of LECs, were curated for display; an **estimated 5,000 visitors** viewed them during six RFL exhibitions across four countries.

Through the DUST website, four citizen position papers, five policy briefs, two handbooks, 17 storytelling videos and a compilation of best practices were disseminated among local, regional, national, and international audiences. Around **10,000 policy practitioners** were reached via the presentation of project results at six international policy conferences.

Another example of major international collaboration is the **UP2030** project, funded under the European Union's **Horizon Europe Innovation Actions programme**. UP2030 aims to support **11 cities** in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate-neutrality targets through urban planning and design. The role of the Urbanism team was primarily to identify existing tools and to steer the development of new tools to assist cities in this endeavour. A catalogue of tools was produced and linked to a new conceptualisation of the planning cycle, along with guidelines for applying the tools within this cycle. The Urbanism team also developed the Spatial Justice package – a bundle of resources (including a handbook and a benchmarking tool) to support the integration of spatial justice in urban planning and design. The tools catalogue was actively **used by all 11 cities** and contributed to the development of pilot actions promoting net-zero transitions in real contexts. The project achieved substantial **capacity-building impact** in the pilot cities and knowledge dissemination through a series of **conference presentations, events, and workshops** organised (including a major symposium in Delft, resulting in a journal special issue), engaging more than 800 researchers and students. The TU Delft resources developed within UP2030 have seen more than 1,000 downloads on **Zenodo**.

Finally, the **COHERENT** project (2022-2024) is a good example of how research and teaching are combined seamlessly and productively. COHERENT stands for COLlaborative HERitage REsearch and INtervention design. This transdisciplinary **Dutch National Research Agenda (NWA)** project explored how heritage – specifically festive foods, garments, and war sites – can be repurposed to create sustainable, inclusive futures. It connects scientific and societal partners to redesign, interpret, and implement interventions in these areas. From Urbanism, the Landscape Architecture section contributed to the sub-project 'Citizens' Perspective on the Atlantikwall', organising **design workshops** for students from the universities of Delft, Leiden and Amsterdam, working in interdisciplinary groups to develop future perspectives on the contested heritage of the Atlantikwall. This was done in collaboration with the province of South Holland, the city of The Hague, and the *Haagse Vrijheidsweken* (The Hague Freedom Weeks).

B.4.3

Green Urbanism / Bio-Cities

This theme brings together research addressing urgent, intertwined societal challenges including climate change, energy transition, environmental degradation, biodiversity loss and food and material security, alongside more explorative and conceptual research that reframes the contemporary urban territory as a landscape metropolis. It focuses on **advancing human and ecological well-being** by understanding and

applying natural, spatial, and place-based conditions for socio-ecologically inclusive design at the building and regional scales. This includes the development of design-oriented landscape approaches that base spatial development on the natural system, along with the exploration and employment of the cultural, spatial, and perceptual characteristics of landscapes in planning and design. Research on **urban climate and energy, regional landscape approaches, urban biodiversity and regenerative and circular urban landscapes** is connected to systemic design, adaptive design principles and regenerative strategies that lead to **healthy and inclusive green-blue cities**. The development of metropolitan landscapes and nature networks, heat-stress mitigation through urban morphology, and increasing sponge capacity and biodiversity in the urban context through greening cities are important topics for research and application, along with circular approaches to improve, restore, and revitalise energy and material sources in the built environment.

Sometimes, our work has an impact on our doorstep, for example, the **EcoCampus TU Delft**. This initiative aims to develop a biodiverse, carbon-neutral, circular, and climate-adaptive TU Delft campus environment with direct impact on the campus and up-scaling, multiplying, and cascading to similar urban environments via knowledge, strategies, tools, and methodologies. It is led by the Landscape Architecture section and is funded by TU Delft Campus & Real Estate (CRE). This 'living lab' initiative to transform the TU campus into an 'EcoCampus' has delivered research knowledge and design principles via demonstrator projects and student projects. Its impact includes increasing biodiversity and the quality of life on campus, and advancing the development of Living Labs as a method for sustainable innovation. Particular examples of impactful demonstrator projects include the **Urban Climate Grove** in the forecourt of the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment and the **Food Village exhibition** at Hortus Botanicus of TU Delft.

There are strong links with teaching – students from the Faculty of Architecture contribute to the design of green outdoor spaces. Through Green TU, students participate in bee monitoring, nature management, and events such as Plant-a-Tree Day, all designed to increase engagement with our campus and its efforts to become greener and more biodiverse. The EcoCampus project has received **recognition from the field** through various invited lectures and selection of the 'Urban Climate Grove' as a **best project** for the 2025 yearbook of landscape architecture and urbanism in the Netherlands.

A highly related project is **i-Tree 2.0-NL** (2020-2025). This research project develops next-generation metrics and methodologies for urban forestry and climate resilience in Dutch cities. It focuses on quantifying cooling performance, species-specific growth, and life-cycle benefits to improve urban planning for heat stress, air quality, and biodiversity. It is part of a Top-sector PPS funding consortium from ClickNL, including 8 major cities, 4 knowledge institutes, 10 industry partners and 5 societal partners. A novel outcome of the i-Tree 2.0-NL project is a **management dashboard** that visualises tree inventories (crown, volume, tree diversity, and ecosystem benefits) of existing urban forest stands and future scenarios. An **8-step methodology for 'trees-first' urban design** was also developed in the project, along with principles and recommendations for urban forest managers, which are incorporated in the IPC programme (*Opleidingsinstituut voor de leefomgeving*). Finally, an **open-source urban forest dashboard** is now in use by participating municipalities and arboricultural firms.

FIG. 4.8 The Urban Climate Grove in the forecourt of the Faculty of Architecture & the Built Environment (image: Frans Snijder).

The outcomes were disseminated in a series of **reports, papers, keynotes, and conference workshops**. The i-Tree project also generated **significant media attention**, particularly from national newspapers (such as Trouw, Parool, and the Telegraaf) and national and international news sites, including NOS and Al Jazeera. The PI from the Department of Urbanism featured in many podcasts, earning him the nickname **'tree professor'**. As with the EcoCampus project, the research is closely intertwined with education. The graduation lab "Urban Forestry – Forest Urbanism" expands on the theoretical and design-technical aspects of urban forestry within the context of built environment disciplines. This lab also partners with international education and research institutions in Norway (Oslo School of Architecture and Design), Sweden (SLU Alnarp), Denmark (Copenhagen University), Switzerland (ETH Zurich), Italy (Polytechnic of Milan), Spain (IAAC Barcelona) and Portugal (University of Lisbon).

A subproject within i-Tree 2.0-NL is the **Atlas of Tree City Delft**. This is an example of **locally-engaged scholarship** that uses the local city context as a canvas for research. This research maps the urban forest of Delft from a historical, spatial, and sociocultural

perspective, contributing to the academic development of urban forestry from a landscape architectural perspective and, more practically, to developing principles and pathways for understanding, ordering, and acting in cities like Delft from a 'forest-scape' perspective. Conclusions from the atlas are now being incorporated into urban planning and policy in Delft.

Moving from urban to suburban/rural landscapes, the **Cowborgs in the polder** (2023-2024) project explored how the design of farm buildings, animal bodies and technologies transformed Dutch dairy landscapes. This topic has received significant attention in the context of the Dutch political and societal discussion about the harmful effects of nitrogen on landscapes and the environment. The work was **exhibited at** a show in Radius CCA **in Delft** and has been presented in **lectures in (inter)national seminars** and conferences across disciplines. It appeared in influential disciplinary media outlets such as Archined. The work will be prominently featured in a major exhibition at the Architekturmuseum der TUM in Munich, opening in April 2026. A spin-off documentary film on the project is in production (financed by TUM).

B.4.4

Data-supported Urbanism

In the field of data-supported urbanism, the Department's impact spans the full data lifecycle from generation and reconstruction to standardisation, management, and usage, while leveraging the opportunities that modern open/big data offer for urban landscape planning and design in the context of Digital Twinning, with a strong focus on the urban and territorial scale. The Department is strongly committed to generating and utilising **innovative, sustainable, and open data and software ecosystems** where researchers and practitioners can interact in various ways: by retrieving and using the data and software, adding new data and software, and delivering improved data and software and new insights back into the ecosystem. The impact encompasses both theory development and implementation and application. It focuses on how **buildings, cities and landscapes** can be **automatically** and **semantically modelled in 3D/4D** to be used for urban planning and design, what new legal, economic, societal, ethical **challenges and opportunities new big/open urban data** bring to urbanism, and how data-supported approaches foster the development of **new methodologies** and products that support all stages of **co-creative urban planning and design** with a focus on sustainability, circularity and inclusiveness.

The prestigious **ERC project Urban Modelling in Higher Dimensions** serves as an example of the research quality and societal impact of our work in this theme. This **€1.7 million project, funded by the European Research Council and the Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS)**, began in 2016. In the project, an open-source method has been developed to automatically reconstruct 3D building models for large areas, resulting in a countrywide open 3D dataset in the Netherlands called **3DBAG**. The 3DBAG is an open, continuously updated dataset of detailed 3D building models for the Netherlands, automatically generated from BAG building data and AHN height data. The 3DBAG is a **widely used dataset** with, on average, **more than**

100,000 tile downloads and more than 850,000 service queries. It has generated a spin-off company (3DGI) and the further development (within and outside the Department) of applications related to energy use in buildings, estimating energy demand, retrofitting costs, finding suitable roofs for solar panels, simulating wind flow and pollutant dispersion in urban areas (e.g., Simwind), and calculating noise pollution in urban areas (e.g., 3D Noise).

Horizon Europe awarded the ERC PI, Prof. Jantien Stoter, a **Proof-of-Concept grant 'Detailed 3D Building models Automatically Generated for very large areas'** (2022-2024) to assure both the technical and economic sustainability of 3DBAG as an up-to-date and open data service. 3DBAG has been widely featured in the media and is used on **municipal platforms** such as 3D.Amsterdam.nl and 3D.Utrecht.nl (Fig. 4.11). Several funding sources from individual organisations have been obtained to adapt 3DBAG to specific needs (e.g., RVO for energy and RIVM for noise). 3DBAG reconstruction software (Roofer) has been used in other countries to **reconstruct 3D models** for large areas (IGN France, Slovenia). Given the world-wide growing role of Digital Twins, particular attention has been paid to **interoperability across different data formats and standards**, with a specific focus on integrating BIM and GIS data. Open-source software has been developed for several parts of 3DBAG (e.g., the viewer and building reconstruction). Apart from downloads and extensive use, the 3DBAG has won academic awards, including the Excellence Award at the Geospatial World Forum 2021, and the Esri Award for Best Scientific Paper in GIS 2023. The 3DBAG innovation platform has been established by seven governmental agencies to ensure the maintenance and further innovation of 3DBAG.

Another aspect of Data-supported Urbanism is the governance of open data, its societal, economic and ethical impact, and the legal conditions for implementing and utilising open data policies. The Department takes a leading role in open science via programmes such as ODECO: towards a sustainable Open Data ECOSystem, a four-year **Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network initiative**. The central aim is to train the next generation of creative and innovative early-stage open-data experts capable of creating user-driven, circular, and inclusive open-data ecosystems through interdisciplinary collaboration between academia and industry. The programme ran between October 2021 and September 2025 and will deliver **15 PhD degrees**, jointly supervised and trained in the public and private sectors. The Department of Urbanism was responsible for the scientific coordination of the project. The programme has delivered a successful **MOOC on open data**, several **dissertations**, seven **peer-reviewed articles**, edited **workshop proceedings**, three **keynote lectures** at major open data events in Aalborg (+800 visitors) and Luxembourg (+550 visitors and online attendees), and many other presentations at conferences, workshops, and seminars. A **position paper** was presented to the Dutch Deputy Secretary General of the Ministry of Internal Affairs as input for the **new Dutch open data vision**. An Urbanism Department member is part of the National Steering Group Open Data, connected to the ministries of the Interior and of Economic Affairs, respectively.

FIG. 4.9 The Municipality of Amsterdam is building a digital copy of the city: 3D Amsterdam. It consists of a 3D model of the city, various functionalities and an interactive web viewer (image: 3D.Amsterdam.nl). The Urban Climate Grove in the forecourt of the Faculty of Architecture & the Built Environment (image: Frans Snijder).

The Department also extends its role as a **knowledge hub for Data-supported Urbanism** with the 3D Urban Understanding Laboratory (3DUU) within the TU Delft AI Labs programme. Advances in 3D sensing, photogrammetry, and computer vision enable large-scale capture of urban environments as images or point clouds. However, creating robust semantic 3D models remains challenging. The 3DUU Lab develops automated techniques that integrate aerial and ground data to reconstruct, localise, and recognise urban objects like buildings, trees, and roads. Combining data from different sources and using AI allows computers to learn and work with them so that large amounts of urban data can be automatically processed and interpreted. The lab's work is widely recognised, with 11 **peer-reviewed papers**, 5 **invited talks** (a.o. for @GoogleResearch and @Huawei Research Europe), and 8 **GitHub repositories with source code and data**. Research outputs are also applied in master's courses by the 3D Geoinformation group.

City River Spaces (CRiSp) (2023-2025) is a research software project that developed a **stable release of the open-source research software** *rcrisp*, used for the automated morphological delineation of urban river spaces, with a wide range of applications for integrated local analysis and global cross-case analysis. The software *rcrisp* is currently undergoing [gold-badge rOpenSci statistical software review]. The CRiSp project also led to the organisation of the **'Tracing Sustainable Urban River Space Transformations' international workshop at the Lorentz Centre** in Leiden, which aided the international validation of the *rcrisp* software and led to a **position paper** on sustainable urban river space transformations. *rcrisp* is increasingly employed in education, and the Department is exploring **applications with societal partners** such as PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency and Rijkswaterstaat.

Integrative Transitional Urbanism

This theme brings together research and design responding to urgent and intertwined societal challenges, including climate change, the energy transition, environmental degradation, biodiversity loss, questions of food and material security, and human well-being. **Rooted in a socio-ecological understanding**, this work focuses on advancing human and ecological well-being by investigating how nature, space, and place conditions can be mobilised for inclusive design across scales, from the building to the macro-region. We examine how the physical structure of cities affects **resource demand, climate resilience, human comfort, biodiversity and accessibility**. We also view morphology as a design field, as reshaping these structures foster a circular territorial metabolism, low-carbon living, and healthier, restorative, liveable environments, and help address place-based trade-offs across multiple transitions. A defining feature of this line of work is its **integrative and practice-oriented approach**: we combine quantitative insights, spatial and system analysis, urban climate modelling and engagement with public and professionals to develop **place-based pathways for transition**.

The Interreg project **ASSET – A spatial Strategy for the EuroDelta: Boosting the circular Built Environment** (2024-2025) is an example of how the research and teaching activities on circular regional development of the Department and faculty were further developed to respond to the call of Dutch, Flemish and German regional and local planning authorities. They cannot address the circularity transition on their own, and space limitations and competing spatial claims require new ways of macro-regional spatial planning. The project developed **three inspiring spatial visions for the EURO Delta**, culminating in the signing of the EURODelta Alliance, in which representatives of ASSET partners signed the Letter of Intent (LOI) as founding partners, establishing these organisations' commitment to further work and collaboration on the scale of the EuroDelta, to develop macro-regional spatial strategies for circularity and beyond. Amongst others, the project developed a Circular Design Atlas with best practices and a final report (in two parts) featuring general outcomes, **design principles, inspirational visions, a roadmap for a spatial strategy** for a Circular Built EuroDelta, and **(policy) recommendations** for relevant stakeholders. An **edited volume and a journal special issue** are underway. The province of Zuid-Holland collaborated intensively with our Urbanism MSc track to test the idea of developing regional spatial strategies for the circularity transition.

The 4TU **HEat Robustness In relation To AGEing cities (HERITAGE)** programme aims to develop a high-tech sensing and design system for detecting, reducing, and preventing **heat stress** (by monitoring and design) in ageing built environments and buildings in Dutch cities, through socio-technical solutions. This integrated system will detect and forecast spatiotemporal patterns of heat stress at unprecedented resolution (1m scale). The **HERITAGE** programme is actively engaging with the Dutch cities of Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Delft, Enschede, and Eindhoven through **Living Labs**, employing quantitative (airborne) measurements and qualitative methods to assess increased heat in urban environments. The project has generated significant national and international exposure for its research and the relevance of urban heat through media outreach, policy advice, and scientific events.

FIG. 4.10 Members from the CitizenVoice initiative presenting the Bio-CiVo project on biodiversity, during the 2025 Spring Festival in Mathenesse, Rotterdam (image courtesy of Isabella Jaramillo Diaz).

The Department of Urbanism was also in the lead in organising the 12th International Conference on Urban Climate in Rotterdam (July 2025), which attracted **more than 900 participants**. The project also renders **policy advice** to Dutch ministries involved in climate adaptation (e.g., Nationale aanpak Klimaatadaptatie gebouwde omgeving fase 1 and the Landelijke maatlat groene, klimaatadaptieve gebouwde omgeving).

The **Urban Comfort Lab**, a close collaboration between Urbanism researchers and the Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS), investigates how architectural and urban design shape the propagation and human perception of **aircraft noise** in cities. The Urban Comfort Lab is a field lab built from more than 120 shipping containers near Amsterdam Schiphol Airport, stacked in the shape of three streets or courtyards, and packed with sensors. The field lab examines the roles of spatial morphology, materiality, and greenery, using data-driven sensing across climate, acoustics, air quality, and atmospheric domains to understand the interactions that define outdoor comfort. Results highlight the importance of spatial form, landscape design, and surface materials. Outputs include **open-source datasets for validating noise, air quality, and climate models**, publications on **spatial-noise relationships, computational mapping frameworks, and integrated urban comfort design** near airports. The project was extensively covered by national radio and television (BNR News Radio, Parool, Trouw, Volkskrant, Radio 1, and Klokhuis, an educational programme for children).

CitizenVoice is a rapidly growing initiative at TU Delft (founded in Urbanism) that aims to empower citizens and communities in urban planning and design by fostering inclusive and meaningful participation and open data practices.

It is a prime example of **bottom-up organisation and funding** (more than €150k acquired and more than 20 people involved). CitizenVoice developed several research projects, ranging from qualitative studies to design and arts-based approaches, as well as community-based and transdisciplinary research. These projects resulted in academic and non-academic **publications**, citizen participation and the organisation of several public events and conferences. **Five workshop events** have engaged more than 100 people with Citizen Voice prototypes, contributing to methodological debates on ethical and meaningful digital engagement and data use. Its deep commitment to **open research and open-source technologies** counterweights the increasing commodification of urban data and knowledge. Research-quality infrastructure set up with source code is made available in the open GitHub repository. Other project outputs are available via Zenodo. Importantly, CitizenVoice also fed into other relatively small but highly engaging and impactful projects, such as Citizens Meet Climate, Cmc, Bio-CiVo, ParticipAlte, Citizen Mapping Tool, CIVILIAN, and Beat the Heat. CitizenVoice contributed to UP2030, where it was included in the catalogue of tools for net-zero initiatives in cities.

CitizenVoice is also a great example of a cross-cutting collaboration that spans across the themes and sections in the Department of Urbanism. It could have been easily mentioned in the Inclusive Urbanism, Green Urbanism or Data-supported Urbanism theme as well.

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The Urban Climate Grove in the forecourt of TU Delft's Faculty of Architecture & the Built Environment

(Image: Frans Snijder)

